

Acceptance type: Keynote

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Building the world's first Ash2Phos plant in Schkopau, Germany

Yariv Cohen

EasyMining, Uppsala, Sweden

Yariv Cohen

What is your current position?

Head of R&D

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Yariv Cohen

Head of Research and Development at EasyMining . Is a specialist in chemical separation technologies and has a long experience in phosphorus chemistry. Obtained his Doctoral Degree from SLU University in Sweden with the title "Phosphorus recovery from urban wastes and ashes". Was awarded the 2008 Science Technology and Environmental Award from the King of Sweden. Was awarded the 2019 Chemical Engineering Award from the Swedish Society of Chemical Engineers.

Short abstract

EasyMining has developed the Ash2Phos process for phosphorus recovery from sludge ash. Phosphorus is recovered as pure calcium phosphate named RevoCaP that can be used as slow-release fertiliser, animal feed phosphate or further processed into conventional fertilisers. Co-products are ferric chloride, aluminium chemicals and a sand fraction. Heavy metals are separated for disposal.

Phosphorgewinnung Schkopau GmbH a joint venture by GELSENWASSER AG and EasyMining is building the first Ash2Phos plant at the Schkopau Chemical Park in the Saxony-Anhalt region in eastern Germany with a capacity of 30 000 ton ash from incinerated sewage sludge per year.

Leveraging Organic Acids in Bipolar Membrane Electrodialysis (BPMED) can Enhance Ammonia Recovery from Scrubber Effluents

Gladys Mutahi, Henri Spanjers, Jules van Lier
Delft University of Technology, Delft, Netherlands

Gladys Mutahi

What is your current position?

PhD Candidate

Short biography of the presenter

I am a Kenyan Ph.D. candidate in my fourth year at Delft University of Technology in the Netherlands. My research focuses on recovering ammonia from wastewater streams using electro dialysis with bipolar membranes. With a background in Environmental Engineering (BSc, University of Nairobi, Kenya) and Water Technology (MSc, Wetsus Academy, the Netherlands), I am passionate about resource recovery and advancing circular economies and sustainability. Previously, I have conducted research on recovering phosphorus and nitrogen from wastewater streams.

Short abstract

Ammonia, a major pollutant, can be removed from waste streams through stripping, followed by acid scrubbing, recovering it as a salt. Organic acids are feasible alternatives to strong mineral acids, but result to increased operational costs. This study proposes a novel approach to simultaneously recover ammonia and regenerate organic acids from scrubber effluents using bipolar membrane electro dialysis (BPMED). Our findings demonstrate that substituting sulphuric acid with organic acids for ammonia recovery significantly reduces energy consumption in the subsequent BPMED process by over 35 %. Moreover, the regenerated organic acids can be recycled, minimizing the high costs associated with their use.

Recovery of trivalent Chromium in the electroplating industry with a novel Hybrid Batch Reverse Osmosis system

Tuur van den Eijnde

Nijhuis Saur Industries, Doetinchem, Netherlands

Tuur van den Eijnde

What is your current position?

Teamleader R&D

Short biography of the presenter

Teamleader R&D

Short abstract

Hybrid Batch Reverse Osmosis (HBRO) is an innovative membrane-based technology optimized for energy-efficient water treatment. Operating at pressures up to 120 bars, it has been implemented at an electroplating facility in Germany for the automotive industry. This system enables the recovery of valuable resources, such as trivalent chromium, from electrolyte rinsing baths, a material for which there are limited treatment options. Other valuable components like complexing and swelling agents are also recovered. The potential to reuse the permeate as rinsing solution makes HBRO a promising solution for Zero Liquid Discharge applications, offering significant environmental and economic benefits.

Cobalt accumulation in methanogenic granular sludge: a potential biorecovery strategy?

Olga Sojka¹, Dainis Sudmalis², M. Cristina Gagliano¹

¹Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ²Wageningen University and Research, Wageningen, Netherlands

M. Cristina Gagliano

What is your current position?

Theme Coordinator Biofilms

Short biography of the presenter

I am an environmental microbiologist who worked in the field of anaerobic digestion during my PhD (IRSA CNR, Italy) and postdoctoral research (Wageningen University and Research, Netherlands). Working at Wetsus now for 8 years, my research focus on many shapes of biofilms, from the “bad” ones growing in drinking water environments, to the positive ones used in bioreactors/biofilters for (waste)water treatment. My expertise is on the extracellular polymeric substance (EPS) characterization, with a combination of multiple microscopy techniques, to study the structure and explore the function of complex microbial communities in several conditions, from oligotrophic to nutrients-rich ones.

Short abstract

Cobalt is a rare metal essential for production of batteries/electronics, recovery of which is becoming crucial. Past studies have shown that methanogenic granules from anaerobic bioreactors can accumulate cobalt. In this study, we investigated the potential to accumulate cobalt in granules formed from two different microbial inocula in saline conditions, believed to promote this. Our results showed that cobalt was indeed accumulated during 120 days of operation, possibly associated either with the extracellular polymeric substances (EPS), the biominerals fraction, or the enzymatic cobamides cofactors of acetotrophic methanogens. Anaerobic granules can become effective sorbents to recover cobalt at minute concentrations.

Activation of sludge char and its use in micropollutant removal in wastewater treatment

Sini Reuna, Niilo Kasanen, Kati Blomberg, Maria Valtari
Helsinki Region Environmental Services Authority HSY, Helsinki, Finland

Sini Reuna

What is your current position?

project engineer

Short biography of the presenter

Sini Reuna is working as a project engineer in Helsinki Region Environmental Services Authority. There her tasks include the development of the RAVITA™ process related to the recovery of nutrients from wastewater. She graduated from the University of Jyväskylä in 2022 with a PhD in Chemistry.

Short abstract

Helsinki Region Environmental Services (HSY) has studied the pyrolysis of sludge and its application to the removal of micropollutants from wastewater. The sludge char produced in the pyrolysis pilot was physically activated, increasing its surface area. Activated char material was used to remove micropollutants from the effluent wastewater. The tests measured the concentrations of twelve micropollutants, which are listed as indicator micropollutants in Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive. At best, a reduction of over 90% was achieved for all micropollutants. In addition, the dissolution of phosphorus from char material was studied.

Advancing the Next Generation of Phosphorus Recovery through Struvite Recovery Optimization and Operational Innovation

Rudy Maltos, Dan Freedman, Tanja Rauch-Williams, Liam Cavanaugh, Rylee Rubino
Metro Water Recovery, Denver, USA

Rudy Maltos

What is your current position?

Staff Process Engineer

Short biography of the presenter

Rudy Maltos, an adventurous PhD graduate from Colorado School of Mines, he applies his passion and excitement to the intricate world of process engineering at Metro Water Recovery. When he's not refining densification processes for activated sludge or optimizing phosphorus recovery techniques, you'll find him enthusiastically supporting the Denver Nuggets or navigating Colorado's white water rapids. Rudy's passion for applied research and zest for adventure make him a dynamic force in both his professional and personal pursuits.

Short abstract

Metro Water Recovery's Robert W. Hite Treatment Facility in Denver, Colorado, focuses on enhancing phosphorus recovery within its Mag/AirPrex reactor through three key objectives: maximizing struvite recovery, minimizing struvite buildup in effluent lines, and reducing polymer demand during dewatering. Operating conditions such as HRT, pH, and Mg:P ratios were modified, increasing struvite recovery from 136 to 545 kg/day. New infrastructure, including PVDF liners, addresses struvite buildup. Residual magnesium at 50 mg/L within the centrifuge-feed lines reduced polymer use by 30%. Conductivity and zeta potential were identified as tools for real-time monitoring, improving system performance and efficiency.

Recovery of Lithium Resources from Shale Gas Wastewater in China

Baicang Liu

College of Architecture and Environment, Chengdu, China

Baicang Liu

What is your current position?

Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Baicang Liu received his bachelor's degree from Wuhan University in 2004 and his Ph.D. degree from Harbin Institute of Technology in 2009. Then, he joined Sichuan University as an Assistant Professor (2009-2013), Associate Professor (2013-2018), and Professor (2018~). From 2011 to 2012, he worked in John C. Crittenden's group at Georgia Tech as a Visiting Scholar. He has published over 120 papers. He was awarded 4 grants from National Natural Science Foundation of China. He focused on shale gas flowback and produced water (FPW) on regional water quality and management strategies for reuse.

Short abstract

Firstly, we summarized the development trends of global lithium resources in different industries over the past 10 years, as well as the distribution and reserves of lithium resources. Then we conducted an in-depth analysis of the development history of China's shale gas industry and the lithium concentration in its wastewater, and compare the applicability of different lithium extraction technologies. Finally, we developed high-performance lithium-ion adsorbents based on aluminum, manganese, and titanium systems, and carried out a series of performance testing experiments.

Industrial scale polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) production, are we ready?

Ruizhe Pei^{1,2,3}, Erik de Vries², Ángel Estévez^{1,2,4}, João Sousa⁵, Henk Dijkman⁵, Jelmer Tamis⁵, Alan Werker^{1,2,6}

¹Delft University of Technology, Delft, Netherlands. ²Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ³University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria. ⁴Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium. ⁵Paques Biomaterials, Balk, Netherlands. ⁶University of Queensland, St. Lucia, Australia

Ruizhe Pei

What is your current position?

Postdoc

Short biography of the presenter

Ruizhe Pei is the Chair of the IWA Young Water Professionals Switzerland Chapter and a postdoctoral researcher at the University of Vienna. His research focuses on using microbial ecology to enhance wastewater treatment processes and develop next-generation treatment plants with improved circularity. With a background in environmental engineering, he has experience in both fundamental and applied research, collaborating with public agencies and private technology providers. His expertise in bioprocess design, resource recovery, and microbial ecology helps bridge research with societal challenges.

Short abstract

Scalability of polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) production using waste activated sludge (WAS) was critically evaluated in parallel testing at pilot (200 L) and demonstration (4 m³) scales. Production performance, PHA maximum content and production yields, were similar demonstrating method robustness and technology scalability. Successful industrial upscaling needs temperature and foaming control. Additionally, feedstock composition reproducibly determined co-polymer composition and blend distribution. Green solvent extraction methods yielded consistent product quality and offers ways for the downstream quality control. Overall, Technological readiness for WAS-based PHA production was successfully demonstrated. Establishing long term supply chains will be critical for next steps of industrial implementation.

Upscaled open-culture production of microbial flocculants from industrial wastewaters

Carlos Contreras-Davila¹, Dainis Sudmalis², Cees Buisman¹

¹Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ²Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, Netherlands

Carlos Contreras-Davila

What is your current position?

Scientific Project Manager

Short biography of the presenter

Carlos works part-time as Scientific Project Manager at Wetsus and as Process Specialist in Paques. He holds a PhD degree from Wageningen University where he worked at the department of Environmental Technology. Carlos is specialized in microbial fermentation processes for carbon recovery into valuable products such as carboxylic acids and exopolymers.

Short abstract

Flocculants are used for solid-liquid separation in (waste)water treatment and many industrial sectors. However, synthetic flocculants pose risks to the environment such as microplastics accumulation or release of toxic compounds. Microbially-secreted polymers with flocculation properties are emerging as biobased, nontoxic alternatives. This study shows the feasibility to long-term produce exopolymers (EPS) at high efficiency (up to 40% COD-fed) in two bench-scale bioreactors (MBR, chemostat) from glycerol, biodiesel wastewater and hydrolyzed starch. High molecular weight is linked to better flocculation performance of EPS (up to 94% turbidity removal on dual-clay). These results help to guide future engineering of microbially-produced flocculants.

From Innovation to Implementation: Success Factors in Resource Recovery

Olaf van der Kolk, Jouke Boorsma
AquaMinerals, Nieuwegein, Netherlands

Olaf van der Kolk

What is your current position?

Director

Short biography of the presenter

Olaf's been involved in recycling from the beginning of his career. Last 13 years he has been working at AquaMinerals, giving residuals from water treatment a second life. Last years his emphasis has been on circular use of these residuals, with use within the water sector as priority.

Short abstract

This presentation delves into the critical factors that determine the success or failure of resource recovery innovations. Based on an analysis of 100 projects evaluated against 14 criteria, it reveals key patterns and lessons learned. While scientific research in this field is limited, existing theories and frameworks offer valuable guidance. Practical examples, both successes and failures, illustrate the importance of collaboration, timing, and market readiness in achieving implementation. Attendees will gain actionable insights to navigate common pitfalls and apply success factors effectively, empowering them to drive impactful resource recovery innovations and contribute to a sustainable, circular economy.

Unlocking the Potential of Kaamera biopolymer: From Wastewater to Marketable Resource

Sjoerd Kerstens Martijn Bovee^{1,2}, Eric Van der Zandt³, Rudi Gerard⁴, René Noppeney¹, Paul Roeleveld¹, Julian Muñoz Sierra⁵, Martijn Bovee⁶

¹Royal HaskoningDHV, Amersfoort, Netherlands. ²Kaamera sales & services BV, Nieuwegein, Netherlands. ³HDSR, Houten, Netherlands. ⁴Waterschap Rijn en IJssel, Doetinchem, Netherlands. ⁵KWR, Nieuwegein, Netherlands. ⁶

Sjoerd Kerstens Martijn Bovee

What is your current position?

Leading Professional on wastewater treatment and resource recovery

Short biography of the presenter

Sjoerd is a Leading Professional at Royal HaskoningDHV working on innovative wastewater concepts that allow for resource recovery and reuse of effluent. Since 2003, he has worked on a range of industrial projects, sanitation projects in Asia and the development of the Nereda technology. He holds a PhD from WUR on "Sanitation planning in developing countries; added value of resource recovery". He has been a lecture at WUR and WETSUS Academy on aerobic wastewater treatment and other topics related to the circular economy.

Short abstract

Following the application of full scale Nereda Aerobic Granular Sludge plants in 2007, interest appeared in the extraction of extracellular polymeric substances. These biopolymers from Nereda sludge are the product Kaamera®. The versatility of Kaamera is promising, with opportunities in agriculture, construction, and various industrial sectors. The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the extraction was scaled from lab (2010) to pilot (2017-2018), leading to two extraction units in 2019 and 2020. This update details how, besides TRL, we increase the Resource Maturity Index of Kaamera, addressing commercial, legal, and social readiness through a company (Kaamera Sales & Services BV) with 4 Dutch water authorities and Royal HaskoningDHV.

Valorisation of Brines and Scrap Metals for Coagulant Production to Boost Circular Economy in the Water Sector

Eleonora Paissoni¹, Feliu Sempere², Tatiana Montoya², Enrique Escrig², Francisco Bosch³, Silvia Oyonarte³, Laura Grima³, Arturo Doménech⁴, Víctor Doménech⁴, Elvira Serra¹, Babi Uku¹, Blanca Antizar¹

¹Isle Utilities, London, United Kingdom. ²Global Omnium Medioambiente, Valencia, Spain. ³AIDIMME, Valencia, Spain.

⁴Creaciones Joviar, Ibi, Spain

Feliu Sempere

What is your current position?

R&D Engineer

Short biography of the presenter

Chemical Engineer from the University of València (Spain) with a PhD and postdoc secondment based on the development of a marketable biotechnology for the elimination of solvents in air emissions, work carried out at laboratory, pilot, and industrial scale. He has experience as process and R&D engineer since 2006 in different sectors related to environmental engineering with a clear approach on upscaling biological, physical, and chemical processes. In 2019 he joined the Wastewater Innovation department of Global Omnium, where he received a postdoc contract from the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation to develop a biological biogas purification process.

Blanca Antizar

What is your current position?

Director of Consultancy, Europe, Africa and Latin America

Short biography of the presenter

Professor Blanca Antizar is a leading expert in water security and resource recovery. As Director of Consultancy at Isle Utilities Ltd and Royal Academy of Engineering Visiting Professor at UCL, she bridges the gap between research and real-world impact. With over 20 years of experience, she collaborates with technology pioneers, end-users, and investors on global projects like the World Bank's Utility of the Future program. Her work has been recognized with numerous awards, including the 2022 iAgua award for 'Woman of the Year' in the water sector. Blanca holds a PhD in Civil and Environmental Engineering from the Technion-IIT, Israel.

Short abstract

The Electrolytic System (ELS), developed by the LIFE Waste2Coag project, valorises brines from desalination and demineralisation processes (often discharged untreated to the environment) via electrolysis using scrap metals as electrodes, while producing metal-based coagulants for wastewater treatment. ELS coagulants, non-toxic to wastewater bacteria, have metal concentrations of 1200 mgFe/l and 700-1000 mgAl/l. The effectiveness of ELS coagulants has been demonstrated achieving high removal (>92%) of heavy metals, such as Cu, Ni, Zn and Cr(IV), from industrial wastewater, providing an alternative to commercial coagulants (global coagulant consumption is estimated at \$7,134 million/year) and supporting circular economy practices.

Closing the loop: microalgae for digestate valorisation and as co-substrate for the anaerobic digestion of agri-food industry by-products.

Miguel Martínez-Quintela¹, Beatriz Ascencio¹, Sandra M. Masías¹, Mabel Mora¹, Josué González-Camejo¹, Herminia De la Varga², Maribel Calvo³, Ignasi Salaet²

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Miguel Martínez-Quintela

What is your current position?

Post-Doctoral Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Miguel Martínez Quintela is a chemical engineer, with a master's degree in biotechnology and a PhD in chemical and environmental engineering from the University of Santiago de Compostela. In his thesis he worked on the study of emerging contaminants (pharmaceuticals, personal care products, etc.) and antibiotic resistance in biological water treatment systems. At BETA TC he is working in the environmental technologies line, in the development of technologies for the valorisation of water and industrial waste, mainly from the agri-food industry.

Josué González-Camejo

What is your current position?

Postdoctoral researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Josué González Camejo is a chemical engineer and holds a PhD in Hydraulic Engineering and Environment from Universitat Politècnica de Valencia (Spain), also having 3-year of international experience at Università Politecnica delle Marche (Ancona, Italy). He is currently a postdoctoral researcher at BETA centre (Spain) and his main lines of research are related to wastewater treatment and reuse and biorefineries based on microalgae.

Short abstract

This work presents an innovative strategy following a zero-waste approach to valorise some agri-food industry by-products by coupling anaerobic co-digestion with microalgae cultivation processes. The resulting side-streams of a 100-L pilot-scale co-digester (digestate and CO₂) are used to cultivate microalgae in a 250-L raceway pond. The loop is finally closed by applying the resulting microalgae (once cultivated, harvested and hydrolysed) as co-substrate for the anaerobic digestion. Within this biorefinery approach, reclaimed water, energy, concentrate with potential agronomic value and algae-based biostimulants were obtained.

Translating Electrochemical Ammonia Stripping to Practice: Long-term operation and early steps toward commercialization

Kindle Williams, Brandon Clark, Anna Kogler, William Tarpeh
Stanford University, Stanford, CA, USA

Kindle Williams

What is your current position?

Postdoctoral Scholar

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Kindle Williams is a postdoctoral researcher in chemical engineering at Stanford University. She focuses on scale-up, translation, and commercialization of electrochemical nutrient recovery technologies and is currently building a company called Recovered Potential to that end. Kindle completed her B.S. in chemical engineering and chemistry at the University of Alabama and her M.S.CEP and Ph.D. in chemical engineering at MIT, where she studied electrocatalysis for CO₂ valorization, organic electrosynthesis, and the fundamentals of blended electrolyte systems. She lives in Mountain View, CA with her partner and enjoys cycling, gardening, and public transit.

Short abstract

Nitrogen recovery from wastewaters can help circularize the nitrogen economy, reducing overall energy and chemical consumption, GHG emissions, and costs. Electrochemical stripping (ECS) has been developed as a modular ammonia recovery process. We have demonstrated long-term ECS operation, as well as performance with a variety of wastewaters such as source-separated urine, anaerobic digestate, and reverse osmosis concentrate. This talk will address recent advances in membrane fouling mitigation and system energy requirement reduction as well as pilot-scale operation, potential markets for adoption, and effective business models, leaning into the value of cost-effective nitrogen removal with recovered product sales subsidizing wastewater treatment.

The forgotten nutrient - new approaches towards potassium (K) recovery

Cora Eichholz, Almut Hönerloh, Sica Liesegang, Heidrun Steinmetz
University of Kaiserslautern-Landau (RPTU), Kaiserslautern, Germany

Cora Eichholz

What is your current position?

Research assistant

Short biography of the presenter

10/2018-10/2021: Master of Science in Civil Engineering at the Technical University of Berlin. Major: Urban Water Management, Water Resources Management and Modelling of Hydrosystems

11/2021-06/2024: Research Assistant at the Technical University University of Berlin. Department for Urban Water Management

Since 08/2024: Research Assistant at the University of Kaiserslautern-Landau (RPTU). Department for Resource Efficient Wastewater Technology

Short abstract

We live in an era with enormous dependence on resources, causing environmental destruction and political dependencies. To ensure food security, nutrients must remain available for fertilisation everywhere, potassium (K) being one of them. So far, research into nutrient recovery from wastewater has focussed on N and P, while K rushes through wastewater treatment plants. To date, hardly any studies on K recovery from wastewater have been described in literature. First promising results on recovery of potassium via ion exchange from own investigations will be presented and discussed towards the current state of K recovery, which slowly gains attention in research.

Circular fertilisers from sanitation, urban wastewater, and agri-food industry process water

Kees Roest¹, Kimo van Dijk², Wim van Dijk², Willem van Geel³, Tiemen Nanninga⁴, Frank Oesterholt¹

¹KWR Water Research Institute, Nieuwegein, Netherlands. ²Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, Netherlands. ³Wageningen University & Research, Lelystad, Netherlands. ⁴LeAF, Wageningen, Netherlands

Kees Roest

What is your current position?

Senior Scientific Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Kees Roest has worked at KWR Water Research Institute since 2008 and was among the pioneers in KWR's wastewater research. On the Energy and Circular Systems team he works on sustainable transitions with a focus on innovative (waste)water treatment concepts and the reuse of water, energy, and materials. Kees is managing the KWR TKI Water Technology program for public-private partnerships (PPPs) and is portfolio manager resource recovery and circular systems issues at KWR. Kees has a Ph.D. in Environmental Microbiology from WUR.

Short abstract

The applied research project focuses on circular, sustainable and safe fertilizers. It includes field trials with promising recovered nitrogen-rich fertilizers of different origins, including aerobic biomass from the potato, sugar, beer and dairy industries and various flows from the urban wastewater chain, including black water, nitrified source-separated human urine, sludge ash products and nitrogen solutions from sewage treatment plants. The results of this field trial are integrated with the development of an assessment framework for guaranteeing the quality and safety of recovered fertilizers, and evaluate their compliance within the legal framework.

Managed aquifer recharge as low-cost and nature-based tertiary treatment for urban wastewater

Miriam Tena¹, Javier Rico², Karen Mora³, Patricia Zamora⁴, Patricio Herмосilla⁵, Victor Monsalvo⁴, Lourdes Martinez-Landa^{6,7}, Cristina Valhondo^{8,6}, Silvia Diaz⁸, Jesus Carrera^{8,6}, Frank Rogalla⁴

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Miriam Tena

What is your current position?

R&D technician

Short biography of the presenter

Miriam Tena Villares, who holds a PhD in Agri-Food Resources from the University of Cadiz, earned an Excellent Cum Laude distinction and an award for her thesis on hydrogen and methane coproduction through codigestion of biosolids and vinasse. She specializes in enhancing anaerobic digestion of sewage sludge, with her research published in high-impact journals and presented at conferences. As a postdoctoral researcher, she validated lab studies on a pilot plant scale. Currently, she works in Aqualia's R&D department, contributing to European projects on anaerobic digestion and wastewater treatment processes.

Patricia Zamora

What is your current position?

Senior Project manager

Short biography of the presenter

Patricia is a Senior R&D Project Manager and Researcher at Aqualia, currently leading several European projects dealing with resource recovery and energy production from wastewater. Her education is a Bachelor in Chemical Engineering (2005), PhD in Analytical Chemistry (2012) and Master's Degree in Occupational Risk Prevention (3 specialities), Environmental and Quality Management (2006).

Short abstract

The MARadentro project employs managed aquifer recharge (MAR) through infiltration ponds designed to recharge reclaimed water from the effluent of the Medina del Campo wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) in Valladolid, Spain. This approach not only serves as a resource management method by enabling the storage and recovery of groundwater bodies but also acts as a natural tertiary treatment system, requiring no energy consumption and presenting itself as a nature-based solution (NBS) to promote water reuse.

Industrial wastewater reuse: a comparison of laundry and paper mill case studies in Estonia

Kris-Robin Sirge¹, [Laura Laurelli](#)¹, Asya Drenkova-Tuhtan²

¹Spacedrip OÜ, Tallinn, Estonia. ²National Institute of Chemical Physics and Biophysics (KBFI), Tallinn, Estonia

Laura Laurelli

What is your current position?

Water technologist

Short biography of the presenter

Laura Laurelli is a water technologist and consultant. She leads water monitoring and compliance activities, contributes to research and development activities, data analysis, and technical documentation at Spacedrip. Previously, she completed an internship at Tallinn Water drinking water department with hands-on tasks in potable water production technologies, including data collection and process optimization. With a BSc in Environmental Technology and various industry certifications, Laurelli is committed to advancing water technology and sustainable solutions. She is part of a research project on preservation, long-term storage and revitalization of vacuum freeze-dried activated sludge for rapid inoculation of a bioreactor.

Short abstract

The EU Water Reuse Regulation 2020/741 sets minimum requirements for the quality of reclaimed water, thus addressing the necessity to reduce the significant freshwater consumption by industries and agriculture. We present a comparison of two case studies from Estonia with 100-250 m³/d daily wastewater production, out of which 50-74 m³/d are reused. In 2024-2025, wastewater treatment plants utilizing aerobic membrane bioreactor (MBR) technology were installed at the factories. This work outlines the effluent water quality, technology compliance, and discusses the challenges and lessons learned throughout the projects, offering insights into the early stage implementation of industrial wastewater reuse.

Phosphorus recovery as vivianite from sludge

Outi Grönfors¹, Martijn van Leusden², Saskia Hanneman³, Vesa Vuori¹

¹Kemira Oyj, Espoo, Finland. ²Royal HaskoningDHV, Amersfoort, Netherlands. ³Waterboard Limburg, Roermond, Netherlands

Outi Grönfors

What is your current position?

Application Development Manager, Water treatment

Short biography of the presenter

Application Development Manager in water treatment, with a demonstrated history of working in the chemical industry more than 20 years. Leading phosphorus recovery project ViviMag® in Kemira. Enthusiastic about sustainable solutions and resource recovery.

Short abstract

A novel technology ViviMag® has been demonstrated successfully in industrial trials at municipal wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) to recover phosphorus magnetically from sewage sludge. Up to 60% of the phosphorus present in the influent of the WWTP can be recovered. The method is compliant with the phosphorus removal targets of the more stringent revised urban wastewater treatment directive through the dual role of iron in removing phosphorus and enabling the recovery even above 80% of the vivianite. ViviMag® will be scaled up to a first of its kind full-scale demonstration plant in the Netherlands.

From Organic Waste to Membranes: Enhanced PHA Production and Sustainable Membrane Fabrication

Yizhou Xing Liang-Shin Wang^{1,2,3}, Robbert Kleerebezem³, Mark van Loosdrecht³, Zandrie Borneman², Kitty Nijmeijer², Alan Werker^{1,4}

¹Wetsus, European Centre of Excellence for Sustainable Water Technology, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ²Membrane Materials and Processes, Eindhoven University of Technology, Eindhoven, Netherlands. ³Department of Biotechnology, Delft University of Technology, Delft, Netherlands. ⁴School of Chemical Engineering, University of Queensland, Brisbane, Australia

Yizhou Xing Liang-Shin Wang

What is your current position?

PhD researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Liang-Shin is a PhD researcher at Wetsus and TU Eindhoven, focusing on polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) downstream processing and property tuning for membranes and films. Her research focuses on polymer-solvent interactions to optimize recovery and directly convert PHA into high-value functional materials through sustainable solvent-based processes.

Yizhou is a PhD researcher at Wetsus and TU Delft, focusing on optimizing PHA production using mixed microbial cultures like waste-activated sludge. His work provides insights on microbial competition to improve bioprocess performance and aims to develop sustainable, efficient solutions for biopolymer production and resource recovery.

Short abstract

This presentation includes principles for simultaneous selective growth of PHA-storing microorganisms in WAS, focusing on metabolic energy distribution during PHA synthesis. This selective growth significantly enhances PHA productivity. PHA content up to 60% of the organic matter were obtained in 24 hours in a direct PHA accumulation bioprocess simply starting from municipal WAS. The PHA is readily extractable from the dried biomass using greener non-halogenated solvents. A method for producing PHA-based membranes serves as an example of the approach to integrate PHA recovery directly with solution processing. Different types of PHA copolymer blends can be generated. The polymer interaction with the non-halogenated solvent are identified as key factors for tuning the membrane fabrication process and properties (i.e. barrier, mechanical, etc.). For example, to obtain dense homogeneous films, casting condition and solvent evaporation are to be carried out above the polymer-solvent gelation temperature. This research supports the upscaling of biopolymer production from organic waste, offering a path for waste valorisation and sustainable membrane production with quality control.

In situ lactate-driven medium-chain fatty acids production from real urban waste with natural buffering: substrate feeding regimen and products fate

Agata Gallipoli¹, Francesca Angelini¹, Michela Sbicego¹, Stefania Angelini¹, Andrea Gianico¹, Barbara Tonanzi^{1,2}, Simona Crognale^{1,2}, Marco Lazzazzara³, Giancarlo Cecchini³, Alessandro Frugis³, Simona Rossetti¹, [Camilla Maria Braguglia](#)¹
¹Water Research Institute, National Research Council (CNR-IRSA), Rome, Italy. ²National Biodiversity Future Center (NBFC), Palermo, Italy. ³Acea Infrastructure SpA, Rome, Italy

Agata Gallipoli

What is your current position?

Senior Technologist

Short biography of the presenter

Agata Gallipoli is Senior Technologist at the Water Research Institute of the Italian National Research Council (CNR-IRSA). She graduated in Chemistry at the University of Parma and obtained a PhD in Chemistry, Biochemistry and Ecology of Xenobiotics at the University of Milan. Her main research interests can be found in the environmental biotechnology area, in particular for biomass and waste treatment and anaerobic valorization (bioenergy production and resource recovery from organic waste and sludge). She is (co)-author of about 50 articles in peer-reviewed ISI Journals and co-inventor of a patent on biogas production from pretreated sludge and

Camilla Maria Braguglia

What is your current position?

Senior Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Camilla Braguglia is Senior Scientist of the Water Research Institute of the Italian National Research Council (CNR-IRSA). She graduated in Chemistry at the University of Rome La Sapienza and obtained a PhD in Industrial Chemical Processes from the same University. Her main research interests falls within the area of environmental biotechnology for waste minimization, decontamination and biomass valorization, in particular for bioenergy and chemicals production, with the aim to develop efficient and reliable technological solutions. She (co)-authored 90 articles in peer-reviewed ISI Journals and International Book chapters, and is co-inventor of a patent on sludge reduction and biogas production.

Short abstract

This study provides a comprehensive exploration of the chain elongation process for real urban waste through an open-culture biotechnological production platform without adding electron donors nor buffering agents. We developed a stable bioprocess implemented in a single bioreactor where the presence of food waste promoted the in situ production of lactate further converted into caproate in a natural buffered system thanks to the presence of sludge. Daily feeding strategy permitted to maximize caproic acid production and waste treatment, making it the most sustainable and economically viable option, despite a slight decrease in conversion efficiency with respect to the intermittent fasting.

IntensiCarb™: Transforming Anaerobic Digestion with Enhanced Loading and Resource Recovery

Ali Khadir¹, Eunkyung Jang², Domenico Santoro², John Walton², Ahmed Al-Omari³, Christopher Muller³, Katherine Y. Bell⁴, Wayne Parker⁵, George Nakhla¹

¹Western University, LONDON, Canada. ²USP technologies, LONDON, Canada. ³Brown and Caldwell, MA, USA. ⁴Brown and Caldwell, TN, USA. ⁵University of Waterloo, Waterloo, Canada

Domenico Santoro

What is your current position?

Director of Research at USP Technologies

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Domenico Santoro is the Director of Research at USP Technologies, a company specializing in innovative solutions for water and wastewater treatment. He is also an Adjunct Research Professor at Western University, where he collaborates on cutting-edge research in environmental and chemical engineering. Dr. Santoro has contributed significantly to advancing wastewater treatment strategies, ranging from disinfection/advanced oxidation to sludge treatment and sewer management.

Short abstract

IntensiCarb™ (IC) is a groundbreaking anaerobic digestion (AD) technology addressing challenges in scalability, efficiency, and resource recovery. By decoupling HRT and SRT through side-stream vacuum evaporation, IC enables organic loading rates 400–600% higher than conventional systems while maintaining methane yields at 0.2 L-CH₄/gCOD_{fed} (50% COD destruction) and stabilizing ammonia levels at 1.5 gN/L at OLR of 11.3 kgCOD/m³-d. IC recovered 43%-46% of total digester influent TKN fed as ammonia in a clean condensate. This transformative approach positions IC as a scalable, sustainable solution with reduced capital costs for wastewater treatment, maximizing energy and nutrient recovery and environmental stewardship.

Acceptance type: Oral

#1.2

From Microalgae to Biofertilizers: Resource Recovery from Wastewater to Minimize Inorganic Fertilizer Use

Enrica Uggetti, Ana Álvarez-González, [Etielle Morais](#)
Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain

Enrica Uggetti

What is your current position?

Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Enrica Uggetti holds a PhD in Civil Engineering, she is internationally recognized for her expertise in green solutions for waste and wastewater treatment and resources recovery. Her work focuses on innovative approaches such as constructed wetlands and microalgae-based treatment systems. Over her career, she has honed her skills in the design and operation of nature-based solutions for wastewater treatment, microalgae culture and biomass applications. She has been involved in numerous research and demo projects, and has co-authored more than 50 scientific publications. Her research interest is now focused on resource recovery from wastewater within the framework of a circular economy.

Etielle Morais

What is your current position?

Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Etielle Morais, a Food Engineer with a PhD in Food Science and Engineering, is a Ramón y Cajal researcher at the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC). She specializes in microalgae culture, downstream processing, and biomass applications across laboratory, pilot, and industrial scales. Since March 2022, she has been part of UPC's GEMMA group, focusing on cultivating microalgae in wastewater for full biomass valorization. Her research advances environmental biotechnology, contributing to waste treatment and bio-based product development, promoting sustainable and eco-friendly solutions.

Short abstract

Alternatives to inorganic fertilizers are needed due to economic, environmental, and policy challenges. Microalgae offer a sustainable solution by accumulating nutrients from wastewater. In this study, microalgae biomass was cultivated in real urban wastewater, and pot trials were performed comparing three scenarios: microalgae biofertilizers, inorganic fertilizers, and a combination of both. Results demonstrate that microalgae-based biofertilizers are not only feasible but also safe, environmentally advantageous, and economically viable. To fully realize their potential, supportive regulations and policies are needed to promote resource recovery and application, advancing a circular economy and closing the nutrient loop.

#2.28

Identifying key challenges and opportunities for expanding source-separating sanitation system

Albina Dioba, Anna Schmid, Isabel Fróes
Copenhagen Business School, Frederiksberg, Denmark

Albina Dioba

What is your current position?

Postdoctoral researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Albina Dioba holds a Ph.D. in Economics. Her research focuses on applying behavioral science to promote pro-environmental behavior change. Currently, as a postdoctoral fellow at the Sustainability Center of Copenhagen Business School, she involves in EU Horizon 2020 projects like P2GreeN and BECoop, emphasizing the circular economy, stakeholder engagement, and energy communities. Dr. Dioba also contributes to the CBS urban gardening initiative, Permahaven, with a focus on biodiversity conservation.

Short abstract

Here's the revised version incorporating the opportunities:

Source-separating sanitation systems offer a sustainable solution for resource recovery from wastewater while mitigating climate change. This paper ranks key challenges and opportunities for expanding these systems using a PESTEL framework and the analytical hierarchical process. Expert surveys highlighted major barriers, including limited support for ecosystem innovation, inconsistencies in policy implementation, and low social acceptance. Opportunities include implementing clear policy measures such as tax incentives to support circular economy initiatives and government solutions to assist start-ups and innovative SMEs. Proposed strategies also include fostering stakeholder engagement and strengthening municipal-utility collaboration for effective adoption

Sewage sludge-based Bio-Adhesive for Plywood

gaojun wang, Zhaofu Liu, Bo Zhang, Rong Chen
Xi'an University of Architecture and Technology, Xi'an, China

gaojun wang

What is your current position?

Associate Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Wang is an associate professor in Xi'an University of Architecture and Technology. His research interests include valuable products recovery from sewage sludge, PHA generation from bio-waste stream, biochar-assisted anaerobic digestion, and anaerobic membrane bioreactor. In these areas, Dr. Wang has published over 20 peer-reviewed journal papers with over 1500 citation, and one book chapter .

Short abstract

A proof-of-concept roadmap of sewage sludge (SS)-based bio-adhesive preparation was proposed. Citric acid outperformed H_2SO_4 for SS-protein (SSP) precipitation due to amidation reaction occurrence. After alkali modification, tannic acid/ Zn^{2+} were doped into SSP by cross-linking/coordination reactions, which re-assembling the fragmented peptide structure to perform excellent hydrophobicity, thermal stability and mold-resistance. Curing procedure facilitated the penetration of adhesive into woody pore, and boosted condensed network structures by shaping β -sheet formation and triggering esterification reaction, which generated a shear strength of plywood reaching 1.09MPa. The economic benefits and carbon neutrality potential of this roadmap were envisioned to consolidate practical significance.

Extracellular Polymeric Substances (EPS) extracted from aerobic granules as bioadhesives for sunflower bark particleboards: mechanical and thermal insulation Properties.

Jose Agustin REYES SALGADO¹, Ferial BACOU¹, Nicolas DERLON², Yolaine BESSIERE³, Elisabeth GIRBAL-NEUHAUSER⁴, Nathalie LEBLANC¹, Abdo Bou Sarkis¹

¹UniLaSalle Transformations and Agro-Ressources, Mont Saint Aignan, France. ²EAWAG, Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology, Dübendorf, Switzerland. ³TBI, Université de Toulouse, CNRS, INRAE, INSA, Toulouse, France. ⁴Université de Toulouse; UPS, LBAE, Laboratoire de Biotechnologies Agroalimentaire et Environnementale, URU 4565, Institut Universitaire de Technologie, Auch, France

Abdo Bou Sarkis

What is your current position?

Associate Professor in Biotechnology

Short biography of the presenter

Abdo Bou-Sarkis is a researcher specializing in the field of environmental biotechnology. His research focuses on the valorization of biological aggregates, particularly by extracting hydrogel-forming polymers such as Extracellular Polymeric Substances (EPS) from wastewater treatment processes. Currently, Abdo BOU-SARKIS is an Associate professor at UniLaSalle, teaching about the beneficial uses of microorganisms for environmental and food applications.

Short abstract

Particleboards can be used as thermal insulators in buildings. Urea-formaldehyde resins, currently used as adhesives, release harmful formaldehyde, impacting indoor air quality and health (Nguyen et al., 2018; Gibier et al., 2022). Alginate and Extracellular Polymeric Substances (EPS) from wastewater treatment are potential bioadhesive substitutes due to their similar biochemical compositions (Lin et al., 2010). Initial tests showed that adding 2.5g of alginate or EPS improved mechanical properties of particleboards. EPS from synthetic wastewater increased the Modulus of Rupture (MOR) threefold, while real wastewater EPS doubled it. Thermal conductivity remained unaffected, maintaining good insulation properties.

Green and High-Yield Recovery of Phosphorus from Municipal Wastewater for LiFePO_4 Batteries

Yijiao Chang, Lin Lin

Tsinghua Shenzhen International Graduate School, Tsinghua University, Shenzhen, China

Yijiao Chang

What is your current position?

PhD candidate

Short biography of the presenter

Yijiao Chang is a PhD candidate in Environmental Science and Engineering at Tsinghua University, specializing in sustainable resource recovery and solid waste management. The current research focuses on developing innovative methods for recovering phosphorus from municipal wastewater and repurposing it in high-value applications, addressing global resource scarcity while supporting sustainable energy solutions. Yijiao Chang has published 5 SCI papers on phosphorus recovery and green battery materials and is passionate about advancing environmentally friendly solutions to municipal waste challenges.

Short abstract

A sustainable method recovers phosphorus (P) from municipal wastewater to produce lithium iron phosphate (LiFePO_4) battery cathodes. Fe-based chemical phosphorus removal (CPR) sludge is converted into P-Fe oxides, substituting up to 35% of commercial FePO_4 . The resulting LiFePO_4/C cathodes deliver a specific discharge capacity of $114.9 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{h}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ and maintain 99.2% cycle stability over 100 cycles. This innovative approach not only addresses P scarcity but also provides a cost-effective solution for producing high-performance battery materials, supporting environmental sustainability.

Ammonia recovery with bipolar electro dialysis and vacuum stripping from anaerobic digestion reject water.

Iosif Kaniadakis, Jules van Lier, Henri Spanjers
Technical University of Delft, Delft, Netherlands

Iosif Kaniadakis

What is your current position?

PhD

Short biography of the presenter

Iosif Kaniadakis holds a BE in environmental engineering from UPatras in Greece. He completed his MSc studies in Wageningen University and Wetsus in the Netherlands. Currently he is on the 4th year of his PhD journey in TU Delft working on the utilization of bipolar electro dialysis and vacuum stripping for NH_3 recovery from reject water of anaerobic digestion. His research through the last years focused on nutrients removal via adsorption materials, electrochemical membrane processes for energy storage, resource recovery and membrane processes for physical separation.

Short abstract

Total ammoniacal nitrogen (TAN) is a significant component of reject water streams from anaerobic digestion processes. Its removal can be effectively achieved through electro dialysis, which transports TAN as NH_4^+ ion. By using electro dialysis to concentrate NH_4^+ , bipolar electro dialysis can then be integrated to generate an alkaline stream, recovering and converting NH_4^+ to NH_3 . The recovered NH_3 can be subsequently extracted from the alkaline solution via vacuum membrane stripping. Additionally, in-situ pH control enhances the stripping process while reducing energy consumption. The process faces the challenges of membrane organic fouling and fluxes of impurities in the stripping permeate.

Bioflocculant production from volatile fatty acid-rich and glycerol containing wastewaters

Berke Kisaoglan^{1,2}, M. Cristina Gagliano², Dainis Sudmalis³, Huub Rijnaarts³

¹Wageningen university and Research, Wageningen, Netherlands. ²Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ³Wageningen University and Research, Wageningen, Netherlands

Berke Kisaoglan

What is your current position?

Phd Student

Short biography of the presenter

I am a 4th year PhD student at Wetsus, working on natural bio flocculant production from wastewater. My background is chemical engineering and I completed my master 's degree in the field of algal biotechnology.

Short abstract

Synthetic flocculants are applied in coagulation/flocculation process to trigger agglomeration of particles. A major concern associated with them is their environmental impact. Due to their charge and ability to flocculate colloids, extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) are promising natural alternatives. Such EPS-derived bioflocculants can be produced during biological wastewater treatment, thereby offering an environmentally-friendly and cost-effective way for synthesis. Here, VFA-rich and glycerol-rich wastewaters were compared in continuous stirred (CSTR) and membrane (MBR) reactors for their potential to yield EPS with excellent flocculation ability in clay dispersions. Higher flocculation efficiency (91%) was obtained with EPS produced from VFA-rich streams.

Aqua2[®]N – Innovative Technology to Remove and Recover Nitrogen from Wastewater

Sido Altenburg¹, Yariv Cohen², [Lars Bergmann](#)¹

¹EasyMining, Gothenburg, Sweden. ²EasyMining, Uppsala, Sweden

Sido Altenburg

What is your current position?

Technical Sales Engineer

Short biography of the presenter

Sido has a BSc in Chemical Engineering and a MSc in Innovation Management. In the Netherlands he worked with industrial wwtp application, in the fertiliser industry and has done research on novel wwtp technologies at the Dutch Research Institute of the Netherlands (NIOO-KNAW). Before joining the EasyMining business development team, Sido worked within the R&D department at EasyMining focusing on phosphorus and nitrogen recovery.

Lars Bergmann

What is your current position?

Technical Sales Aqua2N

Short biography of the presenter

Lars Bergmann is an experienced entrepreneur and business leader with over 20 years of expertise in wastewater treatment, sustainable technologies and international project development. He is committed to advancing innovative solutions that bridge the gap between research, industry and real-world applications. Throughout his career, Lars has successfully led multicultural businesses and teams across Europe, North America, Asia and Africa, spearheading projects that drive environmental sustainability and circular economy initiatives. With a strong passion for strategic business development and innovation, he actively supports initiatives that promote clean water, resource recovery, and sustainable infrastructure.

Short abstract

The Aqua2N process by EasyMining revolutionizes wastewater treatment by efficiently recovering ammonium from high-ammonium streams, such as reject water and sludge condensate. This sustainable method removes up to 95% of ammonium without releasing nitrous gas or heating the incoming flow. By regenerating the precipitant, it minimizes chemical use, enhances the carbon footprint of wastewater treatment plants, and converts them into nutrient factories, yielding high-quality ammonium sulfate fertilizer. Aqua2N is a robust, tested solution that aligns with circular economy principles and addresses climate change effectively.

Extraction of valuable metals from acid mine drainage by an electrochemically activated limestone system

Weiquan Li, Yang Lei

Southern University of Science and Technology, Shenzhen, China

Weiquan Li

What is your current position?

Ph.D. student

Short biography of the presenter

Weiquan Li is a Ph.D. student in the College of Environmental Science and Engineering at Southern University of Science and Technology. His research focuses on the development of sustainable practices for mining wastewater treatment, with an emphasis on the recovery of critical metal elements by using novel and carbon-negative electrochemical methods.

Short abstract

Acid mine drainage (AMD) contains toxic yet valuable metals. Though chemical neutralization can efficiently mitigate metal pollution, it generates hazardous solid wastes without metal recovery. Here, we propose an electrochemically activated limestone (EAL) system for AMD treatment and metals (Cu, Cd, Zn, REE) extraction through electro-reduction and local pH-mediated precipitation. Additionally, the effluent after treatment contains high alkalinity and Ca^{2+} , which is proven to have CO_2 sequestration potential. Overall, the EAL treatment reduces costs by 17.9% and CO_2 emissions by 60.1% compared to conventional lime-dosing treatment, demonstrating its economic viability and ecological superiority for practical AMD remediation and metals recovery.

KOBE Harvest project; From sewage to agriculture through sustainable regional phosphorus resource circulation system

Santisak Kitjanukit¹, Ryo Kanda¹, Noriko Igarashi¹, Taketoshi Shimizu²

¹Swing Corporation, Tokyo, Japan. ²Kobe City Sewage Works Department, Hyogo, Japan

Santisak Kitjanukit

What is your current position?

Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Santisak Kitjanukit is a researcher at Fundamental Engineering Research Center of Swing Corporation (SJC), a private plant engineering company in Japan. Prior to joining SJC in 2020, Mr. Santisak completed his D.Eng degree (Earth Resource Engineering) and worked postdoctoral researcher at Kyushu University, Japan. As a researcher, he is responsible for the development of sewage treatment, anaerobic digestion, phosphorus recovery, and sludge dewatering process. Additionally, he also working on the study of N₂O emission mechanism and removal process in biological wastewater treatment.

Short abstract

In this presentation, one of the successful projects demonstrating a sustainable regional phosphorus resource circulation system, KOBE Harvest project will be introduced. The project was initiated in 2012, with a full-scale plant in Kobe City, Japan. The plant capable of producing about 100 tons of recycled phosphorus as struvite annually. Numerous social events were conducted to boost-up public acceptance of recycled phosphorus, resulting in a realization of sustainable regional phosphorus resource circulation system. Kobe recycled phosphorus has become the symbol of SDGs in Kobe City through over ten years of working in partnership with the local community.

Application of adsorbents derived from industrial sidestreams for ammonium and nitrate adsorption from agricultural runoff

Tatiana Samarina^{1,2}, Janne Pesonen¹, Sari Tuomikoski¹, Magdalena Andrunik³, Ulla Lassi¹

¹Oulu University, Oulu, Finland. ²Kajaani University of Applied Sciences, Kajaani, Finland. ³Mineral and Energy Economy Research Institute, Polish Academy of Sciences, Kraków, Poland

Tatiana Samarina

What is your current position?

Doctoral student

Short biography of the presenter

Tatiana Samarina devoted her research work to the valorization of industrial and municipal waste streams, in particular for various applications of these material flows in agriculture, construction, and water treatment sectors. The applications include manufacturing adsorptive materials from locally available yet underutilized industrial by-products. By elaborating geopolymer technology for mine tailings, steel-making slags, and ashes to manufacture new functional materials, she is looking for cost-effective solutions for wastewater treatment and resource recovery.

Short abstract

Uncontrolled and excessive supply of nutrients to balanced natural water systems is a recognized cause of environmental stress. To address this issue, reactive filtration or adsorption may facilitate sustainable nutrient management practices especially for diffuse nutrient overload. Applying the principles of circular economy, this study seeks for supporting sustainable waste and nutrient management practices by developing a joint solution for waste stream valorisation and protective filtration. Zeolites synthesized from fly ashes after coal combustion, and activated carbons obtained from textile waste were tested for uptake of ammonium and nitrate from agricultural runoff.

The water-soluble fraction of extracellular polymeric substances from a resource recovery demonstration plant: characterization and potential application as an adhesive

Le Min Chen¹, Özlem Erol², Young Hae Choi², Mario Pronk^{1,3}, Mark van Loosdrecht¹, Yuemei Lin¹

¹Delft University of Technology, Delft, Netherlands. ²Institute of Biology, Leiden University, Leiden, Netherlands. ³Royal HaskoningDHV, Amersfoort, Netherlands

Le Min Chen

What is your current position?

PhD Candidate

Short biography of the presenter

Le Min Chen is a 4th-year PhD candidate in the Department of Biotechnology at TU Delft. With a background in Life Science and Technology, she developed an early interest in biopolymers during her master's studies. Now, her research focuses on the extracellular polymers in aerobic granular sludge, where she explores the roles of various biofilm matrix components and investigates innovative applications for these biopolymers.

Short abstract

Extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) recovery from waste excess sludge significantly reduces disposal costs and provides a high-value biomaterial. Valorising the EPS by discovering new applications may stimulate resource recovery and ultimately circular economy. This study focuses on a water-soluble fraction of EPS, which is composed of a mixture of proteins (26%), carbohydrates (22%) and fatty acids (0.9%). The fraction demonstrated a shear strength reaching 36-51 kPa cross a pH range of 2 – 10 without additional chemical treatment. These findings offer novel insights into the concept of resource recovery and valorization of excess sludge at wastewater treatment plants.

Green flocculant of *Aspergillus Niger* fungus cultured from food waste hydrolysate for enhanced sludge dewatering

Yingfei Sun^{1,2}, Xiao-yan Li^{1,3}, Lin Lin¹

¹Tsinghua University, Shenzhen, China. ²University of California, Berkeley, Berkeley, USA. ³HongKong University, Hongkong, China

Yingfei Sun

What is your current position?

4th-year Ph.D candidate

Short biography of the presenter

Yingfei Sun is a fourth-year doctoral candidate in Environmental Science and Engineering at Tsinghua University. Currently, she is a visiting scholar at the University of California, Berkeley (2024–2025), where her research centers on advancing sustainable methodologies in wastewater and sludge treatment, with a particular emphasis on resource recovery from waste. With a commitment to environmental stewardship, Yingfei seeks to contribute innovative, resource-efficient solutions to global waste management challenges.

Short abstract

Conventional coagulants in water treatment present challenges, including toxicity and cost. This study pioneers food waste hydrolysate as a novel substrate to cultivate *Aspergillus Niger* (AN), replacing costly potato dextrose agar. Acid/base-modified AN significantly improves sludge coagulation and dewatering, reducing specific resistance to filtration by up to 19.9%, and achieving a 75.7% reduction when combined FeCl₃. Surface modifications facilitate water hydrophobicity and physically wrap EPS to sludge particles, improving solid-liquid separation. This fungal coagulant aid provides a cost-saving of \$26.26~\$54.26/t dry solid, advancing sustainable management through resource-efficient, eco-friendly practices.

Boosting biogas production and dye removal in textile wastewater treatment with conductive material-enhanced anaerobic bioreactors

Duc Viet Nguyen^{1,2}, Yue Chen¹, Thu Huong Nguyen³, Dongha Kim¹, Takahiro Watari⁴, Takashi Yamaguchi⁴, Minseok Kim⁵, Jeonghwan Kim⁵, Di Wu^{1,2}

¹Centre for Green Chemistry and Environmental Biotechnology, Ghent University Global Campus, Incheon, Korea, Republic of. ²Department of Green Chemistry and Technology, Ghent University, Gent, Belgium. ³Department of Environmental Engineering, Kyoto University, Kyoto, Japan. ⁴Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Nagaoka University of Technology, Nagaoka, Japan. ⁵Department of Environmental Engineering, Inha University, Incheon, Korea, Republic of

Duc Viet Nguyen

What is your current position?

Postdoctoral Fellow

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Duc Viet Nguyen is a postdoctoral fellow at Ghent University Global Campus, Republic of Korea, specializing in environmental engineering. He earned his Engineering degree from Hanoi University of Science and Technology in 2017, graduating as valedictorian with an honors degree. That same year, he visited Kyoto University, Japan, and King Abdullah University of Science and Technology, Saudi Arabia. Dr. Nguyen completed his doctoral studies at Sungkyunkwan University, Korea, in 2022. His research interests encompass advanced environmental technologies, including membrane filtration and biological wastewater treatment. He also explores the application of artificial intelligence to optimize system performance in these fields.

Short abstract

This study investigates the use of reduced graphene oxide (rGO) in enhancing biogas production and dye removal in anaerobic reactors treating synthetic textile wastewater. Two UASB reactors, one with rGO and one without, were operated under varying hydraulic retention times and the presence of copper. The rGO-supported reactor demonstrated higher organic degradation, improved dye removal (up to 99%), and significantly enhanced biogas production (0.9 L/day) compared to the control. Microbial analysis revealed improved diversity and activity in the rGO reactor, particularly under copper addition. These findings suggest that rGO enhances direct interspecies electron transfer (DIET) in wastewater treatment.

Potential of phosphorus recovery in form of vivianite from wastewater treatment plants

Lobna Amin^{1,2}, Raed Al-Juboori¹, Jin Wang², Marina Graan³, Sabrina Guérin Rechdaoui⁴, Helene Hauduc⁵, Anna Mikola¹, Mathieu Sperandio²

¹Aalto university, Espoo, Finland. ²Institut national des sciences appliquées de Toulouse, Toulouse, France. ³Helsinki Region Environmental Services, Helsinki, Finland. ⁴SIAAP, Colombes, France. ⁵Dynamita, Sigale, France

Lobna Amin

What is your current position?

Doctoral researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Lobna Amin is doing her doctoral research as a cotutelle between Aalto university in Finland, and INSA Toulouse in France. She got her master's degree in environmental engineering and technology focusing on wastewater modelling. Her current research focuses on phosphorus recovery in the form of vivianite from wastewater treatment plants.

Short abstract

This study explores phosphorus recovery from wastewater as vivianite, a key process in promoting circular economy principles in wastewater treatment. By analyzing two full-scale plants, we identified critical factors influencing vivianite formation, including iron reduction, sulfur competition, and molar Fe/P ratios. Results show that higher Fe/P ratios and optimized anaerobic sludge retention times enhance vivianite recovery. Additionally, kinetic studies and modeling using Sumo© software allowed for accurate prediction of vivianite precipitation, improving recovery strategies. Our work provides novel insights into phosphorus, iron, and sulfur interactions and offers practical solutions for optimizing vivianite recovery in various treatment settings.

Can we build houses with toilet paper? Upcycling recovered cellulose from urban wastewater.

Aina Soler-Jofra, Mireia Marce, María M. Micó
ACCIONA, Innovation Department, El Prat de Llobregat, Spain

Aina Soler-Jofra

What is your current position?

Project Manager

Short biography of the presenter

Aina Soler Jofra holds a PhD in environmental biotechnology from the Technical University of Delft, the Netherlands (2021). She has more than 8 years of experience in different research groups related to the water cycle and development of innovative solutions for wastewater treatment. Resulting in the publication of different scientific articles in impact journals and presentations at international conferences. She is currently focused on the management of European research projects related to wastewater treatment, development of new technologies and transfer to market.

Short abstract

Starting from different waste streams, the ICARUS project will demonstrate innovative technologies for recovering Secondary Raw Materials (SRM) for their application in the construction sector. In Democase 2, the recovery of cellulose from wastewater treatment plants, especially toilet paper, will be showcased using a rotatory belt filter (RBF). This recovery will include the removal from the SRM of pharmaceuticals, metals and microplastics, previously spotted in the RBF influent, bringing the process beyond the state of the art. A special focus will be dedicated on ensuring social and market acceptance and the development of a successful business model.

Rubiphos phosphate recovery technology for secondary nutrient sources

Mohamed Takhim¹, Josien Ruijter², Jan Peter Born², Jonathan Desmet¹

¹TTBS BV, Louvain la Neuve, Belgium. ²HVC NV, Alkmaar, Netherlands

Mohamed Takhim

What is your current position?

Founder and director of TTBS

Short biography of the presenter

Mohamed Takhim is the owner and CEO of TTBS – a Belgian company mainly focussed on phosphate & lithium recovery technologies and waste water treatment. He is an industrial project manager and process developer with over 25 years of experience.

He has a Master's degree in Project Management from ESC Lille and a MBA from the French Business School SKEMA, and holds the title of Process Chemical Engineer. He has more than 10 granted patents on his name.

He has led the conception and construction of several factories based on his technologies overall the world.

Josien Ruijter

What is your current position?

Strategic developer sludge treatment

Short biography of the presenter

Background in earth sciences and hydrology (Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam), having a broad experience in water management within the drinking water and waste processing sector, as well as in resource recovery. Networker that combines insight in value chains and impactful relations for environmental best solutions, finding cross-border alternatives that more and more require the awareness on environmental justice. Passionate about, amongst others, honey bees in the light of local biodiversity.

Short abstract

Rubiphos is a process developed for the recovery of phosphorus. Since 2020, tests at various scales have shown that more than 90% of the phosphates present in the HVC ash can be recovered as fully water-soluble products. Heavy metals can be largely removed and extracted from the process. The remaining residue is marketed as so-called RubiCas as a compound solid inorganic fertilizer. The sulphates and part of the magnesium are extracted as epsom salt. This technology contributes to the potential to balance the phosphate cycle in Europe in a sustainable way with a limited spatial footprint by applying secondary sources.

Transforming CO₂: Unleashing Microorganisms and the Power of Hydrogen for Multi-Carbon Innovation

Sanne M de Smit, Johannes H Bitter, David PBTB Strik
Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, Netherlands

Sanne M de Smit

What is your current position?

Assistant Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Sanne de Smit works as an Assistant Professor at the Wageningen University. She got a Msc degree (2018) in Biotechnology with a thesis on microbial chain elongation and earned her PhD degree (2023) on the topic of Microbial Electrosynthesis from a self-obtained WIMEK grant. Her main research interests are bio-electrochemical solutions for treatment or reutilization of various waste streams, e.g. CO₂, H₂S, NH₄⁺. Within the field of bio-electrochemistry, she focusses on the combination of chemical and microbial catalysis within bio-electrochemical systems and the characterization of local conditions and gradients by e.g. microsensor measurements.

Short abstract

Microorganisms can convert CO₂ into multi-carbon compounds, such as volatile fatty acids, as alternatives to fossil-based chemicals. In bio-electrochemical systems, these conversions are enhanced by electrical energy, using hydrogen as a key energy carrier between electrodes and CO₂-converting microbes. We developed a method employing microsensors to measure local hydrogen distribution (50 μm resolution) inside porous carbon electrodes with varying recirculation flow strategies. Using that approach we could show that differences in the local hydrogen concentration of over 80% can exist depending on the recirculation flow strategy.

Circular economy of drinking water treatment residues – A local French approach

Stéphanie PIEL¹, Wouter Noordman²

¹Saur France, Paris, France. ²Nijhuis Saur Industries, Doetinchem, Netherlands

Stéphanie PIEL

What is your current position?

Teamleader R&D - Drinking Water

Short biography of the presenter

Teamleader R&D - Drinking Water for Saur France.

Short abstract

In France advancing the circular economy in the water sector is focussed on the themes of Industrial and Territorial Ecology. By repurposing waste from water treatment plants, the company Saur recycles ferric sludge for gas desulphurization and decarbonation pellets for use in glass and flooring, reducing landfill and environmental impact. Compliance with the REACH registration ensures product safety, while quality tests and interviews with manufacturers help align by-product use with local needs. Large-scale trials validated the process, including using calcite as a microsand primer alternative, enhancing recovery routes without operational changes. This approach optimizes environmental and economic benefits regionally

Integrated approach for recovering valuable metals and sulphuric acid from wastes generated in the mineral extraction industry

Ana Guedes¹, Lidia Fernández-Rojo¹, Eric Vilanova¹, Carlos Echevarría¹, Tamara Martínez-Santos², Manuel Sevilla²
¹Cetaqua, Barcelona, Spain. ²Tharsis mining, Huelva, Spain

Ana Guedes

What is your current position?

Project Manager

Short biography of the presenter

Ana Guedes is a civil engineer with demonstrated experience in water R&D. She is currently working as a researcher and project manager at Cetaqua - Barcelona with industrial wastewater treatment and reuse, water desalination, membrane technologies and system modelling.

Short abstract

The Horizon Europe Resilex project proposes an innovative circular treatment process to recover metals from acid mine drainage (AMD) while also producing sulphuric acid from solid mining waste. Recovering critical and valuable metals from AMD is not only important for the global economy but also for mitigating soil and water contamination. The valorization of mining waste to produce sulphuric acid and its subsequent recovery within the process can also significantly reduce the environmental impact associated with the mining industry, since it is a key reagent in the extraction of metals and its production often involves harmful emissions and resource depletion.

Advanced P-removal and recovery from WWTP-effluent with the BioPhree® technology

Mathijs Oosterhuis¹, Pim de Jager²

¹Royal HaskoninDHV, Amersfoort, Netherlands. ²Aquacare Europe BV, den Bosch, Netherlands

Mathijs Oosterhuis

What is your current position?

senior consultant water and resource recovery

Short biography of the presenter

Mathijs works since 2017 for Royal HaskoningDHV where he joins the R&D team of the Wastewater Advisory Group. He has more than 25 years experience in wastewater treatment and contributed to the development of wastewater and sludge treatment technology mainly by doing pilot research projects. Nutrient removal and recovery has his specific interest.

Short abstract

The novel adsorption technique BioPhree® was demonstrated on pilot scale to remove phosphorous from wastewater effluent. This pilot was operational for 15 months, aiming for a total phosphorus concentration in the final effluent of < 0.1 mg P/L.

The measured average P-tot in the final effluent was close to 0.1 mg P/L at an adsorption capacity of circa 2-4 g P/kg adsorbent. The adsorbent was regenerated > 5 times at high pH with a stable P-adsorption capacity. A test with nanofiltration to recover NaOH resulted in 70% recovery and a P and TOC retention of respectively 98% and 90%.

Integrating biomethanation into extracellular polymeric substance (EPS) extraction via alkaline anaerobic digestion.

Beatriz C. Diniz, Philipp Wilfert, Dimitry Y. Sorokin, MCM Van Loosdrecht
TU delft, Delft, Netherlands

Beatriz C. Diniz

What is your current position?

PhD candidate.

Short biography of the presenter

Beatriz C. Diniz is a PhD candidate at TU Delft in the environmental biotechnology section. Her work focuses on integrating an alkaline environment in anaerobic digestion with the goal of capturing the CO₂ from biogas.

Short abstract

The extraction of extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) from aerobic granular sludge (AGS) requires high-temperature and high-pH conditions, producing an alkaline residue retaining up to 50% of the original organic matter. This residue can be directly converted into methane (CH₄) through alkaline anaerobic digestion (AD), using specially adapted microorganisms. In this process a methane-rich biogas is produced, as CO₂ remains in solution in bicarbonate/carbonate form. This study shows similar methane production rates to neutral conditions and high-methane purity gas stream (>90%). No bottlenecks, such as ammonia inhibition, were observed. This approach effectively integrates CH₄ production with CO₂ capture.

Advancing to water neutral residential areas: the water house “Heuvelstraat” in the Netherlands as case study.

Peter Scheer, Jan Weijma, [Wilbert Menkveld](#)
Nijhuis Saur Industries, Doetinchem, Netherlands

Peter Scheer

What is your current position?

Industry Development Manager

Short biography of the presenter

Specialties: Interim-management, Research (feasibility-studies), Business Development, City farming, Vertical farming, Sanitation, Decentral waste water treatment, First Aid

Wilbert Menkveld

What is your current position?

Chief Technology Officer

Short biography of the presenter

CTO at Nijhuis Saur Industries

Short abstract

In Silvolde, Netherlands, an innovative water cycle system has been implemented for 13 homes in the Heuvelstraat residential area. This circular system utilizes rainwater as the primary drinking water source and recycles shower wastewater for toilet flushing, reducing water consumption by 30%. Partners Vitens, Wonion, Oude IJsselstreek, Rijn en IJssel, and Nijhuis Saur Industries aim to address climate and demographic water challenges. The system includes nanofiltration and UV purification for contaminants, with treated sewage reintegrated into the soil. Back-up water and sewer connections are available, and monitoring will provide data to optimize and scale this sustainable model.

Magnesium Recovery from Reverse Osmosis Concentrate for Struvite Production

Tejas Vasa¹, SGJ Heijman¹, Synco Tee²

¹TU Delft, Delft, Netherlands. ²Waternet, Amsterdam, Netherlands

Tejas Vasa

What is your current position?

MSc Environmental Engineering Student

Short biography of the presenter

Currently pursuing my masters in TU Delft in Environmental Engineering specializing in Water resources and treatment. He has hands-on experience in air and water quality management, wastewater treatment, and sustainable resource recovery. He is dedicated to translating experimental findings into practical, large-scale solutions in the realm of water and environment

Short abstract

This research focuses on **recovering magnesium (Mg) from reverse osmosis (RO) concentrate**, a waste stream, The recovered Mg can be used in struvite production, promoting circular economy practices. **A counter-current IEX (Ion exchange) column setup** was used to recover Mg from the RO concentrate. By combining pre-treatment with Na_2CO_3 to remove calcium and optimizing ion exchange (IEX) with HCl as the regenerant a concentration of 30 grams of magnesium per liter was recovered. The study explores the potential for **industrial upscaling using a carousel-based multi-column system** to maximize efficiency and continuous operation. This method offers scalable and efficient Mg recovery.

Magnetic Adsorption-Desorption for Phosphorus Recovery from Wastewater

Norbert Kuipers, [Tania Mubita](#), Ronald Vroon, Johan van Groenestijn, Lesly Garcia Chavez, Jan Wichers
Wageningen University and Research, Wageningen, Netherlands

Norbert Kuipers

What is your current position?

Senior Scientist Separation & Purification

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Norbert Kuipers is a leading researcher at Wageningen University and Research with a focus on the Water-Food-Energy nexus. His work addresses sustainable solutions in brine treatment, nutrient recovery, and separation and purification technologies, particularly within water treatment systems.

Tania Mubita

What is your current position?

Knowledge Leader of the Expertise Separation and Purification at Wageningen Food & Biobased Research

Short biography of the presenter

I am the Knowledge Leader of the Expertise Separation and Purification at Wageningen Food & Biobased Research, specializing in membrane separation technologies, particularly electrically driven processes like electro dialysis. Focus is on removal and recovery of valuable compounds from wastewaters and agri-food side streams, ensuring high removal efficiency with low energy consumption. Work spans lab to pilot scale, covering the entire value chain from resource recovery to high-value, reusable products, with attention to economic feasibility for industrial applications.

Short abstract

This study presents the Magnetic Adsorption-Desorption (MAD) process, an innovative method for phosphorus recovery from wastewater. Using magnetite-based adsorbents, MAD selectively captures phosphorus compounds, then regenerates them via magnetic separation. Electrodialysis with bipolar membranes (EDBM) is integrated to produce acid and base on-site, eliminating external chemical needs. Lab-scale tests confirm effective phosphorus capture, purification, and suitability for reuse as sustainable fertilizer. The presentation covers MAD's operational efficiency, phosphorus recovery rates, and its potential for circular phosphorus management.

Integration of Nitrogen Recovery and Biogas Enrichment in WWTPs through Bioelectrochemical Technologies

Federico Ferrari¹, Jorge Luque Rueda², Rubén Rodríguez-Alegre², Pau Bosch², Carlos Andecochea Saiz², Sergi Durán-Videra², Eduard Borràs², María M. Micó Reche¹

¹ACCIONA, El Prat de Llobregat, Spain. ²Leitat Technological Center, Terrassa, Spain

Federico Ferrari

What is your current position?

Researcher in innovation department

Short biography of the presenter

Environmental Engineer from the University of Rome La Sapienza and Ph.D. graduate from the Catalan Institute for Water Research. He is currently a project manager in the Innovation Department at Acciona Agua, where he researches the application of technologies for wastewater treatment, anaerobic digestion, biogas upgrading, sludge pretreatment and bioelectrochemical systems.

Short abstract

NIMBI project introduces a bioelectrochemical system for nitrogen recovery and biogas enhancement at WWTP. Employs primary effluent as the anolyte, harnessing energy from the biodegradation of organic matter. This facilitates hydroxyls generation at the cathode, increasing the pH of anaerobic digestion centrate, rich in ammonium, used as catholyte. The basification enables the conversion of ammonium into ammonia, which is recovered by biogas stripping. From that gas stream, two membrane contactors will recover NH_3 as ammonium salt, and will capture CO_2 , upgrading the biogas stream to biomethane ($\text{CH}_4 > 80\%$). NIMBI will undergo laboratory optimization using real effluents prior pilot testing.

Crystallization-Optimized Membrane Process for Sustainable Brine Treatment and Resource Recovery

Norbert Kuipers, Jolanda van Medevoort, Arnoud Togtema, Mahmoud Alkhalid
Wageningen University and Research, Wageningen, Netherlands

Norbert Kuipers

What is your current position?

Senior Scientist Separation & Purification

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Norbert Kuipers is a leading researcher at Wageningen University and Research with a focus on the Water-Food-Energy nexus. His work addresses sustainable solutions in brine treatment, nutrient recovery, and separation and purification technologies, particularly within water treatment systems.

Short abstract

With growing water scarcity and the need to reduce waste, innovative brine treatment for freshwater and mineral recovery is essential. This study introduces the COMBRINE process, combining membrane distillation and antisolvent crystallization for efficient high-salinity brine treatment. COMBRINE produces high-quality freshwater and recovers valuable salts, using low-grade waste heat and avoiding chemical additives. Laboratory tests demonstrated reduced membrane fouling, extending system stability and efficiency. Initial results suggest COMBRINE's potential to transform waste brines into freshwater and valuable salts, supporting a circular water economy through sustainable water management.

NPHarvest journey from academia to business - commercialization experiences in the field of nutrient recovery

Juho Uzkurt Kaljunen

NPHarvest, Espoo, Finland

Juho Uzkurt Kaljunen

What is your current position?

CEO

Short biography of the presenter

Juho finalized his PhD on nutrient recovery and started NPHarvest company based on the results of his research. He is an experimental engineer with endless curiosity towards saving the world. Sometimes it's good, sometimes hazardous.

Short abstract

NPHarvest is an university spin-off from Aalto University. Towards the end of the 7-year research phase, it was clear that there was a market for a recovery technology that provides profitable N and P recovery.

The main advantages of NPHarvest recovery tech are low operational cost, easy operation and maintenance and high end product quality. Especially tolerance for high suspended solids in the wastewater has peaked interest in clients.

Despite interest from the field and solid research, commercializing a new technology means conquering obstacles and navigating the valley of death. This presentation reflects on the experiences of the commercialization journey.

Towards a coherent EU policy for wastewater nutrient recovery

Ludwig Hermann, Robert Van Spingelen
ESPP, Brussels, Belgium

Ludwig Hermann

What is your current position?

ESPP Board and Proman

Short biography of the presenter

Board of the European Sustainable Phosphorus Platform

Short abstract

The revised EU Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive specifies phosphorus “reuse and recycling targets” to be set within three years, opening a path to systematic valorisation of phosphorus in sewage. Assessment of N-recovery will be carried out. This fits with other EU policies on phosphorus enacted over recent years: the EU Critical Raw Materials Act, Taxonomy (green investment rules), Fertilising Products Regulation, Organic Farming, Animal By-Products. Further developments are expected in the EU Circular Economy Act announced 2025 and Sewage Sludge Directive revision. We will discuss evolution towards a coherent EU policy for nutrient stewardship and challenges remaining.

Industrial scale long-term validation of waste sludge fermentation and volatile fatty acids valorization

Matteo Grana^{1,2}, Michele Platè¹, Davide Scaglione¹, Elena Ficara²

¹Gruppo CAP, Milano, Italy. ²Politecnico di Milano, Milano, Italy

Matteo Grana

What is your current position?

Process Engineer

Short biography of the presenter

Process engineer at Gruppo CAP, dealing with wastewater treatment and waste management for biomethane production. He obtained a PhD at Politecnico di Milano in environmental engineering, focusing mainly on resource recovery from sewage sludge through biological processes. More in detail, acidogenic fermentation for volatile fatty acids production, biological nutrients removal from wastewater, and polyhydroxyalkanoates production were the main research topics.

Short abstract

The challenges posed by climate change are driving the search for new solutions to achieve sustainable wastewater management. WWTPs are thus transitioning towards biorefineries to perform resource recovery. This research validates acidogenic fermentation for VFAs production from sewage sludge at full-scale. The research was conducted at the Sesto San Giovanni WWTP, with a fermentation reactor of 315 m³. The process was monitored over a four-year period, where the link between the operative parameters and the fermentation performance was assessed. The potential of fermentate in promoting enhanced denitrification was evaluated, while a pilot plant for polyhydroxyalkanoates production will be started soon.

Oligotrophic biofilms for the recovery of manganese as crystalline manganese oxides (MnOx)

Amanda Larasati, Maria Cristina Gagliano
Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands

Amanda Larasati

What is your current position?

Scientific project manager

Short biography of the presenter

Amanda has been a researcher at Wetsus since 2021, focusing on micropollutant removal from water. She earned her PhD in environmental engineering in the UK in 2020. During her postdoctoral research at Wetsus, she worked with BAC filters. She and her colleagues discovered the BAC potential not only for removing micropollutants but also for recovering metals, such as manganese, from wastewater.

Short abstract

This study examined manganese (Mn)-oxidizing biofilms from a full-scale oxygen-supplemented biological activated carbon (BAC) filter to recover Mn(II) from wastewater through the production of biogenic Mn-oxides (MnOx). The biofilms were enriched in Mn-oxidizing bacteria (MnOB) by feeding manganese carbonate in oligotrophic conditions. The MnOB converted Mn(II) into MnOx crystals (birnessite) within the biofilm matrix. When tested against a pharmaceutical, the MnOx-enriched biofilms removed ~90%, compared to ~60% by non-enriched biofilms. This approach demonstrates the potential to recover low concentrations of Mn(II) in wastewater into MnOx using a biofilter, creating enriched biofilms that effectively catalyze pharmaceutical removal.

Transforming Waste into Wealth: Enhancing Natural Microbiomes for the Production of High-Value Water Sector Bioproducts

Eleonora Paissoni, Elvira Serra, Babi Uku, Blanca Antizar
Isle Utilities, London, United Kingdom

Eleonora Paissoni

What is your current position?

Environmental Technology Consultant

Short biography of the presenter

Eleonora is an Environmental Engineer and joined Isle Utilities in 2023 as an Environmental Technology Consultant. She holds a PhD in Water from Cranfield University (UK). Her PhD research focused on anaerobic treatment of municipal wastewater in temperate climates for water reuse and resource recovery.

At Isle, Eleonora is primarily involved in the delivery of the exploitation and engagement activities for EU-funded projects and wastewater consultancy projects.

Short abstract

The sustainable production of bio-based polymers, of increasing interest for the water sector, has traditionally relied on pure culture systems and chemically defined substrates. The PROMICON project is pioneering a shift by leveraging the power of natural mixed cultures. Utilising innovative biotechnological tools, PROMICON enhances and optimises microbiomes for high productivity, deploying them in a biorefinery approach to generate high-value bioproducts, such as polymers, butanol, and hydrogen, using waste substrates and carbon dioxide. This transformative approach not only valorises microbial resources, like those sourced from wastewater treatment plants, but also replaces fossil-based products with environmentally friendly alternatives.

Assessing the sustainability of waste-activated sludge-based PHA production

Antonio Mineo¹, [Giorgio Mannina](#)¹, Mark van Loosdrecht²

¹Palermo University, Palermo, Italy. ²Department of Biotechnology, Delft University of Technology, Delft, Netherlands

Giorgio Mannina

What is your current position?

professor

Short biography of the presenter

Dr Giorgio Mannina is Professor of Sanitary and Environmental Engineering at the Engineering Department of Palermo University – Italy. His research interest and focus is on: resource recovery from wastewater, advanced wastewater treatments (MBR, MBBR, hybrid processes, IFAS, Granular systems etc..), BNR processes, mathematical modelling, water quality issues related to integrated urban drainage systems.

Affiliations and expertise

Director of WRRF'lab at Palermo University

Short abstract

This abstract shows the key insights gained after a three-year experimental period on waste-activated sludge (WAS) based PHA production processes. Results show that achieving a considerable amount of PHA was possible without adopting environmentally harmful practices (like thermal sludge pre-treatment). The systems also showed high carbon and nitrogen removal, while nitrous oxide emissions similar to those reported by wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) were obtained when the complete nitrogen removal via nitrite pathway was adopted. PHA production accounted for 0.4 g PHA/g VSS. The results indicate that the environmental aspect during the PHA production process cannot be further neglected.

Feeding regime and carbohydrate type determine the lactic acid-to-VFA ratio in thermophilic mixed-culture fermentations

Laia Vulart^{1,2,3}, Néstor Gil^{1,2,3}, Ángel Estévez^{2,3}, Enrique Peiro¹, Francesc Gòdia¹, Ramon Ganigué^{2,3}

¹MELiSSA Pilot Plant – Laboratory Claude Chipaux, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Bellaterra (Barcelona), Spain.

²Center for Microbial Ecology and Technology (CMET), Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium. ³Centre for Advanced Process Technology for Urban Resource Recovery (CAPTURE), Ghent, Belgium

Laia Vulart

What is your current position?

PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

Laia Vulart is a doctoral researcher at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona and Ghent University, with an interest in bio-engineering and biotechnological processes. Her PhD work focuses on advancing sustainable resource recovery technologies for long-term space missions under the European Space Agency's MELiSSA project. Her research explores thermophilic mixed-culture fermentation and bioelectrochemical systems, leveraging biotechnology to transform waste streams into valuable resources. Her work not only addresses the challenges of closed-loop life-support systems for space exploration but also contributes to advancing circular bioeconomy solutions on Earth, promoting more efficient and sustainable resource management across diverse environments.

Short abstract

Carboxylic acids are produced in mixed-culture fermentations, though product profile varies across different studies. While much is known about the influence of operational parameters on mixed-culture fermentations, there is little understanding on how different substrates and feeding regimes affect product distribution under thermophilic conditions. Our findings indicate that the feeding regime and the type of carbohydrate determine carbohydrate conversion to either lactic acid or VFAs in thermophilic fermentation, obtaining higher lactic acid-to-VFAs ratios when the carbohydrate input per cycle is higher.

Chemicals-free inorganic scaling prevention in electrochemical nutrient recovery

Widya Prihesti Iswarani^{1,2}, Philipp Kuntke^{1,2}, Tom Sleutels¹, Bert Hamelers^{1,2}

¹Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ²Wageningen University and Research, Wageningen, Netherlands

Widya Prihesti Iswarani

What is your current position?

PhD researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Widya is a PhD researcher at Wetsus. Her PhD focuses on nutrient recovery from (source-separated) wastewater using electrochemical systems. Her project is a collaboration between Wetsus and Wageningen University (WUR). She is originally from Indonesia, and before embarking on her PhD studies, she worked as a lecturer at Avans Hogeschool, after having completed an MSc at Delft University of Technology (TU Delft).

Short abstract

Nitrogen recovery from wastewater through electrodialysis (ED) enhances agricultural circularity and prevents pollution. Nevertheless, large-scale implementation is restricted by inorganic membrane scaling by Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} precipitation. Combining ion exchange resin (IEX) and bipolar membrane electrodialysis (BMED) process can address this challenge. The acidic BMED effluent regenerates the resin, while the alkaline stream recovers NH_4^+ , and Na^+ is reused for reconditioning of the IEX. IEX pretreatment effectively removed Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} without affecting NH_4^+ recovery. The stable cell voltage indicates that IEX pretreatment inhibits scaling and extends the operational lifespan. Therefore, IEX-BMED allows for sustainable nutrient recovery.

Aerobic Granular Sludge Enhances Membrane Filtration in a Full-Scale Industrial Treatment Plant

Mukhtiar Ahmed, Eirini Tsertou, Koen Goossens, [Jan Dries](#)
University of Antwerp, Antwerp, Belgium

Jan Dries

What is your current position?

Associate Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Jan Dries is an associate professor at the Faculty of Applied Engineering at UAntwerp.

The research of his team, the BioWAVE research group, is directed towards the development of biochemical engineering technologies for a sustainable water cycle. The research is specifically focused on industrial wastewater engineering & wastewater valorization.

The main strength and unique selling proposition of the team are the strong interaction with industrial partners in the development, application and optimization of innovative water technologies. The research interests are very much focused on applied research to bridge the gap from innovation to application

Short abstract

This study quantified the performance of ultrafiltration (UF) integrated in a full scale industrial aerobic granular sludge (AGS) plant. Phase A consisted of a pilot-scale test that showed the positive impact of granular biomass on the membrane filtration properties. In phase B, UF was integrated in the full-scale operation of the AGS plant. The results confirm the significant positive effect of granular/densified biomass on the permeability and fouling tendency of the membranes, leading to lower costs. The AGS-UF configuration thus contributes to a more sustainable water cycle as the effluent is perfectly suited for further upgrade for water reuse

Enhancing Biogas Production and Digestate Quality through Temperature-Phased Anaerobic Digestion

Javier Rico¹, Johanna Zambrano¹, Karen Mora², Miriam Tena³, [Patricia Zamora](#)⁴, Victor Monsalvo⁴, Frank Rogalla⁴

¹Aqualia, Salamanca, Spain. ²Aqualia, Lleida, Spain. ³Aqualia, Badajoz, Spain. ⁴Aqualia, Madrid, Spain

Johanna Zambrano

What is your current position?

Project manager R&D

Short biography of the presenter

Mrs. Zambrano, an Environmental Engineer from San Francisco University, holds a PhD in Chemical and Environmental Engineering from University of Valladolid, where she also earned her MSc in Environmental Management and Technology. She has authored 12 publications and has been a speaker at international conferences and expert meetings on wastewater treatment. Since 2019, she has collaborated with the Institute of Sustainable Processes. Her research experience includes working in South Korea's Environmental Biotechnology Laboratory for Water and Energy, focusing on electrochemical processes for wastewater treatment. Additionally, she contributed to a project on nanoplastics at the International Water Research Center in Cyprus.

Miriam Tena

What is your current position?

R&D technician

Short biography of the presenter

Miriam Tena Villares, who holds a PhD in Agri-Food Resources from the University of Cadiz, earned an Excellent Cum Laude distinction and an award for her thesis on hydrogen and methane coproduction through codigestion of biosolids and vinasse. She specializes in enhancing anaerobic digestion of sewage sludge, with her research published in high-impact journals and presented at conferences. As a postdoctoral researcher, she validated lab studies on a pilot plant scale. Currently, she works in Aqualia's R&D department, contributing to European projects on anaerobic digestion and wastewater treatment processes.

Patricia Zamora

What is your current position?

Senior Project manager

Short biography of the presenter

Patricia is a Senior R&D Project Manager and Researcher at Aqualia, currently leading several European projects dealing with resource recovery and energy production from wastewater. Her education is a Bachelor in Chemical Engineering (2005), PhD in Analytical Chemistry (2012) and Master's Degree in Occupational Risk Prevention (3 specialities), Environmental and Quality Management (2006).

Short abstract

Temperature-phased anaerobic digestion (dual digestion) presents a promising solution for addressing challenges in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) and methane production. This method effectively removes gas toxicants, particularly H₂S and enhances the profitability of biogas produced. Regulatory pressures on sludge management and quality have spurred the development of technologies like dual digestion, which ensures hygienic sludge disposal meeting EPA's CLASS A standards and offers CAPEX and OPEX benefits. This study investigates the thermophilic/mesophilic anaerobic digestion of sludge in semi-continuous reactors, focusing on biogas production and digestate dewatering properties.

Sustainable nitrogen recovery from industrial wastewater

Ioanna Gkoutzamani, Martin Pot
EVIDES Industriewater BV, Rotterdam, Netherlands

Ioanna Gkoutzamani

What is your current position?

Process engineer

Short biography of the presenter

Ioanna Gkoutzamani holds a diploma in Civil Engineering from Aristotle University of Thessaloniki with specialization in hydraulic and environmental engineering. Moreover, she followed the master track Water Management in Civil Engineering at Delft University of Technology with specialization in urban water engineering. Currently, she is working as a process engineer within the R&D team of Evides Industriewater focusing on wastewater re-use and resources recovery options with ion exchange, nitrous oxide emissions control and optimization of aeration processes.

Short abstract

The design and performance of a full-scale, targeted and decentralized treatment installation of a nitrogen rich-condensate from an ammonium nitrate (NH_4NO_3) fertilizer production factory is covered in this presentation. Nitrogen present in the condensate is removed by ion exchange resins in a twostep process. Resins' regeneration with the right chemicals, enables the concentration of nitrogen in the regenerant stream without contamination with other components. The separated regenerant and the purified water are re-used as feedstock and process water respectively within the same factory resulting in a nitrogen recovery of 10 kg/d with nitrogen and water recovery rates of 99.6%.

Understanding lactate-based odd-chain elongation in continuous mixed-culture bioreactors

Ángel Estévez^{1,2}, Ramon Ganigué^{1,2}

¹Center for Microbial Ecology and Technology, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium. ²Center for Advanced Process Technology for Urban Resource Recovery (CAPTURE), Ghent, Belgium

Ángel Estévez

What is your current position?

Postdoctoral Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Ángel Estévez is a post-doctoral researcher at the Center for Microbial Ecology and Technology at Ghent University. He obtained his PhD title in Environmental Biotechnology at Delft University of Technology in December 2022. His PhD project, a collaboration between TU Delft and Wetsus, was focused on the use of municipal waste activated sludge for biopolymers production. At CMET, he aims to understand fermentative microbial communities and their metabolic interactions to develop bioprocesses for a sustainable circular economy. In general, Ángel is fascinated by how microorganisms adapt to different environmental conditions and interact with each other.

Short abstract

This study investigates the use of lactate, produced in situ from carbon-rich waste(water), as an alternative electron donor for odd-chain elongation in anaerobic mixed cultures. Maximum valerate concentrations of 11.4 g/L with high selectivity (56-59%) were achieved from lactate-propionate mixtures, representing the highest valerate concentrations obtained with mixed cultures. Surprisingly, higher lactate availability did not favor the production of longer-chain products like heptanoate. Instead, excess lactate was oxidized to acetate and propionate, maintaining high valerate selectivity. These findings expand the understanding of microbial odd-chain elongation, offering a cost-effective route to valorize waste(water) into valuable biochemicals.

Carboxylate Recovery from PHA & PLA Plastics via Hydrothermal Pretreatment and Open-Culture Fermentation

Yong Jin, Ralf Beckmans, Kasper Leeuw, David Strik
Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, Netherlands

Yong Jin

What is your current position?

PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

I am a PhD student in the Environmental Technology group at Wageningen University, specializing in anaerobic fermentation. My research focuses on advancing resource recovery processes through the carboxylate platform, with a strong interest in sustainable technologies and circular bioeconomy solutions. Currently, I am investigating the bio-recycling of biobased biodegradable plastics into carboxylates and developing strategies for separating and purifying high-value carboxylates, such as n-capric acid, produced via open-culture fermentation.

Short abstract

Increased use of biobased biodegradable products made from plastics like polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) and polylactic acids (PLA) necessitates efficient recovery after end-of-life. This study demonstrates near-complete bio-recycling of PHA/PLA materials into C₂-C₆ carboxylates using hydrothermal pretreatment and open-culture fermentation. PLA addition enhanced PHA dissolution by 250%, achieving 97% hydrolysis and producing 3-hydroxybutyric acid, while PLA reached 99%, yielding lactic acid. The open-culture fermentation converted 100% of the supplied PHA&PLA hydrolysates into products like acetate (4.4 g/L/d), n-butyrate (8.0 g/L/d), and n-caproate (0.3 g/L/d). This approach enables the bio-recycling of bioplastics into valuable carboxylates.

The circular transformation of calcite: From waste product to valuable raw material in the water sector and industry.

Bob Hofkamp¹, Jorrit Remmers², Marco Van Boheemen³

¹AquaMinerals, Nieuwegein, Netherlands. ²Vitens, Zwolle, Netherlands. ³Van Zutven Processing, Veghel, Netherlands

Bob Hofkamp

What is your current position?

Commercial & Operational Manager

Short biography of the presenter

Bob Hofkamp is an experienced professional with a strong focus on the commercial market, specializing in circularity and sustainability. He has extensive knowledge of sustainable business strategies and circular economy and has held various leadership positions. Bob is known for his ability to implement innovative, environmentally friendly and economically viable solutions.

Short abstract

Calcite was once considered a waste product of drinking water treatment, but this residue has transformed remarkably into a high-quality secondary raw material with various innovative applications. This abstract describes the development of calcite within the circular economy, the changed view of this material, and the wide range of applications that have contributed to sustainable resource use and the reliance of virgin materials

Acid recovery from hydrometallurgical copper industry effluents by using nanofiltration

Julio Lopez, Daniel Rodríguez-Jiménez, Marc Fernández de Labastida, José Luis Cortina
UPC-BarcelonaTECH, Barcelona, Spain

Julio Lopez

What is your current position?

Lecturer

Short biography of the presenter

Julio López is a Lecturer at Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC-BarcelonaTECH, Spain). He holds a PhD in Chemical Engineering Processes, and his current research activities are focused on resource recovery from waste streams using green technologies.

Short abstract

Copper hydrometallurgical plants face challenges in treating low-grade ores while maintaining high copper purity. Current processing methods generate waste streams with high acidity and dissolved metals, typically treated with lime. However, these streams present acid and metal recovery opportunities using circular economy approaches. One of these approaches is using nanofiltration (NF), which allows for acid recovery and concentration of metals before any crystallisation route. Therefore, this work evaluated the use of NF for treating effluents from copper hydrometallurgical plants. Results showed high metal rejections while allowing the permeation of acid. However, the precipitation of calcium sulphate might limit the operation.

Multifunctional Bioelectrochemical System for: Wastewater Treatment, Nutrient Recovery, and Hydrogen Production

Jorge Luque-Rueda¹, Martí Aliaguilla¹, Gerard Pérez², Sandra Martínez², Miquel Aguilar², Marcel Boerritger², [Pau Bosch Jimenez](#)¹, Eduard Borràs¹

¹Circular Economy & Decarbonization Department, Leitat Technological Center, Carrer Innovació 2 Terrassa 08225, Barcelona, Spain. ²Applied Chemistry & Materials Department, Leitat Technological Center, Carrer Innovació 2 Terrassa 08225, Barcelona, Spain

Jorge Luque-Rueda

What is your current position?

Researcher II in Bioelectrochemical Technologies for Decarbonization

Short biography of the presenter

I have completed my degree in Chemistry at the University of Málaga and a master's degree in applied Materials Chemistry at the University of Barcelona. My academic research was mainly focused on the synthesis and physicochemical and electrochemical characterization of transition metal phosphides with applications in the catalysis of reactions involved in hydrogen fuel cells and PEM electrolyzers. I also studied platinum-nickel "Core-Shell" nanoparticles as catalysts in these systems.

Currently, I am advancing my professional career at LEITAT Technological Center, at the Circular Economy & Decarbonization Department, working in the field of bio-electrochemical technologies. My research here focuses on hydrogen-related applications.

Pau Bosch Jimenez

What is your current position?

Principal Researcher in Bioelectrochemical Systems area

Short biography of the presenter

Pau Bosch Jimenez has a degree in Chemistry and a Master's degree in Chemical Science and Technology. Pau Bosch is a principal researcher at LEITAT. He worked in different fields of electrochemistry, in photovoltaics, bioelectrochemical systems, and hydrogen technologies. Now, his work is focused on the developing and electrochemical characterization of catalyst and electrodes, and on scaling up and piloting bioelectrochemical and electrolysis systems.

Short abstract

Nitrogen in wastewater is an environmental threat, causing eutrophication and toxicity. Traditional biological processes remove nitrogen, but circular economy promotes its recovery and reuse. Bioelectrochemical systems offer a low-energy solution for nitrogen recovery. Within VIVALDI project, it was developed a novel BES reactor combining wastewater treatment, ammonium recovery and hydrogen production. A Microbial Electrolysis Cell, using selective cation exchange membranes and cathodes with metallic nanoparticles, has been tested for ammonium sulphate recovery. Experiments proven an average recovery of $46 \text{ gN}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$, 55 % organic matter removal and hydrogen production of $1650 \text{ LH}_2\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$, requiring $\approx 30 \text{ kWh}\cdot\text{kgH}_2$.

Fire Performance of Extracellular Polymeric Substances Recovered from Waste Aerobic Granular Sludges

Nam Kyeun Kim^{1,2}, Tan Le^{1,2}, Mark van Loosdrecht³, Yuemei Lin³

¹Centre for Advanced Materials Manufacturing and Design, University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand. ²Department of Mechanical and Mechatronics Engineering, University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand. ³Department of Biotechnology, Delft University of Technology, Delft, Netherlands

Nam Kyeun Kim

What is your current position?

Senior Lecturer

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Nam Kyeun Kim is a senior lecturer in the Department of Mechanical and Mechatronics Engineering, the University of Auckland. He completed Master and PhD in the Mechanical Engineering from the University of Auckland, in 2011 and 2015, respectively. His research interest covers interdisciplinary themes which include the development of bio-based flame retardants and composites, manufacturing and characterisations of composites containing natural and synthetic materials. In particular, he has actively explored upcycling waste materials to develop functional composites. Furthermore, he has been closely working with aerospace and building industry partners in New Zealand to investigate fire performance of composites interiors.

Short abstract

Resource recovery in wastewater treatment process plants has become a promising solution to mitigate excess sludge production and reduce landfill waste. This study investigates the potential of extracellular polymeric substance (EPS) as flame retardants by incorporating them into natural fabrics and polymeric composites. Extensive thermal characterisation and flammability testing have been conducted to assess the thermal and fire properties of EPS-based materials. The EPS-coated fabrics exhibit self-extinguishing behaviour and composite reduces heat and smoke production by adding EPS. These findings highlight the potential of EPS to enhance flame retardancy in materials, indicating valuable applications in sustainable and fire-resistant material development.

Sequential treatment of cheese whey to enhance biohydrogen production: coupling dark fermentation in presence of electrically conductive materials to microbial electrolysis

Cecilia Petitta^{1,2}, Matteo Tucci¹, Marco Resitano¹, Matteo Daghighio³, Chiara Capelli³, Carlo Viti³, Alessandra Adessi³, Federico Aulenta¹, Luca Di Palma², [Carolina Cruz Viggì](#)¹

¹CNR-IRSA, Montelibretti (RM), Italy. ²Sapienza University of Rome, Rome, Italy. ³Università degli Studi di Firenze, Firenze, Italy

Carolina Cruz Viggì

What is your current position?

Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Researcher at the Water Research Institute of the Italian National Research Council. Graduate in Environmental Industrial Chemistry with a PhD in Industrial Chemical Processes. Research interests focus on environmental biotechnologies applied to the sustainable remediation of contaminated soils, sediments, and groundwater, as well as the treatment of municipal and industrial wastewater and organic wastes with simultaneous resource and energy recovery. The research is conducted primarily through the application of bioelectrochemical processes.

Short abstract

Cheese whey (CW), a byproduct of cheese production, poses environmental challenges due to its high chemical oxygen demand (COD >100 gCOD/L). This study explored a two-step treatment for CW: (i) dark fermentation with electrically conductive materials (ECMs) to enhance volatile fatty acid (VFA) production, and (ii) microbial electrolysis cells (MECs) for hydrogen (H₂) generation. ECMs, particularly magnetite, significantly shifted fermentation products towards VFAs, facilitating electron transfer. The VFAs-rich effluent fed MECs, where oxidation drove H₂ production. Using *Rhodospseudomonas palustris* as a cathodic biocatalyst further boosted light-driven H₂ yield. This approach highlights a sustainable strategy for biohydrogen production from CW.

Uncovering the Potential of structural Extracellular polymeric Substances (sEPS) from Partial Nitritation Granular Sludge (PN-GS): A Comparative Study with Aerobic Granular Sludge (AGS)

Jan Pietro Czellnik, Benedetta Pagliaccia, Caterina Senesi, Tommaso Lotti
University of Florence, Florence, Italy

Jan Pietro Czellnik

What is your current position?

PhD candidate

Short biography of the presenter

I am a PhD candidate at the University of Florence, with a 15-month cotutelle experience at the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB). My research focuses on the transition towards biorefineries of municipal wastewater treatment plants, emphasizing the use of granular biomasses. During my PhD, I have worked extensively with Aerobic Granular Sludge (AGS), Anammox granular sludge, and Partial Nitritation-Granular Sludge (PN-GS), investigating their potential for improving wastewater treatment processes and sustainable resource recovery.

Short abstract

This study investigates structural extracellular polymeric substances (sEPS) extracted from Partial Nitritation-Granular Sludge (PN-GS) and Aerobic Granular Sludge (AGS). Using a consistent physico-chemical extraction method, the research characterizes and compares sEPS, assessing extraction yield, chemical composition, crosslinking potential, and biodegradability. Additionally, mesophilic digestibility tests are performed on the alkaline pellet, and respirometric tests are conducted on the acidic supernatant to explore their roles in integrated management. Expected results suggest PN-GS biopolymers may have distinct characteristics that bridge those of AGS, potentially aiding in the development of targeted strategies for sEPS recovery and their effective valorization in wastewater treatment.

Towards circular chemical usage for sulfide control and phosphate recovery in urban water management using magnetite nanoparticles

Miriam Yap Gabon¹, Sirajus Salehin¹, Markus Fluggen¹, Mario Rebosura Jr¹, Bogdan Donose¹, Zhiguo yuan², [ilje pikaar](#)¹

¹The University of Queensland, Brisbane, Australia. ²City University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong, Hong Kong

ilje pikaar

What is your current position?

Associate Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Ilje Pikaar received his Msc in Environmental Technology (2006) from the Wageningen University, the Netherlands. He received his PhD degree in Environmental Engineering in 2012 from The University of Queensland, Australia. His expertise involves the areas of environmental electrochemistry, the global nitrogen cycle, sewer corrosion, sludge management, metal recovery, integrated urban water management and resource recovery with a special focus on system-wide usage and recovery of coagulants. His work on integrated urban water management has been published in *Science*, whereas his work on the global nitrogen cycle was awarded feature article of 2017 in *Environmental Science & Technology*

Short abstract

Our research demonstrates the feasibility of cost-effective electrochemical generation of high-strength magnetite nanoparticles (MNP) and its multiple beneficial impacts for sewer management and wastewater treatment in terms of sulfide control, phosphate recovery and increased biogas production. Due to its superparamagnetic properties, efficient and selective magnetic recovery of in-sewer dosed MNP in the downstream digesters can be achieved. The MNP can be regenerated and reused through lime addition, thereby recovering P as Calcium Phosphate. Overall, our study marks an important step forward for wastewater utilities to transition towards a closed-loop approach for chemical usage in our urban wastewater infrastructure.

Microbial PHA recovery from VFA-rich food wastewater: a long-term attempt with one-stage model operation

Xiang Zhang, Ji Zhang, Kexin Wang, Gaojun Wang, Rong Chen
Xi'an University of Architecture and Technology, Xi'an, China

Xiang Zhang

What is your current position?

Ph.D candidate

Short biography of the presenter

Mr. Zhang is a Ph.D candidate in Xi'an University of Architecture and Technology. Currently, Mr. Zhang's research mainly focuses on the PHA recovery from food waste.

Short abstract

To upgrade conventional two-stage system for PHA production, this study attempted a 130-day PHA production system with one-stage operation using VFA-rich food wastewater. Under OLR of 6 gCOD/L/d with feast/famine regulating strategy, the PHA yield and COD-to-PHA conversion efficiency steadily reached 0.62 gPHA/gVSS and 19.0%, which accompanied PHA producer *Azoarcus* enrichment. This produced PHA exhibited comparable physiochemical properties with commercial PHA. However, either transition of dominant VFA type from short-chain to medium-chain ones, or the decline of C/N in substrate decreased PHA production efficiency. These outcomes provided new insights to understand one-stage PHA production system.

Designing, building and operating a scalable methane producing bioelectrochemical system for Power-to-Methane

Annemiek Ter Heijne¹, Micaela Brandao Lavender^{1,2}, Jos Steller^{1,2}, Dandan Liu^{1,2}, Rieks De Rink²

¹Wageningen UR, Wageningen, Netherlands. ²Paqell, Utrecht, Netherlands

Annemiek Ter Heijne

What is your current position?

Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Annemiek ter Heijne is professor and chair on the topic of "(bio)Recovery Technology for Circular Economy at Environmental Technology, Wageningen University & Research. Her aim is to develop new technologies to recover nutrients, metals and carbon from wastewater and wastestreams. She has special interest in the combination of microbial conversions and electrochemistry in Microbial Electrochemical Systems.

Short abstract

- Development of power-to-gas technologies is needed for future renewable fuel and chemicals supply
- Methane producing BESs still face challenges in conversion rate, energy efficiency and scaling up
- A scalable module of 17L with tubular membrane was tested for 470 days
- Interchange of anolyte and catholyte was used to ensure stable conductivity
- Energy efficiency reached up to 40% at current density of $-125 \text{ A/m}^3_{\text{BES}}$
- Further improvements can be made to reduce cathodic and transport losses

Full-scale nutrient recovery in Germany: challenges and barriers to replication and how to overcome them

Anne Kleyböcker¹, Fabian Kraus¹, Stefanie Meyer², Janina Heinze³, Franziska Gromadecki³, Christian Remy¹

¹Kompetenzzentrum Wasser Berlin gGmbH, Berlin, Germany. ²Stadtentwässerung Braunschweig GmbH, Braunschweig, Germany. ³Abwasserverband Braunschweig, Wendeburg, Germany

Anne Kleyböcker

What is your current position?

Project Manager

Short biography of the presenter

Anne Kleyböcker is a scientist and project manager at the Center of Competence for Water in Berlin. She studied civil engineering and has a PhD in process engineering. She works since more than 15 years in the field of circular economy.

Short abstract

An innovative nutrient and energy recovery concept is operated at a municipal wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) with struvite and ammonium sulfate recovery from sludge liquor. The CE fertilizers are well accepted by farmers as long as quality and price are reliable. However, a WWTP operator is not a fertilizer producer, and replication of the concept is challenging due to legal and economic barriers. The EU project BOOST-IN explores ways to overcome these barriers and develops a roadmap for wider replication together with relevant stakeholders from the region.

Sustainable Sludge Management: Piloting of PUB's Continuous Thermal Hydrolysis (CTH)-Pyrolysis for Biochar Production

Miao He¹, Qinqing Cai¹, Yan Gu¹, Yangshuo Gu¹, Guihe Tao¹, Gurdev Singh¹, Chenghong Guo², Yan Zhou³, Shunzhi Qian³

¹PUB, Singapore's National Water Agency, Singapore, Singapore. ²Leaders Environmental Technologies Limited, Singapore, Singapore. ³Nanyang Technological University, Singapore, Singapore

Miao He

What is your current position?

Specialist

Short biography of the presenter

Guihe Tao

What is your current position?

Chief Specialist

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Tao is currently the chief specialist (Used Water Treatment) of PUB, Singapore's National Water Agency. He has over 13 years of experience in designing and implementing membrane bioreactor processes in PUB and overseas. He is the project leader for the Integrated Validation Plant and Demonstration Plant study. Dr Tao has over 25 years of experience in the process design, project management, R&D, and teaching of environmental engineering. He is a member of International Water Association (IWA) and The Institution of Engineers, Singapore (IES). He has published over 70 technical articles in the international journals and conferences.

Gurdev Singh

What is your current position?

the Chief Engineering and Technology Officer

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Gurdev, Chief Engineering and Technology Officer at PUB, Singapore's National Water Agency, oversees the Technology and Engineering Department and Specialist Groups. Since joining PUB in 2016, Dr. Gurdev has played a pivotal role in steering the agency's R&D initiatives, overseeing key projects and driving innovation. He holds a PhD in Civil Engineering from the National University of Singapore (2003) and has completed the Advanced Management Program in Leadership and Management at the University of California, Berkeley (2015), and the Advanced Management Program in Strategy and Business at Nanyang Technological University (2014).

Short abstract

PUB is piloting a combined CTH–pyrolysis process in a 5 tpd facility to evaluate its technical and economic viability for producing biochar from dewatered anaerobic digested (AD) sludge. In the CTH-filter press system, high temperature and pressure break down the cellular structure of dewatered sludge, increasing sludge solids content from 20% to ≥60%. The dried sludge cake then undergoes pyrolysis at 500-600°C to produce biochar, achieving an overall 90% mass reduction. Studies on biochar applications was also carried out to assess biochar's potential reuse as a fuel supplement, activated carbon for odor control, and construction material.

Phosphate removal in WWTP effluent by granular iron rich sludge

Jacqueline de Danschutter¹, [Luuk de Waal](#)^{2,3}, Steven Westermann⁴, Jan Willem Voort⁵, Martijn Olde-Weghuis⁶, Tessa Vrijhoeven², Martijn van Veggel², Erwin Beerendonk², Emile Cornelissen^{3,2}

¹AquaMinerals, Nieuwegein, Netherlands. ²KWR Water Research Institute, Nieuwegein, Netherlands. ³Particle and Interfacial Technology Group Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium. ⁴Hoogheemraadschap Hollands Noorderkwartier, Heerhugowaard, Netherlands. ⁵Waternet, Amsterdam, Netherlands. ⁶Vitens, Zwolle, Netherlands

Jacqueline de Danschutter

What is your current position?

Manager Business Development

Short biography of the presenter

Jacqueline has a background in environmental technology and has been working in the Dutch water sector for over 15 years. Her main focus has always been circularity and the recovery of resources from waste and drinking water.

Luuk de Waal

What is your current position?

PhD

Short biography of the presenter

Male, 30 years, born in the Netherlands. Background in chemistry (BSc.) and Water Technology (MSc.). Researcher at KWR, manager of project-portfolio Watercycle and doctoral candidate at Gent University.

Short abstract

In the Netherlands, 90,000 tons of iron-rich sludge is produced annually from drinking water preparation. This sludge, containing up to 70mass% iron, is currently reused mainly in biogas plants for hydrogen sulfide removal. High transport costs and environmental impact due to low solids content (5-30%) limit broader application. Pelletizing this sludge into granular material improves handling, transport, and sustainability, enabling use as circular adsorbents. Tested at the Geestmerambacht WWTP, these pellets achieved phosphorus removal efficiencies of 69% (30-min EBCT) and 64% (15-min EBCT). A pilot plant in 2025 will refine design parameters for large-scale application in water treatment.

Calcium phosphate pseudomorph formation in cow manure: Selective transformation via incongruent dissolution of struvite and calcium addition

Lilian Quispe^{1,2}, Chris Schott¹, Renata van der Weijden², Cees Buisman^{1,2}

¹Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ²Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, Netherlands

Lilian Quispe

What is your current position?

PhD researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Lilian is a PhD candidate at Wetsus and WUR, working on phosphorus recovery and crystallization processes in animal manure. She holds a Master's degree in Water Technology from a joint program in the Netherlands. Her research focuses on sustainable phosphorus recovery through mineral transformation mechanisms, contributing to innovative solutions for resource recovery.

Short abstract

Phosphorus in cow manure primarily exists as struvite, complicating selective recovery as calcium phosphate (CaP). This study investigates the incongruent dissolution of struvite, focusing on calcium addition for CaP formation. In synthetic manure under thermophilic conditions (55°C) and a Ca:P molar ratio of 5 showed struvite transforming into CaP pseudomorphs. SEM-EDX and PHREEQC modelling validated the mineral transformation. Results demonstrate that struvite could act as a seed particle for CaP growth when its surface develops a coarse CaP layer. This finding introduces a novel strategy for P recovery, enabling efficient nutrient separation from animal manure in anaerobic reactors.

A decade of developing comprehensive nutrient and carbon recovery from municipal wastewater in Helsinki region, Finland

Maria Valtari, Sini Reuna, Kati Blomberg, Kristian Sahlstedt
Helsinki Region Environmental Services HSY, Helsinki, Finland

Maria Valtari

What is your current position?

Head of unit

Short biography of the presenter

Maria Valtari works as head of R&D unit in wastewater sector of Helsinki Region Environmental Services (HSY). Valtari supervises a unit working on different R&D projects (e.g. GHG emission mitigation, nutrients recovery, process optimization) of the two largest wastewater treatment plants in Finland, Viikinmäki and Blominmäki WWTPs. Previously, Valtari has worked as a process designer specializing in wastewater and sludge treatment, and as a researcher. Ms Valtari holds an M.Sc. degree in water engineering, and she continues working with her PhD project on antibiotic resistance of sewage sludge at Aalto University, Helsinki.

Short abstract

Helsinki Region Environmental Services (HSY) has been developing a comprehensive nutrient and carbon recovery concept from municipal wastewater. In the innovative RAVITA™ process, phosphorus is recovered after the tertiary treatment phase of wastewater and refined into phosphoric acid, which could be further used e.g. in stripping of ammonia at the treatment plant (WWTP). In addition, HSY has operated an industrial-scale pilot plant for the pyrolysis of sludge producing sludge char. The presentation provides an insight into the development process of comprehensive nutrient and carbon recovery at a municipal WWTP with its achievements and challenges during the past decade.

Real time monitoring of anaerobic fermentation by Raman and FTIR spectroscopy

Miguel Bouzas¹, Manuel de la Fuente¹, Juan Cubero-Cardoso^{1,2}, Miguel Mauricio Iglesias¹

¹Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, Santiago de Compostela, Spain. ²Universidad de Huelva, Huelva, Spain

Miguel Mauricio Iglesias

What is your current position?

Associate Professor

Short biography of the presenter

I hold a MSc in Chemical Engineering (Univ. Santiago de Compostela, Spain) and a PhD in Food Technology (Univ. Montpellier, France). My current research interests deal with the construction and analysis of mathematical at different scales: metabolic scale models for fermentation understanding; bioreactor scale models for process optimisation and monitoring and biorefinery-wide models for early stage biorefinery design.

Short abstract

A major challenge in carbon recovery through the carboxylate platform is the poor selectivity of anaerobic fermentation in a given carboxylate (e.g. acetate, propionate, butyrate...). Furthermore, our understanding of how changes in fermentation (pH, retention time, substrate concentration...) may be used to steer the fermentation to a targeted product is limited. Vibrational spectroscopy methods (i.e. Raman and FTIR) can be used for real-time process monitoring by estimation of fermentation metabolites and, in some cases, substrate uptake. Combined with process mathematical models, it is possible to obtain real-time evaluation of the fermentation state and propose corrective actions.

Turning resource recovery into real world solutions: Lessons from Dutch water authorities

Ruud Schemen¹, Jouke Boorsma², Eric van der Zandt³

¹Waterschap De Dommel, Boxtel, Netherlands. ²AquaMinerals B.V., Nieuwegein, Netherlands. ³Hoogheemraadschap De Stichtse Rijnlanden, Houten, Netherlands

Ruud Schemen

What is your current position?

sr adviseur Waterketen

Short biography of the presenter

After my study at Wageningen University I start working by the Water Authorities. In this period I have been coördinator at the network organisation "Energy Factory" which is now de Energy and resource factory. At this moment I work at The Dommel and I am chairman of the working group Nutrient recovery of the EFGF.

Short abstract

Fifteen years ago, Dutch water authorities founded the Energy and Resources Factory (EFGF) to recover biobased raw materials, including nutrients, in collaboration with the private sector to develop viable business cases. Initial efforts centered on struvite recovery, creating marketable resources. AquaMinerals, a sector-owned organization, facilitates market introduction by leveraging collective power and expertise. Refining recovered materials to meet market demands often requires technology adaptation, exemplified by vivianite recovery using mining magnets. By acting as a launching customer, water authorities drive value chain development and circular material use, while EFGF plays a pivotal role in knowledge sharing, market alignment, and advocacy.

From saline waste to purple value: Halophilic purple phototrophic bacteria for sustainable mussel wastewater treatment and resource recovery

Sara Olyslaegers¹, Joao Carvalho², Siegfried E. Vlaeminck¹, Joana Fradinho², Luis D. Allegue¹

¹University of Antwerp, Antwerp, Belgium. ²NOVA University Lisbon, Caparica, Portugal

Sara Olyslaegers

What is your current position?

PhD candidate

Short biography of the presenter

Sara Olyslaegers is a PhD student at the department of bioscience engineering at the University of Antwerp. She is currently exploring innovative approaches in using marine and halophilic bacteria to enhance aquaculture practices.

Short abstract

The European Union, the world's second-largest mussel producer after China (EUFOMA 2021), generates up to 400 L t⁻¹ of cooking water during the industrial thermal treatment of canned mussels. This high-salinity wastewater complicates treatment and increases the costs for producing companies. This research explores using halophilic purple phototrophic bacteria to both treat the water and recovering the organics into microbial protein, reducing reliance on fishmeal for aquafeed. Halophilic PPB exhibit higher levels of valuable pigments, such as bacteriochlorophyll and carotenoids, along with superior antioxidant properties compared to freshwater PPB, offering enhanced valorization potential as high-value ingredient for aquaculture.

Influence of pH and sulfide exposure time on polysulfide formation, internal cell-bound sulfane, and implications for design of the biological desulfurization process at haloalkaline conditions

Kestral Johnston¹, Chenxiao Xu¹, Renata Vičević¹, Pieter van Veelen¹, Rieks de Rink², Annemerel Mol³, Karel Keesman¹, Cees Buisman¹

¹Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ²Paqell B.V., Utrecht, Netherlands. ³Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, Netherlands

Annemerel Mol

What is your current position?

Assistant professor

Short biography of the presenter

I'm curious about the capacity microorganisms have to recover valuable solid resources from (waste)water. I enjoy teaching students about technologies involving such microbial reactions and their role in a circular economy. My core expertise is recovery of minerals and metals (such as S, Se, As, Fe and Mn) from wastewater using microbiological processes and (bio)crystallization. To work on real life environmental issues, I have established various partnerships with companies in both the drinking water production and industrial wastewater treatment sector. I'm currently supervising five PhD students, and collaborate with Wetsus, European centre of excellence for sustainable water technology.

Short abstract

Biological desulfurization under halo-alkaline conditions is a widely applied gas desulfurization technology. Although the process has been studied for over 30 years, knowledge on polysulfides as key-intermediates, is still largely absent. New developments in the process configuration, being the addition of an anaerobic, sulfidic stirred bioreactor, provide extra motivation for this research. We elucidated the effect of pH and sulfide exposure time on polysulfide formation, uptake and product selectivity. It was found that internal cell-bound sulfane plateaus at 0.05 mM-S/mg-N and that at pH ~9.3, long sulfide exposure time works adversely due to chemical oxidation of polysulfides to thiosulfate.

From lab to pilot and back again: elucidating pH challenges in PHA production during scale-up

Andreea-Melisa Tripon^{1,2}, Jelmer Tamis³, Eline van der Knaap², Guido Maat⁴, Sergio Dries³, Horia Leonard Banciu⁵, Robbert Kleerebezem², Gerben R. Stouten^{6,2}

¹Doctoral School of Integrative Biology, Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania. ²Department of Biotechnology, Delft University of Technology, Delft, Netherlands. ³Paques Biomaterials BV, Balk, Netherlands. ⁴Smurfit Kappa BV, Roermond, Netherlands. ⁵Department of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Biology and Geology, "Babeş-Bolyai" University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania. ⁶Max Planck Institute for Biology, Tübingen, Germany

Andreea-Melisa Tripon

What is your current position?

PhD Student

Short biography of the presenter

Holds a Bachelor's degree in Biology (2020) and a Master's degree in Molecular Biotechnology (2022) from the Faculty of Biology and Geology at Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania. Currently pursuing a PhD in Integrative Biology, specializing in microbiology and biotechnology, with a focus on innovative microbial approaches for producing polyhydroxyalkanoates.

Short abstract

Upscaling bioprocesses from the lab often runs into issues. This study presents a PHA pilot-plant using fermented wastewater from a paper recycling facility, which yielded poor results in its first year. To assess the impact of pH fluctuations, five lab-scale reactors were operated for four months at varying pH levels. Results confirmed that the feast-famine enrichment principle works in neutral-alkaline conditions but fails below pH 6. Adjusting feeding patterns enabled PHA accumulation at pH 6, and on implementation improved pilot-scale performance instantly. This highlights the critical interplay between lab and full-scale processes in using fundamental insights to address upscaling challenges.

Valorization of Fish Sludge through Anaerobic Fermentation: Volatile Fatty Acid Production for Nutrient Recovery

Linnéa Otterheim, Zeynep Cetecioglu, Isaac Owusu-Agyeman
KTH - Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm, Sweden

Linnéa Otterheim

What is your current position?

PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

Linnéa is a PhD student in biotechnology at KTH in Stockholm. She has a passion for the environment and works towards developing strategies for a more sustainable world. Her project focuses on developing a circular process in the aquaculture industry, aiming to produce fish feed from fish sludge. She has a MSc in Environmental and Industrial Biotechnology from KTH. Her thesis work focused on bioleaching of metals from Baltic Sea sediment.

Short abstract

The study investigates the production of volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from fish sludge (FS) via anaerobic fermentation. After FS characterization, batch tests were conducted to explore the impact of hydrothermal pretreatment, retention time, and pH. VFA inhibition was tested since FS contains high VFA levels (41 g/L). Initial results show that existing VFAs inhibited hydrolysis at pH 5 and 10 and reduced VFA production at pH 10 but not at pH 5. Pretreatment failed to enhance solubility or VFA yield. Future research aims to utilize the VFAs as substrates for producing single-cell protein, intending to create sustainable fish feed.

Model-Based Design of Fermentation Processes for Tailored Odd-Chain Volatile Fatty Acid Production

Sara García-Gago, Miguel Mauricio-Iglesias, [Alberte Regueira](#)

CRETUS, Chemical Engineering Department, Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, Santiago de Compostela, Spain

Alberte Regueira

What is your current position?

Assistant Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Alberte obtained a Phd on modelling mixed-culture fermentations for the production of volatile fatty acids at the University of Santiago de Compostela in 2020. Soon after, he moved to Ghent University, where he worked in chain elongation processes for high-value carboxylic acids production. Since 2023, he is an Assistant Professor at the Chemical Engineering Department (Universidade de Santiago de Compostela). His main research interests are centred on open culture fermentation processes for carbon recovery from wastes with an emphasis on understanding the mechanisms controlling the process both from an experimental and modelling perspective.

Short abstract

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) production from waste-sourced volatile fatty acids (VFA) is an emerging alternative to plastics. To tune PHA properties, the fraction of odd-chain VFA should be controlled, which remains a challenge due to fermentation variability. We develop a modelling framework that serves as a user guide for waste selection and for fermentation design. Model results show that different wastes have different optimal operational conditions (HRT, pH) for producing VFA mixtures with a high odd-chain share. Thus, this modelling framework represents an early-stage design tool to help establishing the waste-to-bioplastics value chain.

Biomimetic Aquaporin Membranes: A Novel Approach to Steel Wastewater Regeneration

Xuefei Yang¹, Jörg Vogel², Cristina Martínez¹ Martínez¹

¹CETIM Technological Center, Culleredo, Spain. ²Aquaporin A/S, Kongens Lyngby, Denmark

Xuefei Yang

What is your current position?

Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Xuefei Yang is an Environmental Engineer with a PhD in Environmental Engineering from the Polytechnic University of Catalonia (UPC). She works at CETIM Technological Center, Spain, as a researcher in the R&D&I line of Water Treatment, specializing in membrane technologies. She is currently the technical leader of the Horizon project RESURGENCE.

Short abstract

This study evaluates the use of Aquaporin's biomimetic forward osmosis (FO) and brackish water reverse osmosis (BWRO) membranes for lab-scale steel wastewater regeneration, compared to commercial RO membranes. The innovative Aquaporin Inside® technology integrates aquaporin proteins, enhancing water flux and contaminant rejection while reducing energy consumption of the RO by 20-30%. Results demonstrate improved treatment efficiency and reduced fouling, positioning Aquaporin's membranes as a sustainable solution for the steel industry. This approach addresses water scarcity and optimises operational efficiency in industrial water management.

Navigating conflicts and synergies in resource recovery

Jouke Boorsma¹, Leonie Hartog²

¹AquaMinerals, Nieuwegein, Netherlands. ²Waterschap Brabantse Delta, Breda, Netherlands

Jouke Boorsma

What is your current position?

Manager projects/business developer

Short biography of the presenter

Jouke Boorsma is dedicated to sustainable development, focusing on waste management and water resources. Holding an MSc in Technology and Innovation Policy from the University of Eindhoven, Boorsma tackles environmental challenges, in both developed and developing nations. As a Business Developer/Manager Projects at AquaMinerals, Boorsma advocates for circular economy practices, giving residuals a second life and aiming for sustainable solutions. Boorsma believes in collaboration, innovation, and sustainability for a brighter future

Short abstract

Transitioning to circular wastewater treatment requires integrating multi-resource recovery systems. Dutch developments demonstrate progress in recovering carbon (e.g., biomethane, VFA, Caleyda) and phosphorus (struvite, vivianite, ash-based methods). However, conflicts and synergies between technologies must be addressed. A confrontation matrix highlights key dilemmas, such as balancing biogas production with material recovery and selecting complementary phosphorus recovery methods. Success depends on considering CO₂ footprints, market potential, and societal acceptance. Strategic development pathways are essential to overcome these challenges and achieve scalable, multi-dimensional resource recovery systems, aligning environmental goals with economic feasibility.

Comparison of physicochemical changes in carbon and nutrients of anaerobically digested, composted or fermented single dairy manure input

Lourens van Langeveld^{1,2}, Paul Bodelier³, Miriam van Eekert², Valentina Sechi¹, Cees Buisman¹

¹Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ²Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, Netherlands. ³NIOO-KNAW, Wageningen, Netherlands

Lourens van Langeveld

What is your current position?

PhD candidate

Short biography of the presenter

I am researching a variety of cow manure treatments and their application to soils in order to increase soil organic matter content while minimizing GHG emissions. The goal is to improve overall soil functionalities, among which carbon storage and drought resilience through the development and integration of treatment technologies.

Short abstract

Intensified agriculture and excess use of dairy manure have caused a loss of soil functionalities, one of which is carbon storage that regulates other functionalities (Wiesmeier et al., 2019). Organic Amendments can be used as an alternative to improve SOC and thus soil functionalities (Hoffland et al. 2020). By biologically (pre)-treating dairy manure, its physicochemical properties were changed, allowing to parse the effects of different treatment technologies on soil functionality following OA application. These may pave the way forward to more efficient usage and management of organic residues through carbon and nutrient recovery with implications for restoring soil functionalities.

From Sludge to Solution: Acidified Drinking Water Sludge for Efficient Phosphorus Removal in WWTPs

Sabina Bec, Maria Hyvönen, Mirka Viitala, Mika Mänttari
LUT University, Lappeenranta, Finland

Sabina Bec

What is your current position?

Junior Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

I am Sabina Bec, a researcher in Chemical Engineering at LUT University, Lappeenranta, Finland, with a focus on sustainable wastewater treatment. My work explores innovative processes for resource recovery by recycling wastewater side streams. By advancing our understanding of wastewater treatment, I aim to contribute to more sustainable practices that transform waste into valuable resources, paving the way for a circular economy in water management.

Short abstract

Acidifying drinking water sludge (DWS) enhances its ability to remove soluble phosphorus from wastewater, enabling lower dosing levels (mg total solids (TS) per liter) compared to previous studies (g TS/L). Acidification standardizes the performance of DWSs from different sources, with efficiency linked to the metal content (iron in this study). This approach achieved 90% soluble phosphorus removal at initial molar ratios of $\text{Fe}_{\text{DWS}}:\text{P}_{\text{sol}}$ around 2.5, comparable to the effectiveness of commercial coagulants.

Enrichment of polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) accumulating bacteria through uncoupled feeding of carbon and nitrogen in a semi-continuous system

Jinsong Wang^{1,2}, Vittoria Stefanelli³, Suzanne Holst¹, Jelmer Tamis¹, Robbert Kleerebezem^{1,2}

¹Department of Biotechnology, Delft University of Technology, Delft, Netherlands. ²UNLOCK, Wageningen University & Research / Delft University of Technology, Wageningen, Netherlands. ³Department of Chemistry "Giacomo Ciamician", University of Bologna, Ravenna, Italy

Jinsong Wang

What is your current position?

Postdoc researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Jinsong Wang is a postdoctoral researcher in the Department of Biotechnology at TU Delft, where he also serves as the technical manager for the Parallel Cultivation Platform of UNLOCK. Before joining UNLOCK, Dr. Wang completed his PhD at Wageningen University & Research and postdoc research at KU Leuven, where he mainly focused on micropollutant biodegradation in oligotrophic waters. His current research interests include resource recovery from waste(water), with a particular emphasis on microbial interactions within complex communities.

Short abstract

Microbial polymers known as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are promising biodegradable materials to replace petroleum-based plastics. A cost-effective strategy for PHA production involves the enrichment of microbial cultures with high PHA-producing capacities using low-value feedstocks. However, achieving a consistently high and stable PHA content in microorganisms remains a challenge with traditional feast-famine enrichment approaches. Here we investigated a novel strategy to enhance PHA accumulation based on uncoupled feeding of carbon and nitrogen in a semi-continuous enrichment system. The impact of key operational variables, including the C/N ratios and volumetric exchange ratios, were assessed to investigate the culture enrichment and PHA production.

Exploring multiple industrial scale concepts for PHA production from residual organic streams.

João Sousa

Paques Biomaterials B.V., Balk, Netherlands

João Sousa

What is your current position?

Technology Development Lead

Short biography of the presenter

João Sousa came to the Netherlands in 2012 to acquire his PhD degree in Microbiology via Wageningen University and Wetsus. Soon after, he started working at Paques, a global leader in anaerobic wastewater and biogas treatment where he became Head of Emerging Technologies. In 2021, Paques Biomaterials was carved out from Paques to pursue its own path towards implementing PHA production from waste streams. Following his passion, João joined this new adventure from day 1 as Technology Development Lead, keeping an overview on all R&D developments from PHA accumulation by bacteria, PHA extraction and application development.

Short abstract

In the last 2 decades several research initiatives have shown the potential of producing PHA biopolymers using different organic residual streams as feedstock. But how to bring all these technologies into the reality of large industrial scale?

Paques Biomaterials is taking up this challenge with different partners and exploring several concepts for PHA production using residual streams: recycling paper mills process water, agri-food organic residues, source separated organics and municipal sludges. Let us take you along these circular options in PHA production, and the bold steps Paques Biomaterials is taking to implement its first PHA production plants in the Netherlands.

Low-energy thermal stripping to recover quality ammonia for the water sector

Mark Powders¹, Mingming Zhu¹, Pete Vale², Adam Brookes³, David Inman³, Chris Jones⁴, Matt Pickersgill⁴, Ewan McAdam¹

¹Cranfield University, Cranfield, United Kingdom. ²Severn Trent Water, Coventry, United Kingdom. ³Anglian Water, Peterborough, United Kingdom. ⁴Northumbrian Water, Durham, United Kingdom

Mark Powders

What is your current position?

PhD Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Mark Powders is a PhD research student at Cranfield University, UK and belongs to the Water Infrastructure and Resilience 'WIRe' CDT. His research focuses on the recovery of ammonia from wastewater by thermal stripping and the use of the concentrated ammonia product as a zero-carbon fuel. Mark previously undertook research also in resource recovery during his Chemical Engineering MSc at the University of Birmingham where he investigated the production of a green solvent from post-consumer bioplastics.

Short abstract

Thermal stripper design is introduced that reduces energy demand for ammonia recovery by two orders of magnitude and achieves a highly concentrated ammonia product whose quality exceeds that of existing technologies. This is facilitated by characterising the ammonia-water vapour-liquid equilibrium within the region relevant for wastewater, providing new mechanistic insight on which to create disruptive thermal stripper design. A balance between vacuum pressure and temperature is also uniquely demonstrated in real wastewater to offer 'chemical free' or 'heat free' ammonia recovery, evidencing this new thermal stripping architecture to be low cost, and practicable for lowering carbon and improving regulatory compliance.

3D evaporative crystallization for selective lithium recovery from spent lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) leachate

Qian Xu, Yanhong Bian, Xi Chen
Tsinghua University, Beijing, China

Qian Xu

What is your current position?

Master's Degree Candidate

Short biography of the presenter

Qian Xu received her B.S. degree in Environmental Engineering from Tsinghua University in 2024. She is currently a master student in Resources and Environmental Engineering direction at School of Environment, Tsinghua University. Her research interests include spent lithium-ion battery recovery and lithium extraction from saline water.

Short abstract

The increasing demand for lithium is surpassing current supply levels. Lithium recovery from spent lithium-ion batteries is expected to bridge this gap, but current processes are energy- and chemically intensive. Here we propose a sustainable approach through a sequential 3D crystallization of different salt species which was enabled by a porous cotton crystallizers with a horizontal capillary flow toward the far end. The process delivers selectivity ratios of Li/Co, Li/Ni, and Li/Mn at 6611, 21, and 4, respectively, while significantly reducing both carbon emission and costs by orders of magnitude compared with traditional solvent extraction method.

Fluidic 3D evaporative crystallization for lithium extraction from ultra-high Mg brine sources

Xi Chen, Haixu Hou, Yanhong Bian
Tsinghua University, Beijing, China

Xi Chen

What is your current position?

Associate Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Xi Chen received her dual B.S. degrees in Environmental Engineering and Economics from Tsinghua University. She obtained her Ph.D. in Environmental Science and Engineering also from Tsinghua. Dr. Chen currently serves as an Associate Professor at the School of Environment, Tsinghua University. Her research is centered on harnessing innovative physio-chemical processes and advanced materials for water treatment, resource recovery, and zero-liquid-discharge, contributing to the carbon neutrality in water sector.

Short abstract

The rapid growth in lithium (Li) demand has heightened the need for Li extraction from a wider range of sources, including brines with high Mg/Li ratios that are extensively distributed worldwide. Conventional solar ponds are ineffective for Li separation from Mg-rich brines, while direct Li extraction methods relied on substantial energy and reagent usage. Here we present a sustainable-energy-driven and reagent-conserving approach, termed fluidic 3D evaporative crystallization process, which achieves record-high selectivity ratios of Li/Na, Li/K, and Li/Mg, exceeding 2800, 3800, and 320, respectively, from an ultra-high Mg brine (Mg/Li ratio, MLR, >650).

Phosphorus and ammonia recovery through bio-mineral formation

Eric Eric.Hagenimana@cranfield.ac.uk¹, Gautier Prot¹, Ajay Nair², Ana Soares¹

¹Cranfield University, Cranfield, United Kingdom. ²Microvi Biotech, San Francisco, USA

Ana Soares

What is your current position?

Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Ana Soares is a full Professor of Biotechnology Engineering at Cranfield Water Science Institute, Cranfield University, UK. She is an IWA Fellow and leads the Resource Recovery Community of Practice at Cranfield University. Her research focuses on the behaviour and manipulation of bacterial communities under dynamic conditions, leading to new technologies, process optimisation and valuable product recovery. Her research is applied in municipal as well as industrial wastewater, proposing innovative and economically feasible solutions to produce high quality effluents and resource recovery.

Professor Soares co-chairs the IWA Resource Recovery Cluster.

Short abstract

Nutrients must be removed and recovered under the recast Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive. Existing technologies are not fit for purpose and new thinking is needed. The use of microorganisms with specific pathways that can specifically capture nutrients from wastewater, in return producing bio-minerals is increasing in TRL, enabled by the application of immobilisation technologies and offer significant advantages over existing options. The bio-mineral P removal (BMPR) process is being deployed at Minworth WWTP and also tested for recovering nutrients from urine. The latest data shows over 90% P removal and recovery in 2-10h and struvite bio-mineral recovery with high-purity.

Pilot-Scale Insights into Phosphorus Recovery through Fluidized Bed Vivianite Crystallization

Wokke Wijdeveld, Chenxiao Xu
Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands

Wokke Wijdeveld

What is your current position?

Scientific Project Manager

Short biography of the presenter

Wokke Wijdeveld is a Scientific Project Manager at Wetsus, specializing in phosphorus recovery and knowledge valorization. With a background in Applied Earth Sciences (TU Delft) and Mining Engineering and Mineral Processing (Aalto University, Finland), Wokke focuses on water technology in urban mining.

At Wetsus, Wokke began with the ViviMag project, piloting magnetic vivianite recovery from digested sewage sludge. Later, he led efforts in the Water-Mining project, upscaling technologies like phosphorus adsorption and vivianite crystallization. Currently, Wokke drives technology transfer through the Netherlands Enabling Water technology program and collaborates with the mining industry to address water-related challenges for sustainable mining practices.

Short abstract

This study explores the selective recovery of phosphorus (P) from urban wastewater using vivianite crystallization. It evaluates fluidized bed crystallizers (FBC) for P removal and recovery from anaerobic effluent with 5-10 mg P/L. Lab- and pilot-scale experiments investigated factors like pH, iron dosing, and seed loading. Visual MINTEQ modeling confirmed the feasibility of vivianite recovery. Optimal conditions included an Fe/P molar ratio of 1.8 and a seed loading of 75 g/L, achieving 95% reactive P removal and 79% P recovery. Organic matter in the effluent affected crystal growth and purity. These findings support large-scale FBC application.

Microbial Conversion of Cheese Whey to Medium-Chain Fatty Acids: Optimization of Organic Loading Rates, Fermentation Cycles, and pH

Nuria Otero-Logilde, Christian Kennes, [María C. Veiga](#)
University of A Coruña, A Coruña, Spain

María C. Veiga

What is your current position?

Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Maria C. Veiga holds a Ph.D. in Environmental Engineering from the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain). She is a Full Professor of Chemical Engineering at the University of A Coruña (Spain). She also worked as a postdoctoral researcher at Michigan State University (USA). Her expertise lies in environmental biotechnology, with a particular focus on the development of sustainable bioprocesses for the removal of pollutants from wastewater and the utilization of industrial wastes for the production of biopolymers and bulk chemicals.

Short abstract

This study explores the production of medium-chain fatty acids (MCFA) through chain elongation using cheese whey as a substrate. Key findings include the optimization of organic loading rates (OLR) and feeding cycles for higher MCFA yields, particularly caproic and caprylic acids. Lower OLR enhanced caproic acid production. Additionally, the research demonstrates that the MCFA-rich effluent can be used for polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) production, achieving a notable accumulation rate. These results highlight the potential of cheese whey as a sustainable feedstock for both MCFAs and biopolymer production.

Acceptance type: Poster

#1.3

Paving the way for decarbonisation of China's wastewater treatment systems

Hao Xu¹, Qian Ye², Guangtao Fu¹, Shuning Shi¹, Yincheng Liu¹, Danyang Gao¹, Xiaoyu Yan¹

¹University of Exeter, Exeter, United Kingdom. ²University of Leeds, Leeds, United Kingdom

Hao Xu

What is your current position?

PhD candidate

Short biography of the presenter

Hao Xu is a PhD candidate in Renewable Energy at the University of Exeter. His research focuses on the sustainable development of water system, applying life cycle assessment to quantify the environmental impacts of water system.

Short abstract

This study evaluated the decarbonisation potentials of multiple strategies including resource and energy recovery in China's urban water system using life cycle assessment approach. The recovery strategies, including reclaimed water production and use, wastewater thermal energy recovery, sludge biogas recovery, sludge liquid phosphorus recovery, sludge co-incineration and sludge land application were assessed under future conditions. Our findings indicate that energy and resource recovery can mitigate 12.11 and 22.50 Mt CO₂-Eq by 2050. A mix of strategies within the urban water system jurisdictions can reduce global warming impacts up to 67.02%, along with synergistic mitigations of other environmental impacts.

#1.10

Onsite Phosphorous Remobilization for efficient P-Recycling

Joachim Clemens, Christine Oeppert
SF-SoepenberG GmbH, Hünxe, Germany

Joachim Clemens

What is your current position?

Head of Research & Development

Short biography of the presenter

Diplom Geoecologist

PhD at Bayreuth University, Germany

Founder & owner of gewitra mbH (biological waste treatment & greenhouse gas emissions)

Assistant Professor at Bonn University, Germany

Now: Head of R&D at SF-SoepenberG GmbH

private hobbies: small scale photovoltaic systems as a vehicle for
social participation and engagement in communities

Short abstract

We present a technology to remobilizes P from activated excess sludge followed by struvite precipitation at waste water treatment plants. It is suitable for bio-P or Fe-P sludge. The methodology has been tested at a waste water treatment plant for three months. With this technology more than 50% of the P flow into a waste water treatment plant can be recycled.

#1.28

Hydrochar from sewage sludge as biomass waste for a circular approach in environmental applications

Matheus Cavali, [Nelson Libardi](#), Rejane Helena Ribeiro da Costa, Rodrigo de Almeida Mohedano, Paulo Belli Filho, Armando Borges de Castilhos Junior
Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, Brazil

Nelson Libardi

What is your current position?

Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Environmental Engineer, PhD in Bioprocess Engineering. Resource recovery; Wastewater treatment

Short abstract

Waste valorization is mandatory to develop a circular bioeconomy. It is necessary to search appropriate processes to add value to different wastes by utilizing them as feedstocks to provide energy, chemicals, and materials. Concerning waste biomass valorization, hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) is a promising route given its advantages over other thermochemical processes. Crop and forestry residues and sewage sludge are two categories of lignocellulosic and non-lignocellulosic biomass wastes readily available for HTC. In the environmental field, hydrochar might be suitable for removing pollutants from aqueous systems, ameliorating soils, adsorbing atmospheric pollutants, working as an energy carrier, and performing carbon sequestrations.

#1.29

Direct Synthesis of Zeolites using Hazardous Aluminum Salt Slag and Rice Husk Ash

Magali Ritter^{1,2}, Isabel Padilla², María Ángeles Lobo-Recio¹, Maria Eliza Nagel-Hassemer¹, Maximina Romero², Aurora López-Delgado², Nelson Libardi Junior¹

¹Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC), Florianópolis, Brazil. ²Eduardo Torroja Institute of Construction Sciences (IETcc-CSIC), Madrid, Spain

Magali Ritter

What is your current position?

Post-doctoral researcher

Short biography of the presenter

PhD in Environmental Engineering from the Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC) and PhD in Applied Chemistry from the Autonomous University of Madrid (UAM), with a doctoral research internship at the MEDES group of the Eduardo Torroja Institute of Construction Sciences (IETcc-CSIC) in Madrid, Spain.

Post-doctoral researcher of the Water Reuse Laboratory (LaRA) at UFSC. She works in wastewater treatment research with an emphasis on the use of advanced technologies. Her most recent work is based on the synthesis of environmentally friendly adsorbent zeolites produced from hazardous industrial waste, both technologies aimed at the treatment of textile effluents.

Nelson Libardi Junior

What is your current position?

Assistant professor

Short biography of the presenter

Environmental Engineer and Master in Process Engineering. Sandwich master's degree at the Helmholtz Environmental Research Center (UFZ/Germany). PhD in Bioprocess Engineering and Biotechnology from the Federal University of Paraná (UFPR). Post-doctorate PNPd at the Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC). Adjunct professor in the Department of Sanitary and Environmental Engineering at UFSC. Experience in bioprocesses for the treatment of domestic and industrial effluents, in the production of metabolites and microbial biomass, as well as in the degradation/reuse of nutrients and pollutants on bench and pilot scales. Author of scientific and technological development projects in environmental biotechnology.

Short abstract

Salt slags from the aluminum recycling industry pose environmental challenges due to their toxic and reactive nature. These wastes, rich in aluminum, offer potential as raw materials for zeolite synthesis. Zeolites, valued for applications in catalysis, decontamination, and water treatment, are in high demand. Combining aluminum salt slags with silicon-rich rice husk ash (RHA), an abundant and low-cost waste, enables sustainable zeolite production via hydrothermal processes under moderate conditions. This study highlights the synthesis of different zeolite types such as NaP, LTA, ANA and Cancrinite, promoting circular economy and sustainability while offering innovative solutions for waste valorization and pollutant adsorption.

#1.30

BOOST-IN: Enhancing Circular Economy Adoption in Water Management through Innovative Solutions and Stakeholder Engagement

Rafael Casielles Restoy¹, Angela Magno¹, Christian Remy², Blanca Antizar³

¹BIOAZUL, Malaga, Spain. ²KOMPETENZ WASSER, Berlin, Germany. ³ISLE UTILITIES, London, United Kingdom

Rafael Casielles Restoy

What is your current position?

Project manager

Short biography of the presenter

Chemical Engineer from the University of Malaga with a focus on Environmental Engineering, and holds a Master degree in International Cooperation for Development. He is R&D senior consultant in BIOAZUL with more than 16 years of experience in the management of research and innovation projects. Rafael has worked in the validation and transfer of water reuse technologies in the frame of several EU projects such as TREAT&USE, RichWater and SUWANU EUROPE. Rafael is member of Body of Knowledge for Water Scarcity within EIT RIS programme and secretariat of the Working Group Water&Agri-food of the Water Europe Platform.

Short abstract

BOOST-IN is an EU-funded initiative aimed at accelerating the adoption of circular economy practices in the water sector. The project tackles barriers to water reuse, resource recovery, and waste reduction through innovative solutions and a robust multi-stakeholder approach. By identifying and assessing over 500 Water Circular Economy Solutions (WACES), BOOST-IN fosters cross-sector collaboration, policy recommendations, and awareness campaigns in six targeted European regions. The project's goal is to enable sustainable water management, reduce environmental impact, and enhance societal acceptance of circular practices. BOOST-IN's findings support regional policy reforms and market-ready innovations for a resilient, circular water economy.

#1.31

Innovative Magnetic Strategies for Sustainable Phosphorus Recovery

Marcel Cwienczek, Sarah Di Nonno, Roland Ulber
RPTU, Chair of Bioprocess Engineering, Kaiserslautern, Germany

Marcel Cwienczek

What is your current position?

PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

Since 05/2024: Conducting doctoral research at the RPTU in Kaiserslautern at the Department of Bioprocess Engineering

04/2022 - 03/2024: Master's degree in Bio- and Chemical Engineering, RPTU in Kaiserslautern
Topic of the Master's thesis: "Electro-biotechnological production of succinic acid"

10/2017 - 04/2022: Bachelor's degree in Biochemical and Chemical Engineering, TUK
Topic of the Bachelor's thesis: "Electrofermentation with Clostridium acetobutylicum"

Short abstract

Phosphorus has been identified as one of the 30 critical resources for the European Union economy. Furthermore, phosphorus losses are significant, making recovery from waste streams a valuable endeavour. Wastewater represents the most promising opportunity for phosphorus recovery and therefore requires the development of an innovative approach. The aim of this project is to develop such a new scalable recovery process for P, by using magnetic separation. This technique has several advantages over the conventional use of precipitation. The main challenges are the development of magnetic particles that specifically bind phosphorus and the development of a suitable magnetic separation system.

#1.32

Development of an online Dynamic Extinction Spectroscopy Sensor for Real-Time Monitoring of Precipitation and Crystallization Processes in Phosphorus Recovery

Jan Erik Ludorf, Marc Weirich, Sergiy Antonyuk
University of Kaiserslautern-Landau, Kaiserslautern, Germany

Jan Erik Ludorf

What is your current position?

PhD Student

Short biography of the presenter

I am a researcher with a background in mechanical and computational engineering from the University of Kaiserslautern-Landau, currently pursuing a PhD in an interdisciplinary research training group focused on phosphorus recovery from wastewater (WERA). My project involves developing a high-resolution online measurement system for dynamic extinction spectroscopy (DES), integrating statistical and spectral methods. By combining experimental data with computational modeling, my work bridges macroscopic process analysis and microscopic insights, providing a deeper understanding of critical mechanisms like crystallization, particle interactions, and the influence of key process parameters.

Short abstract

This work investigates the kinetics of precipitation and crystallization processes for the recovery of phosphorus from wastewater using dynamic extinction spectroscopy (DES). A high-resolution online measurement system is developed to measure particle size and concentration changes in the size range of 50 nm up to 1 mm. The DES data can be used to enhance the Population Balance Model (PBM) by providing insights into material functions, which can be obtained on the microscale from coupled Discrete Element Method - Computational Fluid Dynamics simulations. This study aims to optimize phosphorus recovery through combined measurements and simulations, addressing critical influences of process parameters.

#1.33

Upscaling ammonium recovery via pilot scale bipolar membrane electro dialysis (BPMED)

Gladys Mutahi¹, Ian Tomassen², Tuur van den Eijnde², Jules van Lier¹, Henri Spanjers¹

¹Technical university of Delft, Delft, Netherlands. ²Nijhuis Saur Industries, Doetinchem, Netherlands

Gladys Mutahi

What is your current position?

PhD Candidate

Short biography of the presenter

I am a 4th Year PhD Candidate at The Technical University of Delft, the Netherlands. My research focuses on the application of electro dialysis with bipolar membranes for the removal and recovery of nitrogen from wastewater streams. With a foundation in Environmental Engineering (BSc, University of Nairobi, Kenya) and Water Technology (MSc, Wetsus Academy, the Netherlands), I am passionate about nutrient recovery driven by the need to advance circular economies and sustainability. Over the years, I've completed several research endeavors specifically targeting the recovery of phosphorus and nitrogen from wastewater streams.

Short abstract

Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) with onsite sludge digestion often require side-stream nitrogen removal to meet stringent effluent standards. Air stripping and acid scrubbing (ASAS) is a cost effective nitrogen removal technology, but it requires continuous acid input and strong mineral acids, posing operation risks. We propose to integrate organic acid ASAS and bipolar membrane electro dialysis (BPMED) to regenerate scrubber acid and recover dissolved ammonia. We evaluate a pilot scale BPMED system using real ASAS effluent from a Dutch WWTP. Furthermore, we investigate ammonia back diffusion and demonstrate 70% coulombic efficiency, at 4-6 kWh/ kg-N for a 2% dissolved ammonia product.

#1.34

Anaerobic sulphide removal involves an intricate interplay between biomass, biosulphur, and dissolved compounds

Rikke Linssen, Sanne De Smit, Annemiek Ter Heijne
Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, Netherlands

Rikke Linssen

What is your current position?

PhD candidate

Short biography of the presenter

After Rikke graduated from MSc Biotechnology, specialised in Process design, at Wageningen University in 2020 she started her PhD in bioelectrochemistry at the department of Environmental Technology at Wageningen University. Here she studies intermittent change storage in sulphide oxidising bacteria.

Short abstract

Haloalkaline sulphide oxidising bacteria in biological sulphur remediation processes have been shown to spatially separate sulphide removal from oxygen consumption. To better understand anaerobic sulphide removal, sulphide removal was measured in batch in biodesulphurisation effluent and different combinations of its constituents (biomass, biosulphur, and dissolved fraction). Four sulphide removal processes could be distinguished: one occurring in the dissolved fraction, two facilitated by biosulphur particles, and three involving biological activity. Where earlier it was thought that only biomass was involved in sulphide removal, our findings show that anaerobic sulphide removal is an intricate interplay between biomass, sulphur particles, and dissolved compounds.

#1.35

Can lime precipitates play a role in phosphorus and nitrogen recovery from wastewater treatment plants?

Francica Cunha¹, Sofia Pereira¹, Tiago Martins^{1,2,3}, Leonor Amaral^{1,4}

¹NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University of Lisbon, Lisbon, Portugal. ²KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium.

³Nijhuis Saur Industries, Doetinchem, Netherlands. ⁴CENSE (Center for Environmental and Sustainability Research) & CHANGE (Global Change and Sustainability Institute), Lisbon, Portugal

Tiago Martins

What is your current position?

PhD Candidate / R&D Engineer

Short biography of the presenter

Tiago Martins earned his Bachelor's degree in Environmental Engineering in 2020 and a Master's in Sanitary Engineering with Magna Cum Laude honours in 2022, both from NOVA University of Lisbon. He then worked as a researcher on treated wastewater reuse at NOVA and was later invited to lecture at the University of Shanghai. In 2024, he began his PhD in Engineering Technology at KU Leuven through the Marie-Sklodowska Curie INCLUE project, supervised by Nadine Boelee, Raf Dewil, and Merle de Kreuk. Although experienced in wastewater treatment technologies, Tiago is currently concentrating his work on the removal of metals from sludges.

Short abstract

Wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) are facing stricter effluent quality standards, which is leading to the reassessment of solid-phase treatment rejected water contributions. The lime precipitates, a by-product of drinking water treatment, can help achieve carbon neutrality while removing and recovering phosphorus and nitrogen from the sludge thickening and dewatering reject water treatment. Analytical tests showed that phosphorus is highly removed (99%), possibly through hydroxyapatite formation, which can be used as an agricultural fertiliser. However, nitrogen presents lower removal (30%), transforming ammonium into ammonia, requiring additional recovery steps, possibly stripping. The use of all these subproducts creates a new value chain.

#1.36

How to turn from traditional to circular cities for sustainable urban & industrial biowaste management: UNITEC CIRCLES project

Johanna Zambrano, Javier Rico, Eugenio Marin, Juan Arévalo, Naiara Hernández, [Patricia Zamora](#), Victor Monsalvo, Frank Rogalla
FCC Aqualia, Madrid, Spain

Eugenio Marin

What is your current position?

Project Manager

Short biography of the presenter

Eugenio Marin has a degree in Environmental Sciences, a Master's in Research and Advances in Microbiology and PhD in Water Technologies from the University of Granada. In 2019 he began his research activity in the Innovation and Technology Department of Aqualia, where he actively participates as technical manager of the H2020 BBI DEEP PURPLE project. In addition, he is running the H2020 BBI B-FERST project, where he investigates the production of struvite from WWTP rejects. He also coordinates the CDTI ECLOSION project activities at the Guadalete WWTP (Jerez de la Frontera), where green hydrogen is obtained from reclaimed water.

Patricia Zamora

What is your current position?

Senior Project manager

Short biography of the presenter

Patricia is a Senior R&D Project Manager and Researcher at Aqualia, currently leading several European projects dealing with resource recovery and energy production from wastewater. Her education is a Bachelor in Chemical Engineering (2005), PhD in Analytical Chemistry (2012) and Master's Degree in Occupational Risk Prevention (3 specialities), Environmental and Quality Management (2006).

Short abstract

Circular cities are characterized by their prioritization of sustainability and resource efficiency. These cities aim to minimize urban biowaste and maximize the reuse of materials and energy. By adopting practices such as local production, recycling, and renewable energy, circular cities strive to create a more sustainable future. UNITEC CIRCLES project exemplifies this approach by focusing on wastewater reuse, sludge valorization, and resource recovery into valuable bioproducts. Through the development and implementation of advanced technologies for urban biowaste, this project contributes to the creation of more sustainable and resilient cities' environments.

#1.37

Towards simultaneous energy and nutrient recovery by anaerobic treatment of domestic wastewater: process performance and micropollutant impact

Domenica Mosca Angelucci¹, Nicolas Pennazza¹, Enrica Donati², M. Concetta Tomei¹

¹Water Research Institute - National Research Council, Rome, Italy. ²Institute for Biological Systems - National Research Council, Rome, Italy

Domenica Mosca Angelucci

What is your current position?

Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Domenica MOSCA ANGELUCCI, PhD in Chemical and Process Engineering, researcher at Water Research Institute of Italian National research Council. Her research interests cover wastewater treatment and bioremediation. Main topics investigated and under investigation include the application of advanced technologies for biological removal of xenobiotics from municipal and industrial wastewater and polluted soils and sequential anaerobic-aerobic digestion applied to sewage sludge stabilization. Recently, she oriented her research activity to the study of uptake/release processes of organic contaminants by microplastics. She authored more than 50 publications including papers on peer reviewed scientific journals, book chapters and conference proceedings.

Short abstract

Anaerobic process is a promising solution, given its potentialities of recovering energy and nutrients, thus promoting water reuse. Nevertheless, recovery from domestic wastewater is challenging due their low concentrations resulting in reduced process kinetics. This drawback can be faced by high-rate anaerobic bioreactors, able to achieve high biomass concentration and increase process performance. We investigated the feasibility of a granular biomass UASB to treat domestic wastewater at different temperatures and HRTs to enhance energy and resource recovery. Relevant for water reuse, the fate of a contaminant of emerging concern, sulphamethoxazole, and its potential impact on process performance have been evaluated.

#1.38

Resource Oriented Sludge Management through Anaerobic Co-Digestion with Food Waste

Benton Otieno¹, Mervyn Khune², Peter Osifo², Kgomotso Funani Maki²

¹WASH R&D Centre, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban, South Africa. ²Vaal University of Technology, Vanderbijlpark, South Africa

Benton Otieno

What is your current position?

Postdoctoral Student

Short biography of the presenter

Dr Benton Otieno is a Researcher affiliated with the WASH Research and Development Centre at the University of KwaZulu Natal (UKZN). He has close to ten years of experience spanning extensive research on water and wastewater management, renewable energy, green economy, and climate change mitigation. He previously worked at Lake Victoria South Water Works Development in Kenya, gaining vast experience in water quality surveillance, monitoring and evaluation of water service providers, and community mobilization and development. Through his research work, Dr Otieno plans to advance progress on the adaptation to climate change and achieve 'net-zero' energy processes for wastewater treatment.

Short abstract

The anaerobic digestion of sewage sludge (SS) is increasingly becoming economically feasible, particularly in the South African context. The economic viability can be enhanced through the codigestion of SS with nutrient-rich substrates such as food waste (FW), thus making wastewater treatment plants net energy producers. In the current study, pilot scale anaerobic co-digestion (AcD) of SS with FW was carried out followed by a techno-economic assessment for full-scale implementation. The study showed that through the codigestion approach, WWTPs can become net energy producers with significant savings. Other sources of income exist such as the sale of compost, struvite, and biogas.

#1.39

The innovative YDRO PROCESS® biotechnology

Roman Zuravliov

Bio-Ran Ltd, London, United Kingdom

Roman Zuravliov

What is your current position?

Technical Managing Director

Short biography of the presenter

Co-founder and Technical Director of Bio-ran Ltd, I have extensive experience in implementing the Ydro process for both domestic and industrial wastewater treatment.

Short abstract

The innovative *YDRO Process*® technology has the potential to dramatically improve the ecological landscape in environmental protection. It offers a substantial reduction (80-90%) in sludge formation within 4-6 weeks through its underlying bioaugmentation method. This technology comprehensively considers the impact on **nutrient removal** and the hydrolysis of slowly biodegradable organic substances, while also detailing the technological specifications for treatment facilities.

#1.40

Beyond macronutrients: Cycling micronutrients from blackwater to agriculture

Melissa Mativo¹, Miriam van Eekert², Lucia Hernandez³, Cees Buisman³

¹Wetsus - WUR, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ²WUR, Wageningen, Netherlands. ³Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands

Melissa Mativo

What is your current position?

PhD researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Melissa Mativo is a PhD researcher specializing in resource recovery from wastewater. She is currently affiliated with Wetsus and WUR in the environmental technology department. Her research explores recovery of energy and fertilizers through thermophilic anaerobic digestion of blackwater.

Short abstract

Effort must be made to alleviate micronutrient deficiencies in soils and crops without artificial fertilizers. Source-separated blackwater contains trace metals which can be trapped in reactors during thermophilic anaerobic digestion, producing blackwater sludge rich in micronutrients. During the operation of a 55°C anaerobic reactor seeded with blackwater sludge, more than 35% of the iron, zinc, manganese and molybdenum in the blackwater were retained in the reactor. The concentration of zinc and copper in the inoculum and resulting sludge comply with EU legislation despite continuous exposure to blackwater and are considered safe to use as organic amendment with regards micronutrients.

#1.41

Integrating Bioengineering and Chemical Approaches for Enhanced Phosphorus Recovery from Eutrophic Marine Sediments

Fengyi Zhu¹, Frederico Marques Penha², Zeynep Cetecioglu¹

¹Department of Industrial Biotechnology, School of Engineering Sciences in Chemistry, Biotechnology and Health, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm, Sweden. ²Division of Resource Recovery, Department of Chemical Engineering, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm, Sweden

Fengyi Zhu

What is your current position?

PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

PhD candidate in the Department of Industrial Biotechnology at KTH Royal Institute of Technology (Sweden). My PhD project focuses on the development of bioengineering approaches for phosphorus recovery from eutrophic Baltic Sea marine sediments.

Short abstract

Recovering phosphorus (P) from sediments through combined biological and chemical approaches presents a promising strategy for mitigating eutrophication and recycling valuable resources. By sequentially inoculating sediment enriched with polyphosphate-accumulating organisms and subsequently enhancing P release through EDTA addition under anaerobic conditions, the final P release rate from the sediment reached >65% and the collected supernatant contained a P concentration of around 150 mg/L. Simulation work for P precipitation will be conducted to optimize recovery conditions, and precipitation-related results will be presented at the conference.

#1.42

Recovering phosphorus from phosphogypsum leachates: An effective approach to resource valorisation.

Małgorzata Szlachta, Caiyong Nong, Xinmiao Yang
Tampere University, Tampere, Finland

Małgorzata Szlachta

What is your current position?

Associate Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Małgorzata Szlachta, Associate Professor in Environmental Engineering at Tampere University, leads the Water Resource Recovery research group. Her research focuses on developing advanced technologies for pollutant removal from municipal and industrial streams while recovering valuable resources. She specialises in adsorption, ion exchange, and electro-assisted processes. Her work aims to valorise recovered materials into marketable products and produce high-quality reclaimed water for various applications. With experience in experimental research, process design, and pilot-scale projects, she has led several national and international research projects, contributing to sustainable water management and resource valorisation.

Short abstract

Many valuable materials, including phosphorus, are lost in industrial by-products. Phosphogypsum (PG), a waste from phosphate rock processing for phosphoric acid and phosphate fertiliser production, can leach phosphorus-rich water into the environment, causing contamination. This study investigates highly efficient phosphorus treatment and recovery from leachates from PG stacks using a hybrid system combining electrochemical and selective adsorption methods. The system employs 3D-printed electrodes and novel bio-based adsorptive materials from renewable sources. The environmental benefits of phosphorus capture are assessed through life cycle analysis, demonstrating the potential for sustainable resource recovery and pollution mitigation.

#1.43

Influence of sewage sludge composition on P recovery from sewage sludge

Linda Müller, Heidrun Steinmetz
RPTU University Kaiserslautern Landau, Kaiserslautern, Germany

Linda Müller

What is your current position?

Research Assistant

Short biography of the presenter

I am Linda Müller and I studied Biophysics in the Department of Physics at the University of Kaiserslautern-Landau. From May 2022 to June 2024, I worked as a research assistant in the "Resource-efficient Wastewater Treatment" (REWA) working group and the organization tectraa e.V. During this period, I focused on the elimination of micropollutants and the establishment of sector coupling between electrolyzers and wastewater treatment plants.

Since July 2024, I have been continuing my work in the REWA working group at the university, with a new focus on phosphorus recovery from sewage sludge.

Short abstract

Many methods exist for recovering phosphorus from sewage sludge and process water. However, large-scale implementation in wastewater treatment plants with chemical phosphorus removal remains limited due to process complexity. This study examines fluctuations in sludge composition in Germany and their impact on phosphorus recovery. The phosphorus compounds are influenced by the precipitants used, with iron(III) chloride-containing precipitants being the most widely used for chemical phosphorus elimination in Germany (> 50 %) as of 01.01.2023. Additionally, other wastewater metals, such as calcium, can interact with phosphorus, affecting recovery efficiency. Understanding these interactions is crucial for optimizing phosphorus recycling from sewage sludge.

#1.44

DALIA project | Danube Region Water Lighthouse Action

Milán Töltősi

Hungarian Innovation Agency, Budapest, Hungary

Milán Töltősi

What is your current position?

International Expert

Short biography of the presenter

Working on EU projects, mostly developing the Hungarian Innovation Ecosystem, focusing on startups and innovative companies and sustainability (like ESG).

Short abstract

The DALIA project pioneers nature-based and systemic solutions to restore and protect the Danube River Basin. Through multi-stakeholder collaboration, it addresses water quality, biodiversity loss, and ecosystem connectivity. This poster showcases a selection of pilot actions focused on nutrient recovery, plastic removal, and habitat revitalization, with an emphasis on scaling solutions across regions. DALIA demonstrates how transnational cooperation can accelerate resource recovery and resilience.

#1.45

BEAMING: Bioeconomy Innovation

Zoltán Palotai

Hungarian Innovation Agency, Budapest, Hungary

Zoltán Palotai

What is your current position?

NA

Short biography of the presenter

NA

Short abstract

BEAMING supports research excellence in the circular bioeconomy across Widening countries. The project strengthens institutional capacity through collaborative Communities of Practice, open science, and stakeholder engagement. This poster presents the project's approach and early results, including research capacity mapping, clustering workshops, and institutional reforms. It highlights BEAMING's contribution to innovation transfer and inclusive green transition.

#1.47

Comparative analysis of incinerated sludge and vivianite for sustainable phosphorus recovery using Mössbauer spectroscopy.

Paul Hausbrandt, Hannah Akthar, Linda Müller, Janek Jost, Volker Schünemann, Heidrun Steinmetz
RPTU Kaiserslautern-Landau, Kaiserslautern, Germany

Paul Hausbrandt

What is your current position?

research scholar

Short biography of the presenter

I am currently a Master student in Biophysics at the RPTU Kaiserslautern-Landau. With an academic background in biophysics, I have focused on the important field of phosphorus recovery, a topic that has interested me since my Bachelor's studies. I have dedicated myself to research to understand and advance methods for sustainable phosphorus recovery, a key component in addressing environmental and resource issues. In the context of environmental issues, I have experience with physical principles such as Mössbauer spectroscopy and molecular spectroscopy.

Short abstract

This study investigates iron phosphate complexes, particularly vivianite, a paramagnetic iron phosphate. Ferric phosphates, formed via iron salt precipitation, are reduced in digested sludge to vivianite-like structures. Precipitation of iron-phosphates was studied in lab conditions and sewage sludge using Mössbauer spectroscopy across wastewater treatment stages. Samples of incinerated sludge from a wastewater plant in Germany with 400,000 inhabitants and incinerated vivianite were analysed for structural and chemical changes at different temperatures. These findings are in line with studies of Wilfert et al. (Water Research 104 (2016) 449), supporting phosphate removal from wastewater and incinerated sludge, contributing to sustainable phosphorus recovery.

#2.25

Towards a universal KPI framework for Circular Economy evaluation in wastewater treatment plants

Carlos Rodrigues^{1,2}, Tiago Martins^{1,3,4}, Leonor Amaral^{1,5}

¹NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University of Lisbon, Lisbon, Portugal. ²AQUAPOR, SAUR Group, Lisbon, Portugal. ³Nijhuis Saur Industries, Doetinchem, Netherlands. ⁴KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium. ⁵CENSE (Center for Environmental and Sustainability Research) & CHANGE (Global Change and Sustainability Institute), Lisbon, Portugal

Tiago Martins

What is your current position?

PhD Candidate / R&D Engineer

Short biography of the presenter

Tiago Martins earned his Bachelor's degree in Environmental Engineering in 2020 and a Master's in Sanitary Engineering with Magna Cum Laude honours in 2022, both from NOVA University of Lisbon. He then worked as a researcher on treated wastewater reuse at NOVA and was later invited to lecture at the University of Shanghai. In 2024, he began his PhD in Engineering Technology at KU Leuven through the Marie-Sklodowska Curie INCLUE project, supervised by Nadine Boelee, Raf Dewil, and Merle de Kreuk. Although experienced in wastewater treatment technologies, Tiago is currently concentrating his work on the removal of metals from sludges.

Short abstract

This work critically evaluates current circular economy frameworks for wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs), identifying significant gaps in standardized KPI methodologies. A systematic PRISMA review of 83 articles yielded 386 KPIs spanning technical, environmental, social, and economic dimensions, categorized according to its R policy – reduce, recovery, reuse and recycle. Therefore, this work allows a unified KPI-based framework proposal, to enhance transparency, comparability, and decision-making, ultimately facilitating the transition of WWTPs into efficient resource recovery facilities.

#2.26

Metal removal from wastewater sludge through electrochemical processes

Tiago Martins^{1,2}, Pradip Saha¹, Nadine Boelee¹, Merle de Kreuk³, Raf Dewil²

¹Nijhuis Saur Industries, Doetinchem, Netherlands. ²KU Leuven, Sint-Katelijne-Waver, Belgium. ³TU Delft, Delft, Netherlands

Tiago Martins

What is your current position?

PhD Candidate / R&D Engineer

Short biography of the presenter

Tiago Martins earned his Bachelor's degree in Environmental Engineering in 2020 and a Master's in Sanitary Engineering with Magna Cum Laude honours in 2022, both from NOVA University of Lisbon. He then worked as a researcher on treated wastewater reuse at NOVA and was later invited to lecture at the University of Shanghai. In 2024, he began his PhD in Engineering Technology at KU Leuven through the Marie-Sklodowska Curie INCLUE project, supervised by Nadine Boelee, Raf Dewil, and Merle de Kreuk. Although experienced in wastewater treatment technologies, Tiago is currently concentrating his work on the recovery of metals from sludges.

Short abstract

In Europe, approximately 10 million tons of wastewater sludge are produced annually. Northern European countries restrict its agricultural use due to concerns over metal toxicity. Electrochemical processes offer a potential solution by enabling sludge detoxification and opening a route for metal recovery. This study explores the electrowinning optimal conditions and reaction mechanisms, a crucial step toward industrial application. Through toxic metal removal, the metalwinning process enhances the potential for safe sludge use in agriculture. Simultaneously, through valuable metal recovery, it increases the circular economy within the urban water cycle.

#2.27

RECOVERY OF MICROALGAE FROM WATER BY ULTRA-FINE BUBBLE FLOTATION

Shen-Yi Chen, Zhe-Wei Xu

National Kaohsiung University of Science and Technology, Kaohsiung, Taiwan

Shen-Yi Chen

What is your current position?

Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Prof. Chen is a Professor of the Department of Safety, Health and Environmental Engineering at the National Kaohsiung University of Science and Technology (NKUST), Taiwan. Prior to joining the NKUST faculty, he was the visiting professor of the Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering at Iowa State University, USA. Prof. Chen received his M.S. in 1995 and Ph. D. in 1999 both in environmental engineering from the National Chiao Tung University, Taiwan. His current research interests are: biological wastewater treatment; sludge treatment, reuse and disposal and environmental nanotechnologies.

Short abstract

Microalgae, with high growth rates and CO₂ fixation, are a promising option for carbon capture and biofuel production. This study developed a cost-effective microalgae recovery method from water using ultrafine bubble flotation, where most bubbles (>90%) were stable nanobubbles (<100 nm). Chitosan (activator) and SDS (collector) were key factors; recovery efficiency increased with their concentrations but dropped beyond 27.5 mg/L. Using 27.5 mg/L of both chitosan and SDS achieved over 99% recovery efficiency, demonstrating this method's potential for biofuel production and carbon capture.

#2.28

IDENTIFYING AND ISOLATING EMERGING PROTEINS OF INTEREST AND STUDYING THEIR ROLE IN COMPOSITION AND BIOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF ACTIVATED SLUDGE

Amrita Bhattacharya, Allan Omar Ghamlouch
Aarhus University, Aarhus, Denmark

Amrita Bhattacharya

What is your current position?

Post Doc

Short biography of the presenter

Ph.D. in Protein structural biology,

My current research interest in protein isolation, extraction and valorization from sludge and other complex biomass

Short abstract

Resource recovery from wastewater has emerged as a critical strategy for sustainable water management and environmental conservation. Wastewater treatment processes generate sludge, a byproduct rich in organic matter, including proteins that can serve as a valuable resource for bioengineering, agricultural, and other sectors. The recovery of proteins from sludge offers a dual benefit: reducing the environmental impact of waste disposal while creating a sustainable source of bio-based materials. These proteins, primarily derived from microorganisms and from human waste, can be harnessed for use in animal feed, bioplastics etc. Identification of major components of the sludge proteome enables valorization.

#2.29

Electricity Generation from Vinasse Treatment via Microbial Fuel Cell with a biocathode for Autotrophic Denitrification

Verena Mandorino Kaminagakura^{1,2}, Marcelo Nolasco¹

¹University of São Paulo, São Paulo, Brazil. ²Universidade of Toulouse, Toulouse, France

Verena Mandorino Kaminagakura

What is your current position?

PhD Candidate

Short biography of the presenter

Environmental manager, master in Chemistry, science and technology of sustainability, PhD student in Sustainability at USP with a sandwich doctorate from the University of Toulouse - France, in the area of research in bioelectrochemical systems, for energy recovery from wastewater. Professor in theoretical technical disciplines. Instructor of training and cognitive, social and ethical development, in person and distance learning. Experience in environmental projects focusing on decontamination, effluent treatment and process performance. Work in administrative, commercial and environmental business procedures, in addition to training and evaluations; Laboratory experience and analytical experience with electronic and spatial characterization techniques for solids and liquids.

Short abstract

This study explores a dual-chamber microbial fuel cell (MFC) for vinasse treatment, focusing on energy generation, organic matter removal, and autotrophic denitrification at the cathode. The MFCs, equipped with low-cost granular activated carbon electrodes, were operated for 15 months with continuous feed. Two configurations were tested: a control MFC with an aerated cathode and phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) as the feed, and a denitrifying MFC using nitrate as the electron acceptor. The study aims to evaluate the potential of MFC technology for wastewater treatment and clean energy generation while addressing challenges related to cost and performance.

#2.30

Influence of thermal pre-treatment and supplementation with magnetite nanoparticles on biomethane potential of municipal sewage sludge

Matteo Tucci¹, Marco Resitano¹, Agata Gallipoli¹, Andrea Gianico¹, Camilla Braguglia¹, Andrea Capodaglio², Federico Aulenta¹, Carolina Cruz Viggli¹

¹Water Research Institute (IRSA - CNR), Rome, Italy. ²DICAR University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy

Matteo Tucci

What is your current position?

PostDoc

Short biography of the presenter

Holding a PhD in Agriculture, Environment and Bioenergy (2020, University of Milan, IT), Matteo Tucci is currently a Postdoctoral Research Fellow at the Water Research Institute (IRSA-CNR, Italy) conducting research on microbial electrochemical technologies (MET), with the aim of developing novel applications for bioremediation, biosensing, and bioenergy production. Other research interests involve waste valorization, nutrient recovery and water quality assessment. Committed to address critical environmental challenges and contribute to sustainable solutions.

Short abstract

Anaerobic digestion (AD) of municipal sewage sludge is hindered by its complex composition, including recalcitrant materials like lignin and cellulose, which slow digestion and reduce biogas yields. Pre-treatment methods, (i.e., thermal, chemical, mechanical, or biological), improve AD efficiency by breaking down these materials into bioavailable forms, accelerating digestion and boosting biogas production. Supplementing AD with electrically-conductive nanoparticles, like magnetite, further enhances methanogenic activity via direct interspecies electron transfer (DIET). A study combining thermal pre-treatment (134°C, 20 min, 3.2 bar) and magnetite supplementation demonstrated significantly improved biomethane potential (BMP) for treated sludge, though nanoparticles had negligible effects on untreated sludge.

#2.31

Lactate-based chain elongation in mixed culture bioreactors without amino acid supplementation

Ángel Estévez^{1,2}, Alberte Regueira³, Ramon Ganigué^{1,2}

¹Center for Microbial Ecology and Technology, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium. ²Center for Advanced Process Technology for Urban Resource Recovery (CAPTURE), Ghent, Belgium. ³CRETUS, Department of Chemical Engineering, Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, Santiago de Compostela, Spain

Ángel Estévez

What is your current position?

Postdoctoral Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Ángel Estévez is a post-doctoral researcher at the Center for Microbial Ecology and Technology at Ghent University. He obtained his PhD title in Environmental Biotechnology at Delft University of Technology in December 2022. His PhD project, a collaboration between TU Delft and Wetsus, was focused on the use of municipal waste activated sludge for biopolymers production. At CMET, he aims to understand fermentative microbial communities and their metabolic interactions to develop bioprocesses for a sustainable circular economy. In general, Ángel is fascinated by how microorganisms adapt to different environmental conditions and interact with each other.

Short abstract

This study explores how nutrient availability shapes the enrichment of lactic acid bacteria and chain elongators in anaerobic processes, facilitating medium-chain carboxylate production from nitrogen-poor wastewaters without additional costs. Using three bioreactor setups with varying nutrient compositions, we demonstrate that vitamins alone can enrich these key microorganisms, removing the need for organic nitrogen sources. These findings provide valuable insights into the microbial ecology of lactic acid bacteria and chain elongators while contributing to more sustainable and cost-effective wastewater treatment solutions.

#2.32

Development of a bioenergetic model for gas fermentation: understanding autotroph metabolisms in microbial consortia for better process management

Léa Laguillaumie¹, Alberte Regueira², Miguel Mauricio²

¹TBI - INRAE, Toulouse, France. ²USC, Santiago de Compostela, Spain

Léa Laguillaumie

What is your current position?

Researcher INRAE

Short biography of the presenter

Recently recruited within the INRAE TRANSFORM department as a research fellow, I am specialized in bioprocess engineering and microbial ecology of anaerobic consortia. I use experimental and modeling approaches to understand these systems, integrating kinetic, thermodynamic and metabolic analyses.

Short abstract

CO₂ reuse is of great importance for carbon resource recovery, and gas fermentation is getting attention in the field. A bioenergetic model is developed to guide gas fermentation process management using anaerobic microbial consortia. The model assumes pathways maximizing ATP production, particularly under substrate limitations encountered in CSTR. First simulations showed 100% ethanol production while experiments yielded only acetate, even at low pH. When acetate was produced, strong energetic limitations were predicted at low pH. This highlights sophisticated enzymatic mechanisms of acetogens, needed to be addressed in the model to increase its accuracy in terms of predicting microbial activity.

#2.33

Pilot-scale investigation of carbon recovery via High Rate Activated Sludge process implementation in existing WWTPs

Raja Guthi¹, Pierre Buffiere², Sylvie Gillot³, Florent Chazarenc³, Stephanie PIEL¹, [Tuur van den Eijnde](#)⁴

¹Saur, Maurepas, France. ²INSA Laboratoire DEEP EA7429, Villeurbanne, France. ³INRAE, Villeurbanne, France.

⁴Nijhuis Saur Industries, Doetinchem, Netherlands

Raja Guthi

What is your current position?

R&D Engineer

Short biography of the presenter

Environmental process engineer, passionate about wastewater treatment. 6 years of experience in biological processes for municipal sector.

Tuur van den Eijnde

What is your current position?

Team Leader R&D Technology Development

Short biography of the presenter

To be added.

Short abstract

As energy self-sufficiency of wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is of growing importance, recovering influent organic matter (COD) for energy valorisation is vital. High Rate Activated Sludge (HRAS) process is a promising alternative to primary settling tanks, that has the potential to improve overall recovery of influent COD.

A pilot-scale HRAS process (reactor volume 0.5 m³) fed with raw wastewater was monitored for a period of >1 year. Up to 27% of the influent COD was captured in the sludge fraction, with mineralization maintained below 20%. Enhancing flocculation can improve recovery potential. The process was sensitive to diurnal load variations.

#2.34

Enhancing PHA accumulation through microaerophilic famine

Serena Falcioni^{1,2}, Alessio Castagnoli³, Elia Biagini¹, Leandro Di Gloria¹, Matteo Ramazzotti¹, Maria Eugenia Suárez-Ojeda², David Gabriel², Giulio Munz¹

¹University of Florence, Florence, Italy. ²Autonomous university of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain. ³University of Pisa, Pisa, Italy

Serena Falcioni

What is your current position?

phd candidate

Short biography of the presenter

phd candidate in the international phd program in Civil and environmental engineering in University of Florence in cotutela with Autonomous university of Barcelona. The topic of the phd thesis is the PHA production through mixed microbial community cultivated in feast-famine regime and uncoupled feeding. The work was framed in the european project "Recycles". Previously she worked with nitrification, high salinity and in autotroph denitrification with sulphide.

Short abstract

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are promising polymers, offering environmental benefits compared to fossil-based plastics. Mixed microbial cultures (MMCs) enable wastewater-based PHA production, reducing costs and promoting a circular economy. Aeration is a major operational expense, while the effects of oxygen concentration on PHA production were not studied in depth. This study explores microaerophilic famine conditions to enhance PHA production by disadvantaging conventional heterotrophs and predators while reducing energy use. Two 10 L sequencing batch reactors (SBRs) working under feast and famine regime were tested, showing microaerophilic conditions boosted PHA content but reduced polymer quality in terms of the hydroxyvalerate content.

#2.35

Enhanced Biomethanation of Biogas in Biotrickling Filters Utilizing Anaerobic Digestate as a Nutrient Source

Israel Diaz^{1,2}, Maria Soto^{1,3}, Federico Ferrari⁴, Maria Luisa Ruiz⁵, Raquel Iglesias⁵, Maria del Mar Mico⁴, Jorge Juan Malfeito⁶

¹Department of Chemical Engineering and Environmental Technology, School of Industrial Engineering, University of Valladolid, Dr. Mergelina, s/n, 47011 Valladolid, Spain. ²Institute of Sustainable Processes, Dr. Mergelina s/n, 47011 Valladolid, Spain. ³Institute of Sustainable Processes, Dr. Mergelina s/n, 47011 Valladolid, Spain. ⁴Innovation department of Acciona Agua S.A.U, Parc de Negocis Mas Blau II, Avda. de les Garrigues, 22, 08820 El Prat de Llobregat, Barcelona, Spain. ⁵Advanced Biofuels and Bioproducts Unit, Department of Energy, Research Centre for Energy, Environment and Technology (CIEMAT), Avda. Complutense 40, 28040 Madrid, Spain. ⁶department of Acciona Agua S.A.U, Parc de Negocis Mas Blau II, Avda. de les Garrigues, 22, 08820 El Prat de Llobregat, Barcelona, Spain

Israel Diaz

What is your current position?

Associate Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Israel Diaz is a university professor at Universidad de Valladolid (Spain) specializing in environmental technologies. His research focuses on biomass treatment and valorization, with an emphasis on biogas and biomethane. His academic work contributes to the development of sustainable solutions for the recovery of bioproducts and energy from organic waste/wastewater.

Maria Soto

What is your current position?

Associate Professor

Federico Ferrari

What is your current position?

R&D&I Project Manager at ACCIONA

Short biography of the presenter

Project Manager in ACCIONA's Innovation Department, leading strategic projects in sustainability and wastewater treatment efficiency.

Short abstract

The feasibility of the utilization of anaerobic digestates (rich in N, P and trace elements) as a nutrient source for the biomethanation of H₂ from renewable power and CO₂ from biogas was evaluated in a lab-scale biotrickling filter (BTF). The maximum loading rate with stationary conversion larger than 90% was 12.48 NLH₂ L_r⁻¹ d⁻¹ and 3.07 NLCO₂ L_r⁻¹ d⁻¹. The specific N consumption observed was 0.73 gN per Nm³ of supplied CO₂. The use of anaerobic centrates eliminates the need for synthetic solutions, providing a sustainable alternative for CO₂ biomethanation.

#2.36

Struvite seed production in a fed-batch reactor to standardise agricultural fertiliser characteristics: An experimental approach

Leynard Natividad-Marin^{1,2}, Lena Cruz-Villacorta³, Rosa Maria Miglio Toledo³, Phillip A. Schneider⁴

¹Doctoral Programme in Environmental Engineering and Science, Universidad Nacional Agraria La Molina, Lima, Peru.

²College of Science and Engineering, James Cook University, Townsville, Australia. ³Departamento de Ordenamiento Territorial y Construcción. Facultad de Ingeniería Agrícola, Universidad Nacional Agraria La Molina, Lima, Peru. ⁴School of Engineering, University of Western Australia, Perth, Australia

Leynard Natividad-Marin

What is your current position?

University lecturer

Short biography of the presenter

Australian-Peruvian researcher with a deep interest in process system engineering.

I'm Chemical Engineer, Master in Food Science and Technology from the National University of Callao (Peru) and I obtained the Doctor of Philosophy (PhD.) in Chemical Engineering at James Cook University JCU (Australia).

I studied nutrient recovery systems through mathematical modelling. My research field topics are nutrient recovery, process system engineering, thermodynamics, reactor design, and kinetics.

I currently hold an adjunct position as researcher at JCU and I'm provisionally lecturing at the Agrarian National University (Peru).

My goal is becoming a very good scientist and participate in research projects worldwide.

Short abstract

Struvite seed crystals were produced in a 5-L mixed fed batch reactor by adding magnesium and basic solutions and awaiting between additions to form crystals. pH and conductivity successfully monitored the reactor liquid when solid formed. Depletion of phosphorus and increment of solid mass were quantified through concentration of P and Mg, dried filtered struvite mass, and visually inspected turbidity. Struvite presence was confirmed through measurements of Mg, N and P molar ratios in the dissolved solid phase, and with x-ray diffraction. Scanning electron microscopy of the crystals showed this technique potential to achieve crystal size under agricultural commercial standards.

#2.37

Long-Term Methane Production in a Nutrient-Restricted Membrane-biofilm Reactor: A Low-energy and Nutrient Input Process for CO₂ Utilization

Shih-Hsuan Lin^{1,2}, Philipp Kuntke^{1,2}, Sanne de Smit¹, Bert Hamelers^{1,2}, Maria Cristina Gagliano²

¹Wageningen U&R, Wageningen, Netherlands. ²Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands

Shih-Hsuan Lin

What is your current position?

PhD candidate

Short biography of the presenter

The author is a PhD candidate at Wageningen University and Wetsus. Working in the Sustainable Carbon Cycle theme at Wetsus, he focuses on developing the membrane-biofilm reactor technology for the biological conversion of captured CO₂ into chemicals and fuels.

Short abstract

Hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis is a bio-based solution to convert captured CO₂ into methane, aligning with the Carbon Capture and Utilization (CCU) strategy. This study proposes a membrane-biofilm reactor (MBfR) designed to optimize the utilization of CO₂ and H₂ by a methanogenic biofilm, improving H₂ transfer and methane production with minimal mixing. The reactor ran for 395 days in nutrient-limited conditions, reaching methane production rates of 21.2 L/m²/day at ≈95% methane content and >95% conversion efficiency. The measurement of trace element concentrations reveals that nutrient recycling by the microbial consortium stabilizes nutrient levels by counteracting microbial uptake and water dilution.

#2.38

Extraction of Extracellular Polymeric Substances from Aerobic Granular Sludge in a Full-Scale Tropical Wastewater Treatment Plant

Samara Geraldo¹, Yuemei Lin², Mario Pronk², Luana Cruz¹

¹UNICAMP, Campinas, Brazil. ²TU Delft, Delft, Netherlands

Samara Geraldo

What is your current position?

Phd Student

Short biography of the presenter

I completed my MSc in Civil Engineering at the State University of Campinas (Brazil) and am currently pursuing a PhD in the Wastewater Treatment and Resource Recovery Group at the same institution. Our research focuses on extracting and analyzing biopolymers from aerobic granular sludge collected at a full-scale wastewater treatment plant.

Luana Cruz

What is your current position?

Professor

Short biography of the presenter

She has a Bachelor's degree in Environmental Sanitation Technology from the State University of Campinas (2006) and a degree in Environmental Engineering from the University of São Francisco (USF). She earned her Master's and Doctoral degrees from the School of Civil Engineering, Architecture, and Urbanism (FECFAU) – UNICAMP in Sanitation and Environment. She conducted postdoctoral research at IHE Delft, Netherlands, focusing on the anammox process. Since 2021, she has been an Associate Professor in Sewage and Wastewater Treatment Systems at FECFAU – UNICAMP. Her expertise includes centralized and decentralized wastewater treatment, emphasizing biological nutrient removal, resource recovery, and solutions for rural areas.

Short abstract

Redefining wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) enhances sustainability by enabling resource recovery. This study evaluated extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) extracted from aerobic granular sludge (AGS) in a full-scale tropical WWTP using the base-acid method. EPS yield was 557.8 ± 76.2 mg EPS/g VS, higher than reported values. Protein (PN) and polysaccharide (PS) contents were 73.9 ± 31.7 mg BSA/g VS EPS and 45.9 ± 16.5 mg glucose/g VS EPS, respectively. High EPS recovery suggests its potential as a valuable biopolymer. These findings highlight the feasibility of EPS extraction for sustainable wastewater treatment applications.

#2.39

Post-treatment of sewage sludge digestate using hydrothermal processes: impact on biomethane production and dewaterability

Lu Feng¹, Dhruv Tapasv²

¹Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research, Aas, Norway. ²Lindum AS, Drammen, Norway

Lu Feng

What is your current position?

Research Scientist

Short biography of the presenter

Lu is a research scientist from NIBIO and works primarily aim to strengthen anaerobic digestion based circular economy, the role of anaerobic digestion process on organic farming, its effect on recycling and relocating the nutrients, and impact on soil fertility and GHG emission. Currently, I have interests on developing innovative biotechnologies for converting organic residues, to bioenergy, organic acids, protein, biomethanation and syngas fermentation.

Short abstract

This study evaluated post-anaerobic digestion (AD) hydrothermal treatments—Thermal Hydrolysis Process (THP) and Hydrothermal Carbonization (HTC)—on sewage sludge digestate. Sewage sludge based digestate was treated with either THP (140°C, 30 min) or HTC (200°C, 4 h). Biochemical methane potential (BMP) assays showed THP increased biomethane yield by 58% (115 mL CH₄·gVS⁻¹), linked to elevated soluble COD. HTC improved dewaterability, achieving >50% total solids (TS) in press-dewatered cake compared to 41% for untreated digestate. These results highlight the potential of post-AD hydrothermal processes to enhance biogas production and digestate management efficiency.

#2.40

Investigation of a cost-effective process train for sericin recovery from silk degumming wastewater

Goksen Capar, Tolga Pilevneli
Ankara University, Ankara, Turkey

Goksen Capar

What is your current position?

Director

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Capar is a full time professor in water management, focusing on resource recovery and pollution control. She is the Director of Water Management Institute of Ankara University, Turkey. Dr. Capar is the member of IWA Resource Recovery Cluster and IWA SG on Industrial Waters. She has co-authored more than 20 international publications, attended several international conferences and assumed voluntary roles for awareness raising in water management and climate change.

Short abstract

A cost-effective process was developed for the recovery of sericin from silk degumming effluents via evaluation of capital and operational costs based on pilot and lab-scale tests. Eight alternatives from A1 to A8, covering combinations of pre-treatment (flocculation/sedimentation), volume reduction (nanofiltration-NF), solidification (ethanol precipitation + centrifugation) and drying (lyophilization, spray drying or oven drying) were considered to find the optimum recovery cost that would be competitive with the commercial price of sericin. Total costs were between €140,000 and €2,600,000 for a plant lifetime of 15 years. The unit cost of recovered sericin varied significantly from €89 to €1300 per kg.

#2.41

In-situ carbon capture in anaerobic digestion via the application of gas diversion

Liwen LUO

Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium

Liwen LUO

What is your current position?

Postdoctoral researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Liwen Luo is working as a postdoctoral researcher in the Department of Biotechnology at Ghent University, focusing on the biotechnological conversion of carbon waste to renewable fuels, chemicals, and materials for the development of circular economy and sustainability. She has published over 50 peer-reviewed academic articles and book chapters and served as an editorial role for several peer-review journals.

Short abstract

Treating organic-rich waste via anaerobic digestion often leads to lactate accumulation under high loading conditions, which impedes methane production and overall carbon recovery. We overcome this challenge by harnessing the redox potential required for lactate oxidation to supplement system demands, thereby regulating intrinsic hydrogen production. This strategy redirects the metabolic pathway to enhance hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis and achieve in-situ carbon capture. By overcoming the thermodynamic constraints associated with lactate oxidation, our approach not only mitigates inhibitory effects but also improves overall carbon recovery efficiency, offering a scalable method to optimize waste-to-energy conversion.

#2.42

Understanding cationic-induced hydrogel formation of extracellular polymeric substances and their properties at the nanoscale through MP-SPR and QCM-D techniques.

Lisa Lopes da Costa¹, Abdo Bou Sarkis², Corinne Rondeau-Mouro³, Yolaine Bessiere⁴, Celine Moreau⁵, Ana Villares⁵
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Abdo Bou Sarkis

What is your current position?

Associate Professor in Biotechnology

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Abdo Bou Sarkis is an associate professor in biotechnology at UniLaSalle, France. His research is focused on environmental biotechnology, with a particular emphasis on the valorization of extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) derived from wastewater treatment processes. His work explores innovative strategies to recover and repurpose EPS as valuable biomaterials for applications in various domains such as hydrogels or bioadhesives. Dr. Bou Sarkis is passionate about transforming waste streams into resources through circular bioeconomy approaches, contributing to more sustainable and efficient wastewater management systems.

Short abstract

This work investigates the calcium-induced hydrogel formation and properties at the nanoscale of structural extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) extracted from aerobic granular sludge. Nanoscale characterization techniques (MP-SPR, QCM-D) were employed to assess how divalent cations influence hydrogel formation and properties. Our findings revealed that polysaccharides played a dominant role in hydrogel formation through ionic crosslinking, as well as in hydrogel softness and water retention, while proteins contributed to the modulation of structure and viscoelasticity. The nanoscale structural analysis conducted in this study lays a valuable foundation for further understanding the macroscopic properties of EPS hydrogels and their potential applications.

#2.43

Biopolymers in the Circular Economy: Redefining waste, creating value.

Ania Escudero¹, Francesca McKendrick², Richard Clarke²

¹Glasgow Caledonian University, GLASGOW, United Kingdom. ²United Utilities, Warrington, United Kingdom

Ania Escudero

What is your current position?

Research Fellow

Short biography of the presenter

A Research Fellow in the Department of Civil Engineering and Environmental Management at Glasgow Caledonian University, Ania is a leading expert on waste and wastewater treatment, with her research centred around nutrient recovery and waste valorisation. As Research Leader Fellow under the Hydro Nation Chair programme focused on embracing the circular economy, Ania is developing opportunities within the Scottish water sector aimed at minimising waste and promoting the sustainable use of resources derived from wastewater. Ania is building a research programme that embrace the circular economy and addresses the challenges and opportunities of the mission.

Short abstract

Wastewater-derived biopolymers provide the water industry and beyond with an unique opportunity to reduce reliance on fossil-based materials and move toward net-zero. By extracting and refining the biopolymers found within the wastewater, they can be used in the manufacture of fertilisers, polyacrylamides, coatings and packaging. The Biopolymers in the Circular Economy project, funded by Ofwat Innovation Fund and led by United Utilities, explores innovative sludge solutions through resource recovery. In collaboration with partners across the resource recovery supply chain, the project is helping the water access new markets. This paper shares the consortium's progress to date and outlines future ambitions.

#2.44

Impact of biochemical properties on the gelation of EPS extracted from aerobic granules.

Abdo Bou Sarkis^{1,2}, Etienne Paul², Yolaine Bessiere², Nicolas Derlon³

¹Université de Toulouse, UPS, LBAE, Laboratoire de Biotechnologies Agroalimentaire et Environnementale, URU 4565, Institut Universitaire de Technologie, Auch, France. ²Université de Toulouse; INSA, UPS, INP, TBI, Toulouse, France.

³EAWAG, Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology, Department of Process Engineering, Dübendorf, Switzerland

Abdo Bou Sarkis

What is your current position?

Associate Professor in Biotechnology

Short biography of the presenter

Abdo BOU SARKIS is an associate professor of biotechnology at UniLaSalle. His research focuses on the valorization of extracellular polymeric substances from aerobic granules for their use as hydrogels or bioadhesives.

Short abstract

Extracellular Polymeric Substances (EPS) from aerobic granular sludge are promising gel-forming biopolymers. These polymers, including polysaccharides, proteins, humic acids, and DNA, have diverse biochemical and molecular properties. Understanding their charge and molecular weight is crucial for the valorization of EPS as gel-forming polymers. Anionic chromatography fractionation helped reveal that gelation correlates with negative charge. However, a very high negative charge reduces gelation capacity. Size Exclusion Chromatography showed that high molecular weight molecules are the most involved in gelation. Infra-red spectroscopy and colorimetric methods indicated that proteins and polysaccharides (uronic acids) are the main contributors to hydrogel formation.

#2.45

Duckweed Ponds as a Direct Route to Convert Effluent Nutrients into Protein for Sustainable Plant-Based Nutrition

Luis Antonio Bueno, Gabriela Marjorie Ern, [Nelson Libardi](#), Renata Fialho Teixeira, Acacio Zielinski, Debora de Oliveira, Paulo Belli Filho, Rodrigo de Almeida Mohedano
Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianopolis, Brazil

Nelson Libardi

What is your current position?

Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Professor at the Sanitary and Environmental Engineering Department. Research field: Bioprocess engineering, Resource recovery, Biological processes for wastewater treatment.

Short abstract

Duckweed ponds can convert soluble nitrogen into crude protein (CP) efficiently. This study evaluated the potential of a pilot-scale duckweed pond for nutrient recovery from wetland effluent and biomass protein production. At an average applied surface load of $2.09 \text{ kgNH}_3(\text{ha.d})^{-1}$, the duckweed pond achieved a removal efficiency of 76% for ammonium nitrogen. The species *Landoltia punctata* produced biomass with 30% of CP on a dry weight, reaching a productivity about $3.65 \text{ tons}(\text{ha.year}^{-1})$ this represents a conversion of nitrogen into protein of 6.3 tons of crude protein per ton of ammonium nitrogen removed from the effluent.

#2.46

Application of extracellular polymeric substances as AGS enhancer

Nathan Pacheco Amin Vieira da Costa, [Nelson Libardi Junior](#), Rejane Helena Ribeiro da Costa
Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, Brazil

Nelson Libardi Junior

What is your current position?

Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. in Bioprocess Engineering. Professor in the Department of Sanitary and Environmental Engineering - Federal University of Santa Catarina. Bioprocess Engineering, Environmental Engineering. Treatment Processes. Resource Recovery

Short abstract

Extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) recovered from aerobic granular sludge (AGS) was tested as AGS enhancer to induce granule formation and stability in a pilot-scale AGS sequence batch reactor (SBR). Three application strategies were tested and, the use of EPS (250 mg/L) + calcium (100mg/L) previously mixed with seed sludge (3g/L) reduced the granulation time to 22 days with increased granule stability and settling velocity (7.2 m/h). Protein, polysaccharides and humic substances responded to the EPS addition, indicating that the external EPS and Ca stimulate microbial EPS secretion and, a shift of the microbial composition was observed after the additive.

#2.47

Development and Evaluation of the High-Rate Granular Sludge (HiGS) Technology for Enhancing Resource Recovery from Industrial Wastewater: Characterization and Applications of Extracted Extracellular Polymeric Substances (EPS)

Laura Andrea Acosta Figueredo, Siegfried Vlaeminck, Jan Dries
University of Antwerp, Antwerp, Belgium

Laura Andrea Acosta Figueredo

What is your current position?

PhD researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Andrea Acosta, Ph.D., is a researcher affiliated with the Biochemical Wastewater Valorization and Engineering (BioWAVE) and Biobased Sustainability Engineering (SUSTAIN) research groups at the University of Antwerp. She focusses on wastewater treatment and the development of innovative technologies for resource recovery.

She has a background in Environmental Technology and Engineering, specializing in Aerobic Granular Sludge, including Photo-Aerobic Granular Sludge (PAGS). Currently, she is exploring the resource recovery potential of the High-Rate Granular Sludge (HiGS) technology, with a particular emphasis on the extraction and industrial applications of extracellular polymeric substances (EPS).

Short abstract

Wastewater treatment faces significant challenges, such as high energy costs, excessive sludge production, and limited resource recovery. To overcome these issues, the proposed High-Rate Granular Sludge (HiGS) technology combines the advantages of High-Rate Activated Sludge (HRAS) and Aerobic Granular Sludge (AGS). HiGS aims to enhance the potential for resource recovery, producing valuable products like biogas, fertilizers, and biopolymers, beyond merely treating the wastewater.

The research aims to demonstrate the viability of HiGS using industrial wastewater and evaluate how operational conditions, wastewater complexity, and microbial communities impact its resource recovery potential.

#2.48

Evaluation of advanced water technologies and assessment of the effluent water quality reuse potential in public blue green solutions.

Moshe Habagil^{1,2}, Christian Baresel³, Margareta Björksund-Tuominen², Fredrik Torisson¹, Karin Jönsson¹

¹Lund University, Lund, Sweden. ²VIVAB, Varberg, Sweden. ³IVL, Stockholm, Sweden

Moshe Habagil

What is your current position?

R&D Engineering and PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

Dedicated the past 22 years of my life to the field of wastewater treatment. Currently, I wear two hats: I'm pursuing a PhD at Lund University in Sweden while also working as an R&D engineer at VIVAB, a municipal company focused on wastewater treatment, drinking water provision, and waste recycling. My passion for water was sparked during my childhood in Israel, where I experienced water scarcity. This early exposure deepened my understanding of the critical role that water plays as the foundation of all life on Earth.

Short abstract

The reuse potential of effluent water treated with advanced water technologies for public blue-green solutions offers several positive affordances. Consequently, the effluent from the combinations of UF:GAC and Ozone:GAC was assessed for its reuse potential in such public areas, according to Swedish and European directives. Results indicated that the treated water meets bathing water quality standards, irrigation class B requirements in areas with a high risk of aerosolization, good chemical surface status, and low concentrations of prioritized substances. Notably, higher microbial removal efficiency was observed with the UF:GAC combination due to its microbiological barrier.

#3.16

Advancing water reuse: Digital Twin, Soft Sensors & Renewable Energy Integration

Jaromír Sobotka, [Michaela Majčínová](#), Marek Holba
ASIO TECH Ltd., Brno, Czech Republic

Jaromír Sobotka

What is your current position?

R&D Project manager

Short biography of the presenter

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Michaela Majčínová

What is your current position?

NA

Short biography of the presenter

NA

Short abstract

Water scarcity is a global issue, however water recycling at WWTPs offers a solution. Current technologies are energy-intensive, where integrating renewable energy (solar power) and digital solutions (digital twins, soft sensors) can improve energy efficiency, optimize operations, and enhance water quality. A water reuse pilot plant in Brno, Czech Republic, demonstrates this approach by using solar power to operate various tertiary treatment technologies (UF, NF, RO, COAG-GAU-UV). Digital tools monitor various parameters, and chemical analyses assess pharmaceutical and PFAS removal. Preliminary results show promising energy savings and high removal rates for RO, with lower rates for other technologies.

#3.17

Contributions of Bioelectrochemical systems towards the circular economy principles in the wastewater treatment context

Vitor Cano¹, Mariana Cardoso Chrispim², Theo Syrto Octavio de Souza³, Eduardo Delloso Penteado⁴

¹Columbia University, New York, USA. ²University of Groningen, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ³University of Sao Paulo, Sao Paulo, Brazil. ⁴Federal University of São Paulo, Santos, Brazil

Mariana Cardoso Chrispim

What is your current position?

Assistant Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Researcher in Circular Economy, mainly about assessment methods, practices, perception of different stakeholders, and challenges to implementation. Lecturer in the Master Program in Sustainable Entrepreneurship. Large experience on water and wastewater sector, particularly water reuse and resource recovery processes.

Short abstract

BES are novel techniques that, using the respiration of electrochemically active bacteria (EAB), can directly convert organic and inorganic compounds within wastewater into electricity and hydrogen (H₂), store CO₂, synthesize value-added organic compounds. Despite the low technology readiness levels of BES, they are considered promising innovative technologies for circular economy integrating the principles introduced by Konietzko et al.(2020): narrow, regenerate, close, and slow. In this research, we assess the linkages between BES and each principle of CE, based on literature data.

#3.18

Two birds, one stone: capturing CO₂ while managing reverse osmosis brines

Evgeniy Matveev¹, Ivaylo Hitsov¹, Emile Cornelissen^{1,2}, Marjolein Vanoppen¹

¹Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium. ²KWR Water Research Institute, Nieuwegein, Netherlands

Evgeniy Matveev

What is your current position?

Doctoral fellow

Short biography of the presenter

Evgeniy Matveev holds a Master's degree in Sustainable and Innovative Natural Resource Management, with a specialization in resource recovery. The master's dissertation focused on upscaling novel membranes for efficient resource recovery, conducted at the Centre of Advanced Process Technology for Urban Resource Recovery (CAPTURE) at Ghent University. Practical experience includes an internship and part-time role at DuCoop's wastewater treatment plant in Ghent, Belgium. Currently, Evgeniy Matveev is pursuing a PhD at Ghent University, researching innovative solutions for simultaneously capturing CO₂ and managing reverse osmosis brines under the project titled "Two birds, one stone: capturing CO₂ while managing reverse osmosis brines".

Short abstract

Modern desalination technologies produce fresh water but also generate large volumes of untreated saline brine, causing environmental problems. Meanwhile, record-high CO₂ emissions worsen global warming. At Ghent University's PalnT research group, we're developing an innovative treatment process to help mitigate both challenges. The process involves dissolving CO₂ into the brine, where it reacts with calcium and magnesium. This reaction recovers valuable carbonates, which can be used as construction materials. If successful, the process could also enable further water recovery and the production of acid and base for internal use, providing a solid foundation for industrial application.

#3.19

Circular chemical use: producing acid and base with (bipolar) electro dialysis from IEX regenerate

Nienke Koeman, Timon Rijnaarts, Bas Pol, Danny Harmsen
KWR, Nieuwegein, Netherlands

Nienke Koeman

What is your current position?

Senior researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Nienke Koeman is a researcher in the team Water treatment. She is mainly active in the field of industrial water treatment and water treatment in agriculture and horticulture. Nienke has a background in bioprocess technology but has built up a lot of experience with physical-chemical water treatment in recent years. She has extensive experience with industrial water flows such as process water, cooling water and industrial wastewater treatment. She also has a great deal of knowledge about water flows and water treatment in greenhouse horticulture. She is engaged in research and innovations in water reuse, recycling and resource recovery.

Short abstract

This study explores a circular method for producing acids and bases through electro dialysis with bipolar membranes (EDBM), using ion exchange (IEX) regenerate streams. By recycling salts from IEX regeneration, the process minimizes waste, enhances energy efficiency, and reduces the need for concentrated chemical storage and logistics. The research compares different membrane performances, with Weifang membranes achieving 77% efficiency and Mega membranes 65%. Additionally, the impact of other ions on EDBM performance from both synthetic and chemical plant streams was evaluated. This innovative approach highlights EDBM's potential to enhance sustainability in the chemical industry by integrating resource recovery and chemical synthesis.

#3.20

An innovative biotechnology for sustainable treatment of saline wastewater aimed to toxic removal and brine recovery

Maria Concetta Tomei, [Domenica Mosca Angelucci](#)
CNR Water Research Institute, Roma, Italy

Maria Concetta Tomei

What is your current position?

Research Director Associate

Short biography of the presenter

Chemical Engineer, Maria Concetta Tomei is Research Director at the CNR Water Research Institute. In the period 2002-2008, she hold the course "Biological Processes in the Industry" at the Rome University "La Sapienza". The main field of her research activity is "wastewater treatment" involving both theoretical and practical aspects. She actively worked on modelling of biological processes for the design and management of Wastewater Treatment Plants. At present, the research activity is focused on anaerobic treatment of urban wastewater finalized to water and resource recovery and on innovative technologies for the biological removal of xenobiotics from water and soil.

Domenica Mosca Angelucci

What is your current position?

Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

PhD in Chemical and Process Engineering, researcher at IRSA-CNR. Her research interests cover wastewater treatment and bioremediation. Main topics investigated and under investigation include the application of advanced technologies for biological removal of xenobiotics from municipal and industrial wastewater and polluted soils, and sequential anaerobic-aerobic digestion applied to sewage sludge stabilization. Recently, she oriented her research activity to the study of uptake/release processes of organic contaminants by microplastics. She authored more than 50 publications including papers on peer reviewed scientific journals, book chapters and conference proceedings.

Short abstract

Saline wastewater is originated by several industries and requires optimized treatment methods focusing on two key goals: effective removal of toxic organics and efficient salt removal or recovery. However, high salt content and toxic organics often hinder bioprocessing treatment solutions. To this aim, in this study a two-phase partitioning bioreactor (TPPB) operated with a polymeric tubing was tested for treating highly saline wastewater. Main outcomes of the study are the practically complete removal of the organic fraction (removal efficiencies >99%) and simultaneous recovering of an effluent reusable as brine.

#3.21

Start-up and optimization of mono-digestion with land-based recirculating aquaculture system sludge

Abdullah Bugra Senol¹, Linn Solli², Nazli Pelin Kocatürk Schumacher¹, John Morken¹

¹Faculty of Science and Technology (REALTEK), Norwegian University of Life Sciences (NMBU), Ås, Norway. ²The Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research, Ås, Norway

Abdullah Bugra Senol

What is your current position?

PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

I am a PhD student at NMBU, Norway. My study field covers energy and nutrient recovery from wastewater.

Short abstract

This study explores the potential of anaerobic digestion to recover energy from sludge produced in recirculating aquaculture system (RAS). Two semi-continuous anaerobic digesters were used to degrade smolt fish aquaculture sludge without co substrate addition. Mono-digestion of aquaculture sludge will be assessed by determining chemical oxygen demand (COD) removal efficiency, biogas production, methane (CH₄) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) content in the produced biogas. Our study aims to highlight the potential of anaerobic digestion and energy recovery, while promoting sustainable waste management practices within the land-based aquaculture industry.

#3.22

Optimising a novel electrochemical approach for phosphorous recovery from wastewater

Simona Pruiti^{1,2}, Kirsten van der Geest¹, Leon Korving^{1,3}, Philipp Kuntke^{1,2}, Michel Saakes^{1,4}, Cees Buisman^{1,2}

¹Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ²Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, Netherlands. ³Aiforo, Breda, Netherlands. ⁴NHL Stenden, Leeuwarden, Netherlands

Simona Pruiti

What is your current position?

PhD researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Simona Pruiti holds a Bachelor's and Master's degree in Chemical Engineering from the University of Palermo. During her Master's, she gained expertise in electrochemistry through advanced courses and laboratory experience. Currently pursuing her PhD at Wetsus and Wageningen University & Research, she has been working for two years on optimizing an electrochemical technology aimed at removing and recovering calcium phosphate. Her work contributes to advancing sustainable solutions in resource recovery, bridging research with practical environmental applications.

Short abstract

Electrochemical technologies can be effective in removing and recovering resources from brines. One example is the recovery of phosphorous (P) from cheese brine. Unfortunately, due to the high concentration of chloride, the production of chlorine at the anode is a major challenge. This work shows that, by keeping the anodic potential low enough by using the hydrogen oxidation reaction at the anode, it is possible to prevent this unwanted chloride oxidation reaction. While the electrochemical system promises to be energy efficient, limitations in phosphate recovery remain a challenge for the technology to be addressed in future research.

#3.23

Phosphorus Removal from Municipal Wastewaters and Surface Waters Using Natural Mineral-Based Sorbents

Rūta Ozola-Davidāne¹, Jūlija Karasa^{2,1}, Sandija Ozoliņa-Grīneviča¹, Solvita Kostjukova³, Alise Viķele¹, Annija Emersons^{3,1}, Inga Jansone⁴

¹Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies, Jelgava, Latvia. ²University of Latvia, Rīga, Latvia. ³P-Agro, Rīga, Latvia. ⁴APP Institute of Agresources and Economics, Dižstende, Latvia

Rūta Ozola-Davidāne

What is your current position?

Tenured associate professor

Short biography of the presenter

PhD, Associate Professor at the Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies, Institute of Landscape Architecture and Environmental Engineering, Faculty of Forest and Environmental Sciences.

Project manager of this research supported projects:

- 1) Administration of Latvian Environmental Protection Fund project No. 1-08/86/2024 “Innovative solution for wastewater treatment and phosphorus recovery” (previous project No. 1-08/92/2023 “Evaluation of the application of filter L for the recovery of phosphorus from wastewater for the promotion of circular economy”);
- 2) Interreg Estonia-Latvia Programme 2021–2027 project No. EE-LV00163 NutriLoopWorks “Circular Nutrient Recovery for Sustainable Municipalities”.

Short abstract

Phosphorus emissions from municipal wastewater and surface runoffs are a primary reason for aquatic ecosystems eutrophication, demanding urgent, effective, sustainable and scalable treatment solutions. This study evaluates the potential use of natural mineral-based sorbents for phosphorus capture and removal in both municipal wastewater treatment systems (e.g. post treatment processes) and small surface water bodies. It is also intended to explore the recovery and reuse of the captured in situ phosphorus as promising soil amendment in municipal green spaces, contributing to circular nutrient management.

#3.24

In-situ caproate recovery during open-culture fermentation for enhanced production

Seyed Behzad Rouhipour, Natalia Gutowska, Nay Yee Wint, Piotr Oleskowicz-Popiel

Water Supply and Bioeconomy Division, Faculty of Environmental Engineering and Energy, Poznan University of Technology, Berdychowo 4, 60-965, Poznan, Poland

Seyed Behzad Rouhipour

What is your current position?

PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

Seyed Behzad Rouhipour is a Ph.D. student at the Poznan University of Technology, Faculty of Environmental Engineering and Energy in Poland. He is doing his PhD under the supervision of Professor Piotr Oleśkowicz-Popiel and co-supervised by Dr Natalia Gutowska. His research interests are the production and recovery of carboxylic acids in the fermentation processes for converting waste into valuable products. His current area of research focuses on the development of in-situ product recovery (ISPR) for caproic acid production.

Short abstract

The in situ product recovery (ISPR) method was applied to recover caproate during open culture fermentation to enhance production. The study was conducted in two stages. In the first stage, four vegetable oils, such as olive, canola, sunflower, and rapeseed oil, were tested with five extractants, including trioctylphosphine oxide (TOPO), trioctylamine (TOA), CYTOP 503, oleyl alcohol, and 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate ([BMIM][PF₆]) at concentrations of 1%, 3%, and 5% (w/v), for extraction phase screening under lab-controlled conditions. The most effective system for caproate extraction, based on extraction efficiency (EE%), distribution coefficient (K_d), and selectivity (S), was identified as 5% TOPO dissolved in vegetable oils, achieving EE% values ranging from 72% to 80%. This organic phase was tested in fed-batch fermentation in the second stage to evaluate caproate production, microbial performance, and EE% under real conditions. The findings showed that using ISPR with vegetable oils and 5% TOPO positively affected recovery with high selectivity and enhanced caproate yield and productivity by reducing product inhibition.

#3.25

Using struvite as a fire-extinguishing agent: Feasibility and key influencing factors

Xin Ye¹, Hancheng Xie^{1,2}, Shaohua Chen¹

¹Institute of Urban Environment, CAS, Xiamen, China. ²Fuzhou University, Fuzhou, China

Xin Ye

What is your current position?

Associate Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Xin Ye is an associate researcher at the Institute of Urban Environment, Chinese Academy of Sciences, specializing in wastewater treatment and nutrient recovery. His research interests span phosphorus recovery, numerical simulation, and life cycle assessment. Ye is dedicated to advancing the practical application of struvite crystallization and brings extensive experience in reactor design, operational optimization, understanding particle evolution mechanisms, controlling pollutant migration and transformation, cost-effect analysis, and product valorization.

Short abstract

Recovering struvite as a fire-extinguishing agent could valorize it and encourage costly phosphorus recovery technologies. Limited research has explored this potential. Our study assessed converting wastewater struvite into a fire-extinguishing agent, comparing its effectiveness to conventional ABC (NH₄H₂PO₄) powder via thermogravimetric analyses and multiscale experiments. We examined how struvite characteristics—particle size, morphology, elemental composition, and organic content—affect performance. Results show struvite effectively extinguishes fires in wooden stacks and oil basins with less dosage than ABC powder. Wastewater-derived struvite promises as a green fire-extinguishing agent, contributing to global phosphorus recovery.

#3.26

Toward Sustainable Wastewater Management: Integrating Biorefineries for Bio-Waste Valorisation and Certified Circular Economy Practices

Elisa Blumethal¹, Alessia Foglia¹, Anna Laura Eusebi¹, Massimiliano Sgroi¹, Nicola Frison², Francesco Fatone¹

¹UNIVPM, ANCONA, Italy. ²UNIVR, VERONA, Italy

Francesco Fatone

What is your current position?

Full Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Full professor in Chemical Engineering, raised more than 10 million euros from EU-funded projects and more than 0.5 from private funding. (a) Team member of more than 15 International R&D&I projects (FP6; FP7; Horizon2020;LIFE+). (c) Member of expert committee about circular economy and member of the expert policy-support group of the Italian Ministry of Environment. (d) co-author of 159 SCOPUS-indexed paper - Hindex = 43; (e) General Secretary of the IWA Resource Recovery from Water Cluster; (f) member of executive board of Ecomondo; (g) International Water Association (IWA) fellow.

Short abstract

Biorefineries are innovative facilities that promote circular economy principles by producing multiple bio-products from bio-wastes. This study presents the first biorefinery integrated into a wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) in Lombardy, Italy, which produces volatile fatty acids (VFAs), struvite, and polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) from sewage sludge (SS), agri-food waste, and organic municipal solid waste (OFMSW). Emphasis is placed on upstream processes, including feedstock collection and transportation, to complement current certification scheme ensuring that the entire production process is sustainable and circular. Reliable certification schemes are essential for ensuring traceability, safety, and environmental performance, thus increasing consumer trust in bio-based products.

#3.27

How silicone membrane extraction improves bioplastic production from cheese whey

[Fabiano Asunis](#)¹, Paolo Dessi², Giorgia De Gioannis¹, Aldo Muntoni¹

¹University of Cagliari, Cagliari, Italy. ²University of Naples Federico II, Naples, Italy

Fabiano Asunis

What is your current position?

Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Fabiano Asunis is a researcher at the Department of Civil, Environmental Engineering and Architecture (DICAAR) of the University of Cagliari, where he also lectures in Biological Reactors within the Industrial and Environmental Biotechnology program. His research focuses on developing bioprocesses to convert agro-industrial residues into high-value bioproducts, including biopolymers, organic acids, and biofuels. He holds a PhD in Earth and Environmental Sciences, and, with over 20 publications and 70 peer reviews, he contributes actively to the field. He has been a visiting researcher in Finland, Portugal, and Ireland, and participated in entrepreneurship programs across Europe and the USA.

Short abstract

This study presents a novel four-stage process for producing polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) from nutrient-rich sheep cheese whey. A silicone membrane-based volatile fatty acid (VFA) extraction step was integrated to tailor carbon-to-nitrogen ratios for microbial selection and PHA accumulation. This innovation increased the maximum PHA content from 28% to 37% (w/w) and doubled the storage yield. The process offers an efficient strategy to valorize dairy waste into high-value bioplastics through the integration of bioprocess and selective separation technologies, contributing to circular resource recovery and bioeconomy.

#3.28

Effect of emerging contaminants on Microalgal-Bacterial Aerobic Granular Sludge (MB-AGS) technology for water resource recovery: Performance, microbial communities, biotransformation and resistance genes

Moein Besharati Fard^{1,2,3}, Jo De Vrieze^{1,3}, Di Wu^{1,2}

¹Department of Green Chemistry and Technology, Centre for Advanced Process Technology for Urban Resource recovery (CAPTURE), Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium, Ghent, Belgium. ²Center of Green Chemistry and Environmental Biotechnology (GREAT), Ghent University Global Campus, Incheon, Republic of Korea, Incheon, Korea, Republic of.

³Center for Microbial Ecology and Technology (CMET), Ghent, Belgium

Moein Besharati Fard

What is your current position?

Research and Teaching assistant-PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

Moein Besharati Fard is a PhD student at Ghent University, specializing in environmental technology. His research focuses on the biotransformation and fate of emerging contaminants, particularly antibiotics and Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances, within resource recovery cycles. With a primary focus on microalgal-bacterial systems and anaerobic digestion processes, he aims to develop sustainable, low-emission solutions. He is affiliated with CMET (Center for Microbial Ecology and Technology, Belgium) and GREAT (Center of Green Chemistry and Environmental Biotechnology, Global Campus, South Korea), developing innovative approaches to optimize biological processes for environmental challenges.

Short abstract

Microalgal-bacterial aerobic granular sludge (MB-AGS) technologies are promising due to their ability to maintain treatment performance and adapt to environmental stressors. This study evaluated the performance of MB-AGS in response to antibiotic stress in two bioreactors, R₁ and R₂, exposed to tetracycline (TC) and ciprofloxacin (CIP), respectively. The investigation focused on (i) monitoring removal efficiency of conventional pollutants, (ii) identifying mechanisms contributing to antibiotic transformation, and (iii) tracking the evolution of microbial community dynamics and antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) under antibiotic exposure. These findings provide insights into development of MB-AGS for water resource recovery under micropollutant exposure.

#3.29

Recovery of sodium sulphate and water from precipitated silica wastewater: pre-industrial scale results & replicability studies at lab-scale

Caroline Sielfeld¹, Miguel Cano², Maria de la Salud Camilleri¹, [Judit Cañellas](#)¹

¹EURECAT, Cerdanyola, Spain. ²Industrias Químicas del Ebro, Zaragoza, Spain

Caroline Sielfeld

What is your current position?

Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Caroline Sielfeld is an Industrial & Bioprocess Engineer and holds Master of Science in Chemical and Bioprocess Engineering (Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile). She works as a researcher at Eurecat since 2020, coordinating and executing private and public funded R&D projects related to the treatment and valorization of urban and industrial residual effluents, and sustainable water management.

Judit Cañellas

What is your current position?

Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Mrs. Cañellas received her M.Sc. and Ph.D. from Cranfield University (UK) for her research on improving ion exchange processes to more effectively recover reactive nitrogen from wastewater. She is a member of the Royal Society of Chemistry, serves as a reviewer for Fulbright UK/US as well as multiple scientific journals. Currently she works at Eurecat as an advanced researcher, focusing on nutrients recovery through ion exchange processes and membrane distillation.

Short abstract

LIFE ZEROSILIBRINE project demonstrates a circular economy-oriented process based on reverse osmosis (RO) and crystallization to recover water and Na₂SO₄ from precipitated silica production wastewater. The pre-industrial plant installed at IQE (Zaragoza, Spain) consists of an UF-RO membranes unit coupled to a crystallization unit. Current results are promising: the RO unit achieves a water recovery of 84%, and the crystallization unit generates recovered Na₂SO₄ with a purity of 96.1%. The treatment (RO concentration step) has been also successfully tested at laboratory scale with other industrial saline effluents (from textile, food and chemical industries), confirming the replicability potential of the process.

#3.30

Unlocking Resource Potential in Brewery Effluents: Screening Microalgae for Essential Nutrient Recovery and Biomass Production

Belén Villarreal-Toribio, [Etielle Morais](#), Enrica Uggetti
Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain

Etielle Morais

What is your current position?

Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Etielle Greque is a Food Engineer and holds a Ph.D. in Food Science and Engineering. She has more than 15 years of experience in microalgae cultivation, downstream processing, and biomass applications. Her research has consistently focused on innovative approaches to harness microalgae as sustainable and eco-friendly solutions. She has worked with microalgae in Brazil, Uruguay, and Portugal, enhancing her expertise in international contexts. Since March 2022, Dr. Morais has been at UPC within the Environmental Engineering and Microbiology Research Group (GEMMA), where her work centers on cultivating microalgae in wastewater, aiming for the total valorization of the produced biomass.

Short abstract

This research investigates brewery effluent as a sustainable nutrient resource for producing microalgae biomass, emphasizing nutrient recovery and the selection of strains. Screening assessments of three microalgae strains—*Scenedesmus* sp., *Chlorella* sp., and *Spirulina* sp.—in different stages of effluent revealed that *Scenedesmus* sp. and *Chlorella* sp. in pre-acidified effluent were ideal for maximizing biomass production and nutrient extraction. The findings indicated a notable decrease in COD and phosphate, highlighting these strains as potential candidates for treating brewery wastewater and recovering resources in a circular manner. This study promotes sustainable, value-enhancing uses of microalgae in managing brewery waste.

#3.31

Unlocking Phosphate Recovery from Cow Manure: How Manure Age Affects Calcium Phosphate Recovery

Feride Ece Kutlar^{1,2}, Daniel Ofoegbu¹, Chris Schott¹, Renata van der Weijden², Cees Buisman^{1,2}

¹Wetsus, European Centre of Excellence for Sustainable Water Technology, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ²Sub-department of Environmental Technology, Wageningen University, Wageningen, Netherlands

Feride Ece Kutlar

What is your current position?

PhD

Short biography of the presenter

Feride Ece Kutlar is a PhD researcher at Wetsus – European Centre of Excellence for Sustainable Water Technology – and the Sub-department of Environmental Technology at Wageningen University. Her research focuses on sustainable resource recovery, with expertise in anaerobic digestion and biotechnology.

Short abstract

In the Netherlands, excessive phosphorus (P) from cow manure contributes to environmental pollution, despite P being a finite resource. Recovering P from manure offers a sustainable alternative to depleting phosphate reserves. This study evaluates the impact of manure age and temperature on P recovery as calcium phosphate (CaP). Results indicate that fresh manure enhances CaP precipitation, whereas old manure primarily forms struvite and CaCO₃. Manure age reduces P recovery potential, while inorganic carbon production plays key roles in precipitate formation. Rapid CaP formation in fresh manure offers a way to reduce nutrient losses and supports a shift toward circular agriculture.

#3.32

Engineering microbiological recovery of critical metals from industrial wastewaters.

Lordina Eshun, Jinxin Xie, Chris Egan-Morriss, Natalie Byrd, Richard Kimber, Vicky Coker, Jonathan Lloyd
University of Manchester, Manchester, United Kingdom

Lordina Eshun

What is your current position?

Research Scientist (Geomicrobiology Research)

Short biography of the presenter

Lordina Eshun holds a PhD in Environmental geochemistry and geomicrobiology from the University of Manchester. Her PhD research focused on developing a biotechnological approach for transforming phosphate-loaded Fe(III) oxides into useful agricultural fertilisers. Her current research is focused on the scale-up of *Shewanella oneidensis* using a 7L Applikon bioreactor for use in critical metal recovery from industrial waste.

Short abstract

The need for critical metals for industrial applications, such as clean energy technologies, is growing rapidly. Increasing demand for these metals (including copper/gold/platinum-group metals (PGMs), and rare earth elements (e.g., cerium) puts significant challenges on the environment due to their unsustainable extraction processes. Not only that but these metals are mined in a very restricted number of countries, raising issues with security of supply. Therefore, developing an approach for recycling and recovering these critical metals from waste streams is crucial. This poster gives an overview of metal bio-recovery research in the Geomicrobiology group of the University of Manchester.

#3.33

Brine valorization using bipolar membrane electro dialysis for acid and base production

Daniel E. Kelly Coto^{1,2}, Jan Post¹, Ruben Halfwerk¹, Leonardo Gutierrez^{2,3}, Emile Cornelissen^{2,4}

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Daniel E. Kelly Coto

What is your current position?

PhD researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Daniel is a PhD researcher at Wetsus, European Centre of Excellence for Sustainable Water Technology, specializing in brine valorization using electro dialysis with bipolar membranes for acid and base production. He holds a MSc. in Environmental Technology and Engineering (IMETE) from the Erasmus Mundus Joint Masters program and has experience in applied research on water treatment technologies and resource recovery. With a strong interest in bridging scientific research and industrial applications, he is passionate about innovation and entrepreneurship. He aims to develop scalable and impactful technologies that enhance water sustainability and resource efficiency.

Short abstract

Membrane-based desalination technologies, like reverse osmosis (RO), always produce brine. Scaling could limit water recovery, affecting brine volume. Managing brine is essential, but conventional methods (e.g., surface water discharge, deep-well injection, evaporation ponds) are costly and environmentally harmful. Bipolar membrane electro dialysis (BMED) on RO brine offers a promising solution, enabling resource recovery through acid and base production. However, BMED requires pretreatment to remove scaling-inducing ions, often relying on chemicals. This research proposes an innovative chemical-free brine softening process integrated with BMED to enhance water recovery, mitigate scaling, and enable resource recovery, contributing to more sustainable desalination processes.

#3.34

Electrochemical NH₃ recovery with electrical current pulse modulation and vacuum stripping. (Poster)

Iosif Kaniadakis

Technische Universiteit Delft, Delft, Netherlands

Iosif Kaniadakis

What is your current position?

PhD

Short biography of the presenter

*Provided earlier

Short abstract

The effective removal of ammonium (NH_4^+), which is commonly present in high concentrations in reject waters, can be achieved through a combination of electrodialysis reversal and be recovered as NH_3 with bipolar membrane electrodialysis. The recovered NH_3 is then further concentrated to an aqueous solution via vacuum membrane stripping. However, the concentration of NH_3 in the permeate during vacuum stripping is influenced by the concentration in the base chamber of the bipolar membrane electrodialysis module. To attain significantly high concentrations of recovered NH_3 at an elevated alkaline pH, bipolar electrodialysis can be controlled based on a target pH value.

#3.35

Removal of manganese and its potential recovery as manganese oxides in biofiltration systems

Elisavet Malea^{1,2}, Amanda Larasati¹, Annemerel Mol², Annemiek ter Heijne², Maria Cristina Gagliano¹

¹Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ²Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, Netherlands

Elisavet Malea

What is your current position?

PhD Candidate

Short biography of the presenter

Elisavet Malea has a background in chemistry and holds a BSc and MSc in Chemistry from Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, specializing in chemical technology and industrial applications. She is a PhD candidate affiliated with Wageningen University & Research and Wetsus, focusing on the biological removal of manganese and the prevention of (bio)fouling in membrane filtration systems. This research integrates fundamental science with practical applications to improve water quality and support sustainable treatment methods.

Short abstract

This study aims to investigate manganese (Mn) removal using (bio)filtration with varying filter media. Mn is typically present in groundwater as soluble Mn(II) and is removed to maintain the aesthetics and safety of treated water. In biofilters, Mn(II) is converted to manganese oxides (MnOx) by manganese-oxidizing bacteria (MnOB), with MnOx incorporated into the biofilm growing on top of the filtration media. MnOx of biological origin are among the strongest natural oxidizing agents, which can be applied as catalyst. During biofilter backwashing, the biofilms, including MnOx, are removed, offering an opportunity for their recovery and further use.

#3.36

Biological coagulant recovery: a novel method to increase resilience and sustainability in drinking water and wastewater treatment processes

Rachael Giles¹, Timothy Holloway², Adam Moody³, Richard Clarke³, Cathy Gillett³, Faye Williams⁴, Daniel Rowlands⁴, Tamsyn Kennedy⁵, Cynthia Carliell-Marquet⁶, Keiron Maher⁶, Joanne Claronino⁶, Ana Soares¹, Bruce Jefferson¹

¹Cranfield University, Cranfield, United Kingdom. ²Thames Water, Reading, United Kingdom. ³United Utilities, Warrington, United Kingdom. ⁴Welsh Water, Cardiff, United Kingdom. ⁵Scottish Water, Stepps, United Kingdom. ⁶Severn Trent, Coventry, United Kingdom

Rachael Giles

What is your current position?

PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

Rachael is a PhD research student at Cranfield University and is part of the Water Infrastructure and Resilience (WIRe) CDT. Her research focuses on investigating the use of microorganisms for biological iron-based coagulant recovery from both drinking water and wastewater treatment processes, and the potential for reuse of this recovered product.

Short abstract

Coagulant dosing has long been used in both drinking water and wastewater treatment processes to remove impurities. However, this linear process, where coagulant is dosed once before disposal, is under increasing stress from market volatility and environmental targets. A novel method is proposed using iron reducing bacteria (IRB) to release iron from sludge for re-use as coagulant. IRB are known to be present in wastewater sludges, however the iron forms present are not always suitable for reduction. Targeting sludges with the most reducible iron may enable efficient recovery of an otherwise waste material, improving resilience and sustainability in coagulation.

#3.37

Lithium Occurrence in Brazilian Aquifers: A Path to Strategic Resource Exploitation

Inalmar Barbosa Segundo¹, Bruno Fukasawa¹, Gracyelly Leocádio¹, Raimon Alfaro², Caroline Colle³, Frank Despinois³, Jonathan Espíndola¹, José Mierzwa¹

¹International Reference Center on Water Reuse, Environmental and Hydraulic Department (PHA), Polytechnic School, University of São Paulo (IRCWR-USP), Sao Paulo, Brazil. ²TotalEnergies E&P Brasil, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

³TotalEnergies OneTech, Pau, France

Inalmar Barbosa Segundo

What is your current position?

Postdoc

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Barbosa Segundo is a postdoctoral researcher at the International Reference Center on Water Reuse of the University of São Paulo (IRCWR-USP), currently working on a lithium recovery project funded by TotalEnergies. He holds a degree in Environmental Engineering, a Master's in Development and Environment, and a Ph.D. in Environmental Engineering, with a focus on the treatment of leachate from hazardous and non-hazardous waste landfills. His research centers on advanced oxidation processes for water and wastewater treatment, with experience in biological systems. His current interests include resource recovery and direct potable water reuse.

Short abstract

Public data on water analysis from Brazilian wells reveal that shallow aquifers don't contain sufficient levels for lithium recovery. A mathematical model for lithium prediction in waterbodies from sedimentary basins suggested its presence in some wells, but analysis of actual samples showed very low values. However, produced waters (PW) data from onshore oil and gas (O&G) activity confirm lithium in higher values, hinting at untapped sources. These aquifers emerge as the most promising reservoirs, potentially holding significant lithium concentrations. These findings underscore the need for further investigation into deep groundwater as a strategic resource for lithium recovery in Brazil.

#3.38

Advancing Resource Recovery in Water Utilities: Introducing the Resource Maturity Index

Julian Muñoz Sierra^{1,2}, Sjoerd Kerstens³, Paul Roeleveld³, Jacob Kragh Andersen⁴, Morten Rebsdorf⁵, Per Overgaard Pedersen⁵

¹KWR Water Research Institute, Nieuwegein, Netherlands. ²Delft University of Technology, Delft, Netherlands. ³Royal HaskoningDHV, Amersfoort, Netherlands. ⁴Envidan A/S, Kastrup, Denmark. ⁵Aarhus Vand A/S, Viby J, Denmark

Julian Muñoz Sierra

What is your current position?

Scientific Researcher and Project Manager

Short biography of the presenter

Julian Muñoz Sierra is a Colombian Chemical Engineer. After graduation, he worked in water treatment, including two years as a project engineer managing industrial projects. In 2010, he moved to the Netherlands for a Bioprocess Engineering Doctorate at Delft University of Technology, specializing in Environmental Biotechnology. After that, he pursued his PhD project (BioXtreme) on anaerobic membrane bioreactors treating chemical industrial wastewater under extreme conditions.

Since 2018, Julian has worked at KWR Water Research Institute developing innovative water treatment technologies and providing research based consultancy services. He has a position as adjunct researcher at TU Delft one day weekly.

Short abstract

Resource recovery is closely linked to innovative water resource recovery facilities (WRRFs), which are evolving towards a circular economy and making a significant societal impact. Our work emphasizes the need for tools to evaluate recovery options across water, sludge, and gas streams. While Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) exist, a method to quantify demand for recoverable resources is missing. To bridge this gap, the Resource Maturity Index (RMI) is proposed, assessing resource readiness through Commercial (CRL), Societal (SRL), and Legal (LRL) Readiness Levels. Using a measurable "bottom-up" approach, RMI aims to guide water utilities toward more sustainable, resource recovery facility practices.

#3.39

Potential for lithium recovery from produced water in offshore oil fields: a case study of Brazil

Bruno Fukasawa¹, Inalmar Barbosa Segundo¹, Gracyelle Leocádio¹, Raimon Alfaro², Caroline Colle³, Frank Despinois³, Jonathan Espíndola¹, José Mierzwa¹

¹University of São Paulo, São Paulo, Brazil. ²TotalEnergies E&P Brasil, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. ³TotalEnergies OneTech, Pau, France

Bruno Fukasawa

What is your current position?

PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

Environmental Engineer from the Polytechnic School of the University of São Paulo (EPUSP), with a Master's degree in non-potable water reuse planning from the same institution. Currently pursuing a Ph.D. at EPUSP, focusing on direct potable reuse.

Short abstract

Lithium is a critical resource for the energy transition, but its conventional extraction is geographically constrained and relies on environmentally harmful methods. Produced water (PW) is a byproduct of oil extraction and contains significant lithium concentrations, representing a still untapped source. Brazil is home to one of the world's largest oil productions, holding promising potential for lithium recovery. Analysis of four Brazilian offshore sedimentary basins revealed averaging lithium of 79.4 mg/L (peaking at 404 mg/L), or a theoretical potential of 0.016 MtLCE/year based on the 2024 PW production, equivalent to 1.3% of the current global lithium demand.

#3.40

The pre-treatments renaissance: from burden to boon in resource recovery mission

Andrea Gianico¹, [Agata Gallipoli](#)¹, Barbara Tonanzi^{1,2}, Maria Cristina Gagliano³, Stefania Angelini¹, Simona Crognale^{1,2}, Carlo Pastore⁴, Daniele Montecchio¹, Simona Rossetti¹, Camilla Maria Braguglia¹

¹Water Research Institute (CNR), Rome, Italy. ²National Biodiversity Future Center (NBFC), Palermo, Italy. ³Wetsus, European Centre of Excellence for Sustainable Water Technology, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ⁴Water Research Institute (CNR), Bari, Italy

Agata Gallipoli

What is your current position?

NA

Short biography of the presenter

NA

Camilla Maria Braguglia

What is your current position?

Senior Scientist

Short biography of the presenter

Camilla Braguglia is Senior Scientist at Water Research Institute of National Research Council, where she leads since 2008 the Research team on Waste Treatment and Valorization. Her main research interests falls within the broad area of environmental biotechnology for waste minimization, decontamination and biomass valorization, in particular bioenergy and chemicals production. The approach is to study and develop efficient technological solutions with particular attention to the fundamental aspects of the processes together with the technological transferability. She (co)-authored 90 articles in peer-reviewed ISI Journals and International Book chapters, and co-inventor of a patent on sludge reduction and biogas production.

Short abstract

In the framework of circular economy, we are asked to recover resources typically entrapped in complex waste matrices. Feedstock pre-treatments, often questioned in the past due to their high costs, are now the golden key to open the resource recovery door. Here we share decades of experience on the topic, both at lab and full-scale, from application of ultrasounds to boost anaerobic digestion of sludge, to thermal hydrolysis of food waste to extract carbohydrates and ignite chain elongation process. Mechanisms of each pretreatment are explained, evaluating pros and cons based on waste type, resource to be recovered, and economic feasibility.

#3.41

The aftermath of the disruption of the FeCl₃ supply chain: Examining Continuity of Essential Resources in Wastewater Treatment.

Joshua de Jong^{1,2}, Olaf van der Kolk¹, Jacqueline de Danschutter¹

¹AquaMinerals, Nieuwegein, Netherlands. ²University of Amsterdam, Amsterdam, Netherlands

Joshua de Jong

What is your current position?

Business developer / Business intelligence Specialist

Short biography of the presenter

I have a background in industrial engineering and management. During my studies, I interned at AquaMinerals, researching critical success factors in circular supply chains. Afterward, I completed a traineeship there, deepening my expertise in resource management, business development, and project management. Since 2024, I have worked as a business developer and business intelligence specialist at AquaMinerals, focusing on circular materials and data infrastructure. My research includes disruptions in chemical supply chains, the subject of this abstract. Additionally, I am pursuing an MBA at the University of Amsterdam to further expand my skills and knowledge.

Short abstract

This year-long study explored challenges in maintaining essential resources for wastewater treatment, focusing on ferric chloride (FeCl₃). It found widespread continuity issues in late 2022 and early 2023 due to hydrochloric acid shortages, driven by the Ukraine war, COVID-19, and industrial disruptions. Short-term solutions included purchasing collectives, calamity protocols, and alternative resources. For the long term, the report suggested sustainable options like using iron sludge from drinking water production and magnesium for phosphate removal. It concluded that adopting these measures can reduce dependence on ferric chloride, fostering more sustainable and circular practices in wastewater treatment processes.

#3.42

Spatial distribution of microbial interactions as the key driver of enhanced energy generation in tubular microbial fuel cells treating diverse organic compounds

Vitor Cano^{1,2}, Julio Cano², Chenghua Long¹, Kartik Chandran¹, Julio Meneghini², Marcelo Nolasco²

¹Columbia University, Earth and Environmental Engineering Department, New York, USA. ²University of Sao Paulo, Sao Paulo, Brazil

Vitor Cano

What is your current position?

Postdoctoral Research Fellow

Short biography of the presenter

I have a PhD degree in sustainability at the University of Sao Paulo (USP, Brazil), with part of the doctoral research carried out in Kartik Chandran's lab at Columbia University. I have a bachelor's and master's in the environmental field in with research exchange at Blanca Jimenez's group at the National Autonomous University of Mexico. For the last 10 years, I have been working in research projects for the development of environmental science and technology, biotechnology and sustainability.

Marcelo Nolasco

What is your current position?

Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Associate Professor at University of Sao Paulo (USP) Brazil. During his doctorate he was also Visiting Scholar at Miami University, USA (PhD Sandwich). He obtained his Ph.D. from USP in the area of sanitation - wastewater treatment. He holds a postdoctoral degree from the Civil and Environmental Engineering Department, University of California - Berkeley, USA (2015-2016). He coordinated the Postgraduate Program (M.Sc., P.h.D.) in Sustainability, and was one of its founders. Among his main interests: wastewater treatment systems, production of bioenergy in bioelectrochemical systems, removal of organic micropollutants (pharmaceuticals, hormones, personal care products) in natural water and wastewater. resources recovery from wastes.

Short abstract

This study examines the spatial distribution of microbial composition and interactions along the anode column of tubular Microbial fuel cells fed with diverse organic carbon sources Under optimal external resistance (R_{ext}) ($R_{ext} \cong R_{int}$) vs limiting R_{ext} ($R_{ext} \gg R_{int}$), *Geobacter* abundance increased, ranging from 17% to 31%, and a diverse array of other Electroactive bacteria (EAB) were observed. A key finding was that only under optimal R_{ext} a spatially-distributed synergistic interaction for organic carbon transformation and extracellular electron transfer was developed among hexose-oxidizing, propionate-oxidizing bacteria, and EAB. This syntrophy sustained higher EAB abundance, up to 2.4 times, along the anode column.

#3.43

A greenfield wwtp addressing water challenges in treating wastewater in the 21st century

maaike hoekstra¹, Yasmina Doekhi-Bennani¹, Coert Petri², Gijs van Pruissen³

¹Hoogheemraadschap Hollands Noorderkwartier, Heerhugowaard, Netherlands. ²Waterschap Vallei en Veluwe, Apeldoorn, Netherlands. ³waterschap Aa en Maas, den Bosch, Netherlands

maaike hoekstra

What is your current position?

innovation engineer

Short biography of the presenter

innovation enigineer at HHNK

Short abstract

The treatment of communal wastewater faces many challenges in the first half of the 21st century, intensified by impending legislative directives and ambitious goals. Maybe it will be possible to obtain an effluent wastewater quality that meets the new regulations by optimising the existing WWTPs. But to obtain a closed water cycle, net zero carbon footprint and circularity, a new system of wastewater treatment needs to be designed. We believe in a very systemic review of our 'standard operating procedures', and propose to do this by developing a vision on wastewater treatment with current knowledge if we could start afresh.

#3.44

Unlocking the potential of resource recovery from wastewater: The Forthbank Resource Recovery Factory.

Ania Escudero¹, Fiona Millar², Deryck Irving², Andrew Tyler², Tamsyn Kennedy³, Grant Hemple³

¹Glasgow Caledonian University, GLASGOW, United Kingdom. ²University of Stirling, Stirling, United Kingdom. ³Scottish Water, GLASGOW, United Kingdom

Ania Escudero

What is your current position?

Research Fellow

Short biography of the presenter

A Research Fellow in the Department of Civil Engineering and Environmental Management at Glasgow Caledonian University, Ania is a leading expert on waste and wastewater treatment, with her research centred around nutrient recovery and waste valorisation. As Research Leader Fellow under the Hydro Nation Chair programme focused on embracing the circular economy, Ania is developing opportunities within the Scottish water sector aimed at minimising waste and promoting the sustainable use of resources derived from wastewater. Ania is building a research programme that embrace the circular economy and addresses the challenges and opportunities of the mission.

Short abstract

Unlocking the intrinsic value of wastewater and biosolids is essential for achieving net-zero targets and driving a green economy. In response, Scottish Water is developing a Resource Recovery Factory (RRF) demonstrator at a WWTP in central Scotland. This testbed will evaluate resource recovery technologies, exploring their scalability and assessing their potential replication across Scotland. Supported by the Hydro Nation Chair Programme, exploring markets for recovered resources which feed into the demonstrator, the RRF offers a platform for innovation and research. This demonstrator represents a keystone in positioning the water industry as a pillar of the Circular Economy.

#3.45

End-to-End Integration of Data Preprocessing, Modeling, and Predictive Control for Full-scale Industrial Wastewater Treatment

Min Yang¹, Ke Chen², Ning Gui³, Aijie Wang¹

¹Harbin Institute of Technology, Shenzhen, ShenZhen, China. ²University of South China, HengYang, China. ³Central South University, ChangSha, China

Min Yang

What is your current position?

Associate Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Yang Min is an associate professor at Harbin Institute of Technology Shenzhen, he was Marie Curie Fellow in the Department of Mathematical Analysis and Modelling at Ghent University, Belgium. He currently serves as Chair of the IWA CFD Professional Committee and Vice Chair & Secretary-General of the European Chinese Ecological Environment Association. With long-term dedication to fundamental research and applications in CFD, his recent focus spans integrated computing and energy efficiency optimization for chemical-environmental processes. Actively engaged in smart water R&D and technology commercialization, he has developed foundational models and software/hardware facilities for the water sector.

Short abstract

This study proposes an end-to-end framework integrating mechanistic models and deep learning (Transformer, CNN-LSTM, RNN) for industrial wastewater treatment. Leveraging full-scale data from Hongxing Wastewater Treatment Plant, the approach combines mechanistic model-based data cleaning to address sensor errors and dynamic process nonlinearity. Deep learning models predict critical water quality parameters with enhanced accuracy, guiding adaptive adjustments of operational parameters (aeration, sludge retention, chemical dosing) via the Nelder-Mead algorithm.

Results demonstrate reduced prediction errors (MAE/MSE) and improved compliance with discharge standards. The integrated system enables real-time optimization, energy efficiency, and robust control, advancing digital twin applications for intelligent wastewater management.

#3.46

Enhancing Sustainable Water Supply in Ibu Kota Negara (IKN) Nusantara Through Innovative Sustainable Urban Drainage System (SUDS)

Lia Dahlia¹, [Raihan Firdaus](#)¹, Rifaldi Aji Sarifudin¹, Faizal Immaddudin Wira Rohmat¹, Eelco Van Beek²

¹Institut Teknologi Bandung, Bandung, Indonesia. ²Bandoengse Technische Hoogeschool Fonds, Bandung, Indonesia

Raihan Firdaus

What is your current position?

Spatial Analyst

Short biography of the presenter

Raihan is a spatial analyst specializing in water resource management planning. As the winner of the ITB-BTHF Hackathon 2023 under the theme "Designing Effective Data-Driven Strategies for Ensuring Sustainable, Resilient, and Sufficient Water Supply for IKN's Future Growth," Raihan is dedicated to advancing innovative, data-driven solutions for sustainable urban water systems.

Short abstract

The Sustainable Urban Drainage System provides an efficient method for improving water management in IKN Nusantara, facilitating a balanced strategy for urban runoff by capturing and repurposing water. This strategy reduces flood risks, guarantees a sustainable water supply, and enhances urban resilience while conforming to the Sustainable Development Goals. This study illustrates the efficacy of SUDS in flood management and sustainability enhancement. The economic viability, evaluated by the Internal Rate of Return and Benefit-Cost Ratio, underscores the commercial prospects of water sales. SUDS offers a scalable and sustainable framework for tackling water issues in rapidly urbanizing areas.

Acceptance type: Poster pitch

#1.1

Donnan Dialysis for Improved Resource Recovery from Greenhouse Wastewater Electrodesalination Concentrate: Selectively Separating Na⁺ and K⁺

Tavishi Guleria^{1,2}, Timion Rijnaarts¹, Joep van den Broeke¹, Leonardo Gutierrez², Emile Cornelissen^{1,2}
¹KWR Water Research Institute, Nieuwegein, Netherlands. ²Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium

Tavishi Guleria

What is your current position?

Scientific Researcher (KWR) and PhD Student (Ghent University)

Short biography of the presenter

Tavishi is currently a scientific researcher at KWR Water Research Institute and PhD student at the Particle and Interfacial Technology Group (PaInT) affiliated with Ghent University. Her specialization is in (electrochemical) membrane processes for selective-ion separation to achieve smart and scalable resource recovery, specifically for the agriculture and horticulture sectors. Additionally, she holds a master's in environmental engineering from TU Delft.

Short abstract

To achieve optimal reuse and minimal liquid discharge in greenhouse horticulture, this study introduces a novel Donnan dialysis (DD) approach for selective Na⁺ removal from electrodesalination concentrate using K⁺ as the driver ion. Lab-scale experiments with CEMs achieved 77% Na⁺ separation, reducing Na⁺ from 15 to 2 mmol/L, suitable for irrigation. The presence of Ca²⁺ reduced efficiency by 9%, mitigated using monovalent-selective membranes, which improved Na⁺ separation with minimal loss in efficiency. Scaled-up DD stacks demonstrated rapid and scalable performance, achieving superior Na⁺/K⁺ selectivity compared to literature, highlighting DD's potential for selective ion-separation for wastewater reuse in horticulture.

#1.4

Development of novel adsorbent biomaterials based on structural extracellular polymeric substances (sEPS) recovered from aerobic granular sludge for the treatment of heavy metal-contaminated wastewater

Benedetta Pagliaccia¹, Mirko Severi², Claudio Lubello¹, Tommaso Lotti¹

¹Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of Florence, Florence, Italy. ²Department of Chemistry "Ugo Schiff", University of Florence, Sesto Fiorentino (FI), Italy

Benedetta Pagliaccia

What is your current position?

Postdoctoral fellow

Short biography of the presenter

I am a postdoctoral fellow at University of Florence (Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering), working mainly on resource recovery from wastewater treatment. I completed a PhD under a double-degree agreement between University of Florence and INSA Toulouse, focused on the recovery, characterization and valorization of extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) from waste sludge (including aerobic and anammox granular sludges). I gained experience in converting EPS into value-added biomaterials of interest in various industrial sectors (wastewater treatment, agriculture, textile industry, etc.). I am contributing to research on emerging contaminants (microplastics and pharmaceuticals), developing advanced techniques for their environmental monitoring and removal.

Short abstract

The feasibility of applying structural extracellular polymeric substances (sEPS) extracted from aerobic granular sludge for the treatment of heavy metal-contaminated wastewaters was addressed. Equilibrium adsorption studies were performed by treating synthetic single- and multi-metal solutions and real wastewaters with sEPS aqueous suspensions (Na⁺-sEPS) and sEPS hydrogel beads. Under all tested conditions, both Na⁺-sEPS and hydrogel beads evidenced high metal-binding capacities, while differences between their adsorption pathways were highlighted, indicating different applicative potentials depending on the level of metal contamination. The promising outcome of this work paves the way for the development of highly performing sEPS-based wastewater treatment technologies.

#1.5

Energy-Efficient Redox Modulation for Enhanced Biomass Value: Enabling Sustainable Biorefinery Feedstocks from Wastewater Treatment

Xueyang Zhou, Bharat Manna, Boyu Lyu, Naresh Singhal
University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand

Xueyang Zhou

What is your current position?

Research Fellow

Short biography of the presenter

Zhou Xueyang graduated with a Ph.D. in environmental engineering from the University of Auckland, New Zealand, focusing on the biological treatment of wastewater. Xueyang is committed to improving wastewater resource utilization and advocating innovative process control strategies to optimize microbial nutrient recovery efficiency. He also has a keen interest in developing mechanistic insights through multi-omics analysis.

Short abstract

As wastewater treatment transitions from pollutant removal to resource recovery, there is an increasing emphasis on converting waste biomass into valuable products. Traditional treatment methods, however, often require high oxygen inputs, leading to substantial energy costs. Our study addresses this challenge by introducing an oxygen perturbation strategy that enhances the value of wastewater biomass as a biorefinery feedstock, focusing on proteins, lipids, amino acids, and fatty acids. By intermittently controlling DO levels between 0–2 mg/L, we reduce excessive oxygen supply, achieving significant energy savings while maintaining microbial metabolic activity.

#1.6

Flocculation kinetics and mechanisms of extracellular polymeric substances in clay suspensions

Bohan Chen^{1,2}, Carlos A. Contreras-Dávila¹, Huub Rijnaarts², Dainis Sudmalis²

¹Wetsus – European Centre of Excellence for Sustainable Water Technology, Oostergoweg 9, 8911MA, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ²Department of Environmental Technology, Wageningen University and Research, Bornse Weiland 9, 6708 WG, Wageningen, Netherlands

Bohan Chen

What is your current position?

PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

I am a PhD student at Wetsus. My research aims to improve extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) flocculation performance by understanding the production and flocculation mechanisms of EPS.

Short abstract

Investigating the flocculation kinetics of colloidal particles is essential for understanding the flocculation mechanisms of microbial extracellular polymers (EPS). This study investigated the flocculation performance of EPS, floc size and structure, and flocculation kinetics under different mixing conditions. The results indicated that mixing time was the key factor in EPS flocculation performance and flocs size and structure. A logistic growth model will be applied to study the flocculation kinetics with several types of EPS. The findings of this study will provide insights into EPS flocculation mechanisms and offer guidance for EPS production and application.

#1.7

Leveraging Alum Sludge for Natural Organic Matter and PFAS Removal in Drinking Water Treatment

Dane Elliott^{1,2}, Allison MacKay¹

¹Ohio State University, Columbus, USA. ²Stantec, Columbus, USA

Dane Elliott

What is your current position?

Graduate Research Associate

Short biography of the presenter

Dane is currently pursuing her PhD in Environmental Science at the Ohio State University, where she has worked as a graduate research associate since 2020. Dane's graduate research focuses on identifying beneficial reuse opportunities for drinking water treatment residuals. Additionally, Dane works at Stantec, an engineering design firm, as a Process Engineer EIT, where she works primarily on design of drinking and wastewater treatment facilities, including process design, residuals management, process optimization, and water quality analysis. Dane has a bachelor's degree in chemical engineering from Case Western Reserve University and a master's degree in environmental engineering from Ohio State University.

Short abstract

Emerging water treatment challenges include cost-effective contaminant removal and sustainable waste management. Reusing aluminum-based water treatment residuals (Al-WTR) addresses both. This study evaluates Al-WTR as an adsorbent for organic contaminants like disinfection byproduct precursors (e.g., natural organic matter) and PFAS in drinking water treatment. We investigated how Al-WTR processing impacts contaminant uptake via kinetic/isotherm studies and jar tests mimicking powdered activated carbon use. This research establishes Al-WTR as a sustainable adsorbent, potentially reducing reliance on costly virgin materials and enhancing downstream treatment, offering a more economically viable approach to achieving drinking water quality standards while repurposing a waste product.

#1.8

Sulfur in the post-fossil age: An exploratory mass flow analysis to identify opportunities for a circular sulfur system in The Netherlands

Sebastiaan van Veen, Miriam van Eekert, [Annemere! Mol](#)
Wageningen Research and University, Wageningen, Netherlands

Annemere! Mol

What is your current position?

Assistant professor

Short biography of the presenter

I'm curious about the capacity microorganisms have to recover valuable resources from (waste)water. I enjoy teaching students about technologies involving such microbial reactions and their role in a circular economy.

My core expertise is recovery of minerals and metals (such as S, Se, As, Fe and Mn) from wastewater using microbiological processes and (bio)crystallization. To work on real life environmental issues, I have established various partnerships with companies in the drinking water production and industrial wastewater treatment sectors. I am currently supervising five PhD students, and collaborate closely with Wetsus, European centre of excellence for sustainable water technology.

Short abstract

Since sulfur is primarily sourced from fossil fuel refinement, drastic sulfur shortages are expected when the world transitions to renewable energy sources. In this study we performed an exploratory mass flow analysis of sulfur in The Netherlands to quantify the current sulfur demand and to identify opportunities for circularity. We found that The Netherlands is highly dependent on external sulfur sources for its industry and agriculture, as mined materials are the primary source of sulfur. We conclude that preventing sulfur losses through surface water emission and groundwater leaching are key to improve the circularity of the agricultural sector.

#1.9

Siderophore Assisted Recovery Of Germanium From Industrial Wastewater: An Approach Towards Circular Economy

Aratrika Ghosh^{1,2}, Rohan Jain¹, Katrin Pollmann¹

¹Helmholtz zentrum Dresden Rossendorf, Dresden, Germany. ²Indian institute of Technology, Delhi, New Delhi, India

Aratrika Ghosh

What is your current position?

PhD

Short biography of the presenter

I am a PhD student from IIT Delhi, India. Currently, I am in Helmholtz Zentrum Dresden Rossendorf, Germany as a guest researcher on the DAAD fellowship. I work on the recovery of critical metals like germanium and gallium from industrial wastewater through sustainable approaches. My research interest are biohydrometallurgy and development of technologies related to siderophores for the recovery and up-concentration of critical metals.

Short abstract

Germanium (Ge) is a critical metal that holds strategic importance in the development of modern technologies like solar cells, catalysis, fiber optics etc. This has resulted in a steadily increasing demand of the metalloid but continuous supply is not assured. Hence, highly efficient and eco-friendly recovery of Ge from low-concentrated waste streams is important. Siderophore-assisted technology could be a solution. In the present study more than 90% Ge has been recovered using selective chelation of siderophore desferroxamine B. Thus, the present technology in combination with hydrometallurgical processes could be a great option to recover Ge sustainably.

#1.11

Utilization of RAS Effluent and Fish Sludge Digestate for Algal Cultivation and Nutrient Recovery

Nazlı Pelin Kocatürk Schumacher, John Morken, [Deniz Uçar](#), Melesse Eshetu Moges
Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Ås, Norway

Deniz Uçar

What is your current position?

Researcher at Faculty of Science and Technology

Short biography of the presenter

Deniz UÇAR is a professor at Bursa Technical University in Turkey. His research focuses on energy and resource recovery from wastewater. Since September 2024, he has been working as a researcher at the Norwegian University of Life Sciences on the SEAREFINERY project. The project aims to recover energy and nutrients from aquaculture wastewater using bacteria and algae-based reactors.

Short abstract

This study investigates nutrient recovery from wastewater and fish sludge in recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) using an algae-based approach. Wastewater and sludge collected from a RAS system were used for algal growth. The targeted algal species included *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Dunaliella salina*, *Schizochytrium sp.*, *Nannochloropsis*, and *Haematococcus*. By assessing their growth and nutrient uptake capabilities, we identified optimal combinations for potential fish feed applications.

#1.12

NTPlus - may just be the future for farming

Mike Waite

Agua DB Ltd, Bisley, United Kingdom

Mike Waite

What is your current position?

CEO

Short biography of the presenter

Mike is a serial innovator who's been looking at the problem of high nitrate in groundwater for the past 25 years. Six years ago, Mike realised that existing nitrate removal processes were neither affordable or sustainable and that the only way was to get the nitrate out of the water and back on the farm. Building on earlier work developing the segmented regeneration process for hexavalent chromium removal, NTPlus was born. Proof of concept was achieved in 2021 and, slowly, this solution kept getting better and better, becoming both climate change mitigation and adaption for both water and agriculture sectors.

Short abstract

Water companies have too many nutrients - and farmers want them. What could be a better solution than getting nutrients out of water and waste water and putting them back on the farm. This is NTPlus - and new, almost 100% efficient zero-waste ion exchange regeneration process which enables the use of potassium chloride and converts it to better nutrients - at 1/12th of the carbon cost of synthetic production. NTPlus recovers nitrate from groundwater and nitrate and phosphate from wastewater as liquid nutrients, driving variable rate application in precision agriculture and better nutrient use of the farm. An Industrial Ecology solution.

#1.13

Investigating Potential Flame-Retardant Mechanisms of Extracellular Polymeric Substances-based Biomaterials Recovered from Wastewater Sludge

Tan Minh Le^{1,2}, Yuemei Lin³, Wei-Qin Zhuang⁴, Mark van Loosdrecht³, Krishnan Jayaraman^{1,2}, Nam Kyeun Kim^{1,2}

¹Centre for Advanced Materials Manufacturing and Design, University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand. ²Department of Mechanical and Mechatronics Engineering, University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand. ³Department of Biotechnology, Delft University of Technology, Delft, Netherlands. ⁴Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand

Tan Minh Le

What is your current position?

PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

Tan Minh Le is a PhD candidate in the Department of Mechanical and Mechatronics Engineering at the University of Auckland, supervised by Dr. Nam Kyeun Kim, Prof. Krishnan Jayaraman, and Assoc. Prof. Yuemei Lin. He holds a bachelor's and a master's degree in Chemical Engineering from Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology, Vietnam National University. His current research focuses on developing innovative bio-based flame-retardant materials from extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) recovered from wastewater sludge.

Short abstract

This study explores the flame retardancy of extracellular polymeric substances (EPS)-based biomaterials derived from activated and blended sludges. A comprehensive set of experiments, including extraction process, thermal measurement and gas analysis, are conducted to investigate possible flame-retardant mechanisms of the biomaterials in condensed and gas phases. Both EPS-based biomaterials effectively form a char layer and release non-flammable gases to slow fire propagation. In particular, the EPS-based biomaterials recovered from the activated sludge demonstrate superior flame-retardant properties compared to their counterpart because of the higher activation energy, increased char residue content and release of nitrogen-containing compounds during combustion.

#1.14

Enhancing CO₂ valorization from biomethane and digestate streams to produce alternative proteins from green microalgae cultivation.

Georgina del Puerto-Tañà^{1,2}, Lidia Paredes¹, Josué González-Camejo¹, Marcella Fernandes de Souza², Erik Meers², Sergio Ponsá¹

¹BETA Technological Center. Universitat de Vic-Universitat Central de Catalunya, Vic, Spain. ²Department of Green Chemistry and Technology, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium

Georgina del Puerto-Tañà

What is your current position?

PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

PhD student on Environmental Technologies at BETA Technological Centre (BETA TC, UVic-UCC), focused on microalgae biomass production from digestate

Short abstract

This study is framed within SEMPRES-BIO project, aiming to recover CO₂ and nutrients from digestate and biogas streams using a 600-L outdoor photobioreactor to cultivate microalgae as integrated valorization strategy. The microalgae biomass produced could be used for animal-feed applications due to their high-protein content. This approach not only addresses environmental concerns related to waste management enhancing the implementation of biogas plants but contributes to the development of sustainable feed alternatives with the produced biomass, enhancing the circularity of the whole process. Preliminary results are promising, showing that the photobioreactor can produce 117 mgVSS/Ld with protein content of 48%.

#1.15

The role of salinity in modulating resource recovery from purple phototrophic bacteria mixed cultures

Alba Pedrouso, Jose Ramón Lorenzo-Llarena, Marcos Gonzalez-Nanin, Anuska Mosquera-Corral
Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, Santiago de Compostela, Spain

Alba Pedrouso

What is your current position?

Postdoctoral researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Alba works at CRETUS of the University of Santiago de Compostela in the Environmental Biotechnology group. Her research focuses on the development of biological processes for resource recovery using mixed cultures. As salinity is a key factor for biological treatment of industrial wastewater in Galicia (her region), she has extensive experience in investigating its effect on different microbial communities, including nitrification, anammox, aerobic granular sludge, and now photosynthetic systems.

Short abstract

Purple phototrophic bacteria (PPB) are promising for resource recovery, but salinity can significantly influence their performance. Two mixed cultures of purple phototrophic bacteria (PPB) were enriched from a common inoculum under saline (S-PPB, 35 g NaCl/L) and non-saline (NS-PPB) conditions. S-PPB, dominated by *Cereibacter sphaeroides* excelled in polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) accumulation reaching up to 60% dw, while NS-PPB (enriched in *Rhodopseudomonas palustris*) reached only 15%. Additionally, NS-PPB showed higher carotenoid production. Salt stress reduced biomass formation and phosphorus uptake, suggesting salinity-induced metabolic shifts. These findings highlight the critical role of salinity in optimizing PPB-based biorefineries for tailored resource recovery.

#1.16

Innovative Magnesite-assisted Electrochemical System for Enhanced Nutrient Recovery: Comparative Evaluation in A Wastewater Co-Treatment Scheme

Yang Lei, Zhengshuo Zhan

Southern University of Science and Technology (SUSTech), Shenzhen, China

Yang Lei

What is your current position?

Assistant Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Yang Lei (1989) was a Marine Sklodowska-Curie Fellow. He obtained PhD with Prof Cees Buisman from Wageningen University in 2019 on “electrochemical phosphorus removal and recovery”. Afterward, he worked on electrochemical P recovery at a large-scale in Wetsus as a post-doctoral researcher. In this period, he received the NWO Take-off Grant. In 2021, he joined SUSTech as an assistant professor. Currently, he is leading the Environmental Electrochemistry Laboratory at SUSTech. The mission of his lab is to initiate innovation in addressing the water-food-energy nexus challenge. His team works on energy-efficient wastewater treatment and resource recovery.

Zhengshuo Zhan

What is your current position?

Ph.D. researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Mr. Zhan is currently a Ph.D. researcher at the Southern University of Science and Technology (SUSTech) in China, specializing in electrochemical wastewater treatment and nutrient recovery.

Short abstract

Struvite recovery is an attractive method for integrated nitrogen and phosphorus recovery, while chemical precipitation (e.g., intensive sludge generation) and Mg electrocoagulation (e.g., anode passivation and complex struvite deposition) face inherent limitations. We here propose an innovative magnesite-assisted electrochemical system that enables easily recoverable struvite generation while eliminating anode passivation. Along with this innovative system, a co-treatment scheme for nitrogen- and phosphorus-rich wastewater is validated, overcoming stoichiometric constraints of struvite recovery and achieving notable cost savings and carbon reduction. This research offers a scalable and sustainable solution for enhanced nutrient recovery, supporting green initiatives in resource management and wastewater treatment.

#1.17

Sustainable Recovery of Critical Raw Materials and Water Reclamation from Acidic Mine Waters Using Integrated Treatment Processes

Alexandra Roa¹, Julio López¹, José Luís Cortina^{1,2}

¹Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain. ²CETaqua, Cornellà de Llobregat, Spain

Alexandra Roa

What is your current position?

PhD Student

Short biography of the presenter

Alexandra Roa is a chemical engineer PhD student from Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, working at the Resource Recovery and Environmental Management research group. She is focused on the valorisation of acidic mine waters to recover critical raw materials, using ion exchange, selective precipitation as well as membrane processes.

Short abstract

Acidic Mine Waters (AMW) pose environmental risks due to their metal content and acidity, while the demand for Critical Raw Materials (CRMs), including Rare Earth Elements (REEs), continues to grow.

This study introduces a circular treatment scheme integrating selective precipitation, ion exchange, crystallization, and nanofiltration (NF) to recover metals and reclaim water from AMW.

The process removed over 99% of transition metals and REEs, while NF effectively reduced salinity and enabled water reclamation.

This method provides a sustainable solution for CRM recovery and AMW treatment, supporting both resource security and environmental protection.

#1.18

Exploring the effect of variability in sewage sludge characterisation on pyrolysis outputs

Siqi Xu¹, Peter Winter², Yadira Bajón Fernández¹, Stuart Wagland¹

¹Cranfield University, Cranfield, United Kingdom. ²Thames Water, Reading, United Kingdom

Siqi Xu

What is your current position?

Doctoral researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Siqi is a doctoral research student at Cranfield University with the Centre for Doctoral Training in Water Infrastructure and Resilience. She is working on the pyrolysis of sewage sludge for Thames Water. She obtained her Master of Engineering in chemical engineering from the University of Cambridge.

Short abstract

The UK water industry is currently exploring pyrolysis as a method of treating sewage sludge due to concerns over recycling sludge to agricultural land. Outputs from pyrolysis can be valorised, including the gas, bio-oil, and biochar. This research presents an updated perspective which investigates the effect of using different types of sewage sludge and their variation over a year. Digested sludge is a relatively consistent feedstock, compared to primary and secondary sludges, for pyrolysis. Differences in the characteristics of pyrolysis outputs may be linked to specific variations in the feedstock sludge.

#1.19

Ammonium nitrate production in a bioscrubber via partial nitrification: assessing the potential of trickling filters

Patricia Gutiérrez Lozano, Marc Spiller, Vincent De Sutter, Siegfried E. Vlaeminck
University of Antwerp, Antwerp, Belgium

Patricia Gutiérrez Lozano

What is your current position?

Predoctoral researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Junior researcher from the group SUSTAIN from the University of Antwerp, Belgium. Colombian environmental engineer and M.Sc. in Water Sustainability: integrating Technology and Nature-based solutions.

Short abstract

This study investigates the potential for utilising trickling filters in bioscrubbers for nitrogen recovery. The reactors demonstrated the capacity to partially nitrify a concentrated influent of 5 g N/L at an average volumetric loading rate of 320 mg N/L_{media}/d (20 °C). These rates were influenced by the start-up strategy with constant salinity and free-ammonia levels. A pH-based feeding regime aided to avoid nitrite accumulation. A maximum loading rate of 550 mg N/L_{media}/d was achieved with higher hydraulic loading rates. This novel approach opens the way for low energy and easy to operate biological nitrogen recovery.

#1.20

Maximizing ammonium nitrogen recovery from liquid fraction of digestate using Air Gap Membrane Distillation (AGMD)

Judith Canellas, Rekha Pich, Carme Bosch, Sandra Casas, xavier martinez
Eurecat, Manresa, Spain

Judith Canellas

What is your current position?

Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Dr Canellas received her M.Sc. and Ph.D. from Cranfield University (UK) for her research on improving ion exchange processes to recover reactive nitrogen from wastewater. This research was conducted in tight collaboration with the five largest water companies in the UK and was continued as part of the EU research project Smart Plant. During research stays at Columbia University (NY, USA), Dr. Canellas focused on using microbiology-based on up-cycling nitrogen to single-cell protein. Funding for Mrs. Canellas' research has been coming from a variety of grants and awards including the Cranfield Mobility Award and a Fulbright UK/US scholarship.

Short abstract

Reactive nitrogen (N_R), a valuable resource, is found in wastewater in high concentrations. Traditional biological processes are energy-intensive and can release harmful NO_x as well as CO_2 emissions. **Membrane distillation offers a more energy-efficient alternative to treat the liquid digestate fraction (LDF).** By utilizing waste heat, this process can produce high concentrations of N_R by selectively transferring only volatile components like water vapor and ammonia through a hydrophobic membrane. **In this study, we investigate the mass transfer mechanisms** between water vapor and ammonia during membrane distillation **to maximize N_R concentration**, paving the way for its efficient upcycling into valuable products.

#1.21

Integration of phosphorus precipitation and membrane distillation for ammonia capture in a single system for dual fertilizer recovery

Bogna Śniatała¹, Dominika Sobotka¹, Marta Ippolito², Francesco Giannici², Giorgio Mannina², Jacek Małkinia¹

¹Gdańsk University of Technology, Gdańsk, Poland. ²University of Palermo, Palermo, Italy

Bogna Śniatała

What is your current position?

PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

MSc Eng. Bogna Śniatała is 3rd year PhD student at Gdansk Tech. Her research focuses on nitrogen and phosphorus removal and recovery from waste streams in reusable forms for closing the macronutrients cycle at wastewater treatment plants.

Short abstract

Integrating struvite precipitation and gas-to-liquid membrane distillation in a single reactor offers high potential for combined nutrient recovery. This study utilized elevated temperature and pH for simultaneous P crystallization and N vaporization. Laboratory tests showed that the maximum N recovery efficiency of 91%, was achieved at pH 10 and 50°C. Under these conditions, P recovery reached 82%, though struvite purity was slightly reduced due to increased N vaporization. Optimization modeling results showed that up to 87%P and 69%N recovery could be achieved at pH of 8.9 and 44.5°C, ensuring efficient nutrient valorization with minimized chemicals and heating demand.

#1.22

Winery wastewater treatment and bioproducts generation using purple phototrophic bacteria in a raceway-type reactor

Francisco Roberto Chavez-Vega, Germán Buitrón

Universidad Nacional Autonoma de Mexico, Instituto de Ingenieria, Queretaro, Mexico

Francisco Roberto Chavez-Vega

What is your current position?

Graduate student

Short biography of the presenter

Roberto Chavez is a graduate student at the National Autonomous University of Mexico. He is interested in bioproducts formation using wastewater and wastes.

Short abstract

Purple phototrophic purple bacteria can assimilate various substrates and produce valuable bioproducts like polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) and 5-aminolevulinic acid (5-ALA), which are useful in agriculture. In this study, winery wastewater that had high organic matter and nitrogen content was treated in a 6L raceway reactor operated in sequencing batch mode. The system maintained microanaerobic conditions, promoting PHA and 5-ALA synthesis while achieving 93% organic matter removal. The process also produced exopolysaccharides, allowing microbial aggregation. This demonstrates the feasibility of using winery effluent for sustainable wastewater treatment and bioproduct production.

#1.23

Packed Bed Biofilm Reactor for robust nitrification in Recirculating Aquaculture System at different salinities.

Saquib Sarosh, Sreenivasan Ramaswami
Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, India

Saquib Sarosh

What is your current position?

Research Scholar

Short biography of the presenter

Saquib Sarosh is a PhD student at the Centre for Sustainable Technologies, Indian Institute of Science (IISc) Bangalore. Before joining IISc, he had worked for about two years as an engineer at the National Fisheries Development Board, Hyderabad, India. Previously, he did an M. Tech in Aquacultural Engineering from the Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, and a B. Tech in Civil Engineering from the Manipal Institute of Technology. His interest lies in the areas of nitrification, ammonia removal, wastewater treatment, sustainable wastewater treatment, aquacultural engineering, and sustainable aquaculture waste management.

Short abstract

A recirculating aquaculture system (RAS) is a sustainable technique that enhances aquaculture production. Ammonia is a critical pollutant in aquafarming, whose removal by nitrification is pivotal for the success of RAS and is the most challenging step. It's well known that higher salinity inhibits nitrification performance. This work shows efficient high-rate nitrification ($\sim 1800 \text{ gN}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\text{d}^{-1}$ vs. $< 100 \text{ gN}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\text{d}^{-1}$ conventionally) using a packed bed biofilm reactor (PBBR) with nitrification efficiency $> 99.7\%$. The effect of salinity (up to 35 g/L) on the nitrification performance was assessed, and even at higher salinities of 35 g/L nitrification efficiency was greater than 99.5 %.

#1.24

Water and nutrient recovery in greenhouse horticulture

Nienke Koeman¹, Tavishi Guleria^{1,2}, Timon Rijnaarts¹, Jolanda van Medevoort³, Emile Cornelissen^{1,2}

¹KWR, Nieuwegein, Netherlands. ²Universiteit Gent, Gent, Belgium. ³WUR, Wageningen, Netherlands

Nienke Koeman

What is your current position?

Senior researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Nienke Koeman is a researcher in the team Water treatment. She is mainly active in the field of industrial water treatment and water treatment in agriculture and horticulture. Nienke has a background in bioprocess technology but has built up a lot of experience with physical-chemical water treatment in recent years. She has extensive experience with industrial water flows such as process water, cooling water and industrial wastewater treatment. She also has a great deal of knowledge about water flows and water treatment in greenhouse horticulture. She is engaged in research and innovations in water reuse, recycling and resource recovery.

Short abstract

Greenhouse horticulture is striving to minimize its environmental impact by closing the water and nutrient cycle. Currently, water is discharged when sodium levels in recirculated irrigation water become too high. This discharged water contains significant amounts of nutrients, with nitrate being the most prevalent. A innovative solution combines monovalent selective electro dialysis (MSED) with selective ion exchange to treat greenhouse wastewater. This treatment process produces three outcomes: water that can be reused in the greenhouse, a nutrient-rich stream for reuse, and a waste stream that can be discharged with minimal environmental impact.

#1.25

The Potential of Resource Recovery at Wastewater Treatment Plants - Full scale case studies

Willie Driessen¹, Tim Hendrickx¹, dhaval mehta¹, ilse van der Linde²

¹Paques Global bv, Balk, Netherlands. ²Fertipaq, Balk, Netherlands

Willie Driessen

What is your current position?

Global technology manager

Short biography of the presenter

Global technology manager at Paques Global bv involved in treatment of industrial and municipal effluent with special focus on resource recovery.

Short abstract

This paper describes various practical examples of recovery of resources from treatment of wastewater.

Municipal as well as industrial full scale case studies demonstrating the potential of resource recovery will be presented. Resources that can be generated from treatment of wastewater are (1) renewable energy, (2) nutrients (3) raw material and (4) purified water. Included are some case studies at which the wastewater treatment plant and the industrial activity are so intertwined, the treatment plant has become an integrated part of the industrial activity.

In the future water reuse and production of bioplastics and polymers (EPS) will become more profound

#1.26

Insights on the integration of hydrothermal carbonization and chemical leaching for simultaneous carbon and phosphorus recovery from aerobic granular sludge

Marta Di Bianca^{1,2,3}, Andrea Salimbeni¹, Tommaso Lotti², Hary Demey Cedeno³, Geert Haarlemmer³

¹RE-CORD, Scarperia e San Piero, Italy. ²Università degli Studi di Firenze, Florence, Italy. ³Univ. Grenoble Alpes, CEA LITEN, DTCH, Laboratoire Réacteurs et Procédés (LRP), Grenoble, France

Marta Di Bianca

What is your current position?

R&D Engineer, PhD candidate

Short biography of the presenter

Marta holds a Master's Degree in Environmental Engineering from the University of Florence. She has been an R&D engineer at RE-CORD (a research centre in Florence) since 2021, working on the application of thermo-chemical processes for the recovery of raw materials from waste in a circular economy perspective. She is currently a PhD candidate in co-tutelle at the University of Florence and at the University of Grenoble, conducting her activities both at RE-CORD's and CEA-Liten's laboratories. Her research focuses on the integration of slow pyrolysis, hydrothermal carbonization and chemical processes for the recovery of raw materials from sewage sludge.

Short abstract

In this work, the hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) of aerobic granular sludge (AGS) was studied, as well as the application of chemical leaching on the AGS-derived HTC solid (hydrochar). By HTC, more than 50% carbon was recovered as hydrochar, and hydrochar chemical leaching enabled to increase the biocoal carbon content by up to 25% compared to the hydrochar and to recover up to 100% of the hydrochar phosphorus. The study showed that the AGS-derived biocoal (up to 62% carbon content) and P-salt (>16% P₂O₅ content) are potentially applicable as a bio-based coal and as a fertilizer precursor respectively.

#1.27

Combined nitrogen and phosphorus removal and recovery from sludge digestate

Jan van den Broek, Gertjan Buffinga
NSI Byosis B.V., Raalte, Netherlands

Jan van den Broek

What is your current position?

Co-founder/managing director

Short biography of the presenter

Co-founder/managing director of NSI Byosis.

Gertjan Buffinga

What is your current position?

NA

Short biography of the presenter

NA

Short abstract

Innovative ammonium stripping technology combines the removal and recovery of nitrogen and phosphorous from sludge digestate in separate fractions

#1.46

Climate-friendly nitrogen management: Partial nitrification/anammox in a rotating biological contactor for urine treatment enabling phosphorus recovery and enhanced centralized treatment

Iris Jiaqi De Corte^{1,2}, Tim Van Winckel^{1,2}, Marijn J. Timmer^{1,2}, Patricia Gutierrez Lozano^{1,2}, Vincent De Sutter^{1,2}, Siegfried E. Vlaeminck^{1,2}

¹Biobased Sustainability Engineering (SUSTAIN), Department of Bioscience Engineering, University of Antwerp, Antwerp, Belgium. ²Centre for Advanced Process Technology for Urban Resource Recovery (CAPTURE), Ghent, Belgium

Iris Jiaqi De Corte

What is your current position?

PhD researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Iris De Corte obtained her bachelor's in Bioscience Engineering at the University of Antwerp, and her master's in Bioscience Engineering – Environmental Technology at the University of Leuven, including a master's thesis at the Biobased Sustainability Engineering (SUSTAIN) group at the University of Antwerp on combined membrane aeration and filtration for wastewater treatment. She won a PhD fellowship by The Research Foundation – Flanders (FWO) and investigates sustainable urban water cycle methods based on source-separated urine, maximizing resource efficiency and environmental sustainability.

Short abstract

The urban water cycle aims at excellent sanitation at minimum environmental impact. Even though resource recovery can contribute, N removal and recovery compete in terms of climate impact, particularly influenced by nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions. Partial nitrification/anammox (PNA) is the most resource-efficient N removal route, being directly applicable to source-separated urine. This study pioneered in assessing N removal from real urine with PNA in a rotating biological contactor. The reactor achieved excellent N removal efficiencies, high process stability, and relatively low N₂O emissions, offering a climate-friendly N management route and enabling P recovery and advantages for centralized sewage treatment.

#2.1

Phosphate Removal and Recovery: Using Moving Bed Ion Exchange for a Circular Economy Solution

Carien Spagnuolo¹, Will McLean², Emma Baillie², Olga Yahorava²

¹Clean TeQ Water, Johannesburg, Australia. ²Clean TeQ Water, Melbourne, Australia

Carien Spagnuolo

What is your current position?

Head of Sales & Marketing

Short biography of the presenter

Carien is the Head of Sales & Marketing for ASX-listed Australian water technology company Clean TeQ Water. In this role she manages Clean TeQ Water's global sales team and is responsible for international growth.

Carien holds a Bachelor's degree in Chemical Engineering as well as a Masters in Business Administration. Most of her career thus far has been spent working in the mining and industrial sectors in South Africa, spanning from engineering to business management roles. She is passionate about creating change in the water sector by championing the principles of waste valorisation and circular economy

Short abstract

Phosphorus recovery is critical in addressing environmental challenges caused by excessive phosphate in water systems. CleanTeQ has developed an advanced phosphate removal and recovery system, piloted in Europe for a multi-national pharmaceutical customer. s system achieves consistent phosphate removal to levels below 1 mg/L while recovering phosphorus as hydroxyapatite, a high-value product with a market worth approximately twice the system's operational cost. This cash-positive approach combines environmental and economic benefits, offering a scalable solution for industries such as wastewater treatment, agriculture, and pharmaceuticals. By transforming waste into valuable resources, this technology supports the global shift toward a circular economy.

#2.2

Optimizing regeneration strategies for sustainable phosphorus recovery using iron oxides

Yuwei Huang^{1,2}, Carlo Belloni¹, Leon Korving¹, Niels van Dijk², Doris van Halem²

¹Wetsus, LEEUWARDEN, Netherlands. ²Delft University of Technology, Delft, Netherlands

Yuwei Huang

What is your current position?

PhD candidate

Short biography of the presenter

Yuwei is a PhD candidate in the Water Management Department at Delft University of Technology and Wetsus. Her study focuses on the development of iron oxide adsorbents and regeneration strategies for phosphate recovery. By analyzing the principles of chemical bonding, her project aims to increase the reusability and sustainability of adsorbents, providing a cost-effective and efficient method for phosphate recovery.

Short abstract

Phosphorus (P) adsorption is an effective strategy for mitigating eutrophication, with regeneration enabling adsorbent reuse across cycles. Neutralization of the adsorbent after alkaline regeneration is critical for maintaining long-term performance but resource-intensive. This study evaluates the impact of regeneration/neutralization strategies on an iron oxide adsorbent over multiple adsorption-regeneration cycles, evaluating the effects of Ca and some other components typically found in wastewaters. Three different neutralization strategies were tested. Results showed that the right neutralization strategy is essential in Ca-containing wastewaters, preserving high P adsorption performances and long-term adsorbent reusability.

#2.3

Phosphate Recovery From Groundwater Treatment Sludge

Tinatin Tkesheliadze^{1,2}, Kaifeng Wang¹, Peter Engelund Holm², Case van Genuchten¹

¹Department of Geochemistry, Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland, Copenhagen, Denmark. ²Department of Plant and Environmental Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Frederiksberg, Denmark

Tinatin Tkesheliadze

What is your current position?

PhD Student

Short biography of the presenter

The presenter is a first year PhD student enrolled at the University of Copenhagen, Department of Plant and Environmental Sciences and employed by the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland. She holds a master's degree in environmental science from the University of Copenhagen.

Short abstract

In this presentation we will report the results of phosphate (P) recovery from arsenic (As)-laden groundwater treatment sludge. We dosed calcium chloride to P-rich solutions remaining after As is extracted from the sludge, to recover P as calcium phosphate (Ca-P). Measurements of dissolved inorganic species using ICP-OES showed that recovering as much P as possible (>60% P), while minimizing As accumulation in the Ca-P solids may be achieved by dosing Ca/P ratio between 1 and 1.7. Structural analysis of the solids indicated all samples had a hydroxyapatite structure, though different experimental conditions resulted in differences in crystallite size.

#2.4

Valorization of sewage sludge for the production of medium chain fatty acids

Hugo Quintana-Álvarez^{1,2}, Leticia Rodríguez-Hernández³, Celia María Castro-Barros¹, Clara Reino¹, Marta Carballa²
¹CETAQUA, Centro Tecnológico del Agua, A Vila da Auga, Santiago de Compostela, Spain. ²CRETUS, Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Santiago de Compostela, Santiago de Compostela, Spain. ³VIAQUA, A Vila da Auga, Santiago de Compostela, Spain

Hugo Quintana-Álvarez

What is your current position?

Project manager and PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

studied a BS in Chemical Engineering and a MS in Environmental Engineering at the University of Santiago de Compostela. After that, I started working as a researcher at CETAQUA, where I am doing my industrial PhD. I have participated in European projects such as ECOVAL, Spanish national projects like Biocenplas and regional projects such as CIGAT Circular, among others. Inside them, I focus my activity in the generation of high value products such as organic acids from waste streams and the generation of biogas from anaerobic digestion.

Short abstract

This work explores biological processes to transform sewage sludge into medium-chain fatty acids (MCFA). A two-stage technology was evaluated to perform fermentation and elongation processes, respectively. The fermentation to obtain volatile fatty acids (VFA) was carried out at pilot scale, while the chain elongation was carried out at laboratory scale using different electron donors (ethanol or methanol). Results showed yields up to 0.3 g COD-VFA/g COD_{feeding} in the fermentation stage and up to 0.3 g COD-MCFA/g COD_{feeding} using ethanol in the second stage. This approach contributes to circular economy principles in the wastewater treatment sectors.

#2.5

Medium-chain carboxylic acid production from winery effluents with in-situ extraction

Germán Buitrón, Sharon B. Villegas-Rodríguez

Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Instituto de Ingeniería, Querétaro, México

Germán Buitrón

What is your current position?

Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Germán Buitrón works at the Institute of Engineering of the National Autonomous University of Mexico. The research interests are focussed on value-added products recovery from wastewater and waste.

Short abstract

This study explored medium-chain carboxylic acid (MCCA) production from winery effluents using native microbiota and ruminal fluid as inoculum. The process was conducted in a sequencing batch reactor (3 L) at pH 6 and 35°C. After each cycle, a liquid-liquid extraction was performed. Results showed stable MCCA production, with hexanoic acid reaching 7.2 g/L. MCCA separation improved productivity from 206 to 728 mg/L·d. It was observed that pH variations influence the metabolic pathway. Phylogenetic analysis indicated that a neutral pH (6.5-7) supported more diverse microbial communities than an acidic pH (5-6).

#2.6

Targeting medium chain carboxylates in the cofermentation of cellulose and xylan

Juan Iglesias-Riobó, Anton Rial-Garcia, Miguel Mauricio-Iglesias, [Marta Carballa](#)
University of Santiago de Compostela, Santiago de Compostela, Spain

Marta Carballa

What is your current position?

Associate Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Associate Professor in the Department of Chemical Engineering at the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain). She holds a Degree in Chemical Engineering (2001) and a PhD in Chemical and Environmental Engineering (2005). She belongs to CRETUS (Center for Cross Research in Environmental Technologies). Her current research interests include: target volatile fatty acid production by mixed culture anaerobic fermentation and biotransformation mechanisms of organic micropollutants during biological wastewater and sludge treatment processes.

Short abstract

This study explores the production of medium chain carboxylates (MCC) from lignocellulosic biomass using mixed-culture anaerobic fermentation. Hydraulic retention time (HRT), volume exchange ratio (VER) and reactor configuration were evaluated to enhance hydrolysis and lactate availability. The most restrictive conditions of SBR system (VER70%; HRT2.9 days) improved butyrate yield (0.14 Cmol/Cmol-s) in detriment of substrate conversion (80%). The two-stage reactor favoured propionate formation, while the sequential fed-batch reactor led to the highest caproic acid yield (0.09 Cmol/Cmol-s). Ongoing work is focused on increasing MCC production in the sequential fed-batch reactor and validating these results by fermenting corn stover.

#2.7

Maximizing carbon fixation by H₂-enhanced mixotrophy in sugars fermentation: insights from metabolic energy-based modelling

Arianna Catenacci^{1,2}, Alberte Regueira¹, Miguel Mauricio-Iglesias¹, Andrea Turolla², Elena Ficara², Francesca Malpei², Roberto Canziani², Juan Manuel Lema¹

¹CRETUS, Department of Chemical Engineering, Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, Santiago de Compostela, Spain. ²Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Politecnico di Milano, Milano, Italy

Arianna Catenacci

What is your current position?

Junior Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Arianna Catenacci received her PhD in Environmental Engineering from Politecnico di Milano in 2014, with a thesis on heavy metal removal from water and a research stay at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill. From 2014 to 2017, she worked in environmental consulting, before returning to academia as a postdoc researcher focusing on anaerobic processes for energy and resource recovery. Since 2022, she has been a Junior Researcher and Teaching Assistant at Politecnico di Milano. In 2024, she was a Visiting Researcher at the University of Santiago de Compostela, studying metabolic energy-based models for H₂-enhanced glucose fermentation.

Short abstract

Sugar-based mixed culture fermentation (MCF) processes face economic challenges due to low conversion efficiency and carbon loss as CO₂. Providing H₂ can shift the process from heterotrophic to mixotrophic fermentation, enhancing carbon capture. This study developed a metabolic energy-based model for co-fermenting glucose and H₂ to explore the impact of mixotrophy on MCF. The model included hydrogen oxidation to NADH and the Wood-Ljungdahl Pathway for acetate production. Results showed homoacetogenesis as the preferred H₂ utilization pathway, boosting carbon capture by 16-19% depending on environmental conditions. Planned experiments will validate the model and refine its predictions for optimizing MCF performance.

#2.8

Integrating Carbon Sequestration and Energy Recovery: A Multifactorial Approach to Optimize Biochar as an Electrode Material for Microbial Electrolysis Cells

Rouven Metz¹, Nazli Pelin Kocatürk Schumacher¹, John Morken¹, Sven Kerzenmacher^{2,3}

¹Norwegian University of Life Science (NMBU), Ås, Norway. ²Center for Environmental Research and Sustainable Technology (UFT), University of Bremen, Bremen, Germany. ³MAPEX Center for Materials and Processes, University of Bremen, Bremen, Germany

Rouven Metz

What is your current position?

PostDoc

Short biography of the presenter

PostDoc in the Resource Recovery group at the Norwegian University of Life Science (NMBU), Norway

PostDoc project: bioelectrochemical systems and resource recovery

Visiting researcher/ stipend in Soil Chemistry group at ETH Zurich, Switzerland

PhD in Environmental Geoscience (EDGE) group at University of Vienna, Austria

PhD project: P and Fe availability from vivianite

Short abstract

Wastewater treatment (WWT) is energy intensive and emits significant CO₂. Microbial electrolysis cells (MECs) enable energy recovery during WWT, but require cost-effective electrode materials. Biochar, derived from organic waste, offers a sustainable alternative. To gain a critical understanding of its suitability as an electrode material, eight biochars were synthesized, varying feedstock and pyrolysis conditions, and tested in MECs. The synthesized biochars achieved limiting current densities (0.04-0.25 mA cm⁻²) comparable to conventional materials. Key synthesis factors affecting performance were identified, allowing for optimization. Biochar demonstrates potential as MEC electrode material, addressing key challenges in WWT applications.

#2.9

The interactions and contributions among bio-anode, bio-cathode, and suspension in hybrid microbial electrolysis cells-anaerobic digestion (MEC-AD)

Xue-Ting WANG¹, Xue Xing¹, Nanqi Ren¹, Duu-Jong Lee², Chuan Chen¹

¹Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin, China. ²City University of Hong Kong, HongKong, China

Xue-Ting WANG

What is your current position?

Associate Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Xue-Ting Wang is an Associate Researcher at Harbin Institute of Technology. Her research focuses on waste-to-energy conversion and resource recovery. She has published 20 SCI papers and led three national-level research projects. Her work aims to develop sustainable technologies for efficient waste utilization and renewable energy production.

Short abstract

The MEC-AD hybrid system enhances methane production, but the roles of bio-electrodes and suspension remain unclear. This study investigated their contributions by transferring each component into blank bioreactors. After four hours, RMEC-A, RMEC-C, and RMEC-S produced 68.5%, 2%, and 11% of total methane, confirming the bio-anode's dominant role. The bio-anode facilitated mixotrophic methanogenesis, while the bio-cathode enhanced ethanol fermentation and acetogenesis, reducing propionate accumulation by 85%. The suspension exhibited strong fermentation but weak methanogenesis. These findings provide insights into optimizing MEC-AD performance, boosting methane productivity, and minimizing propionate accumulation.

#2.10

Sulfide and carbonate as barriers in vivianite formation and their relevance in different matrices

Sophie Banke^{1,2}, Thomas Prot¹, Leon Korving¹, Mark C. M. van Loosdrecht²

¹Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ²TU Delft, Delft, Netherlands

Sophie Banke

What is your current position?

PhD candidate

Short biography of the presenter

Sophie is a 4th year PhD at Wetsus and TU Delft. She studied chemistry at Freiburg university, Haute Alsace university and Dresden technical university. She enjoys looking at the basics of chemistry and applying them to complex systems like sewage sludge, manure, and lake sediments.

Short abstract

Vivianite ($\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 8 \text{H}_2\text{O}$) is a promising mineral in phosphorus (P) recovery from iron (Fe) coagulated digested sludge. It also occurs naturally in lake sediments and could play a role in phosphate recovery from manure. However, its formation efficiency varies in the three matrices. One limiting factor is the amount of sulfur (S) since iron sulfide formation is energetically favored over vivianite formation. At high enough concentrations, carbonate can also inhibit vivianite formation, as can be the case in manure.

#2.11

Electrochemical pH control for K-struvite recovery from denitrified swine manure effluent

Emma Company Masó^{1,2}, Emma Dessì³, Alba Ceballos-Escalera², Albert Magrí², Narcís Pous², Jesus Colprim²

¹LEQUIA - Universitat de Girona, Girona, Spain. ²Laboratory of Chemical and Environmental Engineering (LEQUIA), Institute of the Environment, Universitat de Girona, C/ Maria Aurèlia Capmany 69, E-17003, Girona, Catalonia, Spain., Girona, Spain. ³University of Cagliari, Department of Civil Environmental Engineering and Architecture (DICAAR), Cagliari, Sardinia, Italy., Cagliari, Italy

Emma Company Masó

What is your current position?

Ph.D student

Short biography of the presenter

I am a PhD student at the Laboratory of Chemical and Environmental Engineering (LEQUIA) of Universitat de Girona (Catalonia, Spain).

My research focuses on the recovery of nutrients, particularly nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium, as struvite and K-struvite fertilizers from swine manure through electrochemical-mediated precipitation.

Short abstract

After nitrogen (N) removal from swine manure, phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) can be recovered as K-struvite, a slow-release fertiliser, increasing pH to 10 – 11.5. The pH is typically increased through chemical reagent addition, which is easy to handle but can increase the concentration of ions and result in the formation of low-quality fertilisers. As an alternative approach, this work employs electrochemical-mediated precipitation as a method for pH control through water electrolysis. The energy applied in a two-chamber electrolytic cell generates hydroxyl ions at the cathode, which promote precipitation, and protons at the anode, which neutralize the exhausted effluent.

#2.12

Enhancing phosphorus release and recovery from waste activated sludge by citric acid treatment and cyclic extraction

Fangyue Peng, Weihua He, Dandan Liang, Dongyi Li, Yujie Feng
Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin, China

Fangyue Peng

What is your current position?

PhD Candidate

Short biography of the presenter

Fangyue Peng is a PhD candidate in Environmental Science and Engineering at Harbin Institute of Technology. She specializes in resource recovery, solid waste management, and anaerobic digestion. Her research focuses on developing integrated processes for efficient carbon and phosphorus recovery from sewage sludge, coupled with purification and valorization strategies for phosphorus products.

Short abstract

The role of citric acid in enhancing phosphorus release from WAS was investigated. With the CA dosage increasing from 0.08 to 0.32 g/gTS, the concentration of P reached 698 mg/L. The relative release efficiency of Fe-P and Al-P was enhanced, contributing to 82.4% and 85.6%. Apatite P was almost released under acidic conditions, with the RRE achieving 93.1%. After three continuous acid recycling cycles, the release efficiency of TSP increased to 73.0% with the average PO_4^{3-} -P recovery efficiency achieved 98%. This study provided a research basis for the phosphorus recovery from real WAS by cost-effective methods in practice.

#2.13

One step closer – examining the robustness of MMC during PHA-production from residual streams of the food industry

Cora Laumeyer, Julia Zimmer, Heidrun Steinmetz
University Kaiserslautern-Landau, Kaiserslautern, Germany

Cora Laumeyer

What is your current position?

Research Associate | PhD candidate

Short biography of the presenter

After finishing her studies of environmental engineering in a double degree Masters programme of the KTH Stockholm and the Technical University Darmstadt with a master thesis project on the production of volatile fatty acids from primary sludge and food waste as external carbon source for post-denitrification, she started as a research associate at the department of resource efficient wastewater technology at the University Kaiserslautern-Landau.

In her PhD studies she is now focusing on the production of the biodegradable biopolymer PHA from residual streams with the aim to contribute to a more sustainable future and a solution to plastic pollution!

Short abstract

To enhance circularity within the food industry biodegradable polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) were produced from brewery and fruit juice wastewater in pilot-scale. The suitability of these streams was proven using mixed microbial cultures (MMC) in an enrichment-accumulation approach. Although MMC composition of the initial substrates differed, the relative abundance of potential PHA-producing bacteria increased in all enrichments until day 12 or day 14, with 88.5 % being the maximum reached value. The findings also show that the choice of the residual stream predetermines the biopolymer composition, underscoring the importance of aligning biopolymer characteristics with industry needs through effective communication and control strategies.

#2.14

Applying feast-famine regime for PHA production in hypersaline environment

Serena Falcioni^{1,2}, Alessio Castagnoli³, Elia Biagini¹, Leandro Di Gloria¹, Matteo Ramazzotti¹, Maria Eugenia Suárez-Ojeda², David Gabriel², Giulio Munz¹

¹University of Florence, Florence, Italy. ²Autonomous university of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain. ³University of Pisa, Pisa, Italy

Serena Falcioni

What is your current position?

phd candidate

Short biography of the presenter

phd candidate in the international phd program in Civil and environmental engineering in University of Florence in cotutela with Autonomous university of Barcelona. The topic of the phd thesis is the PHA production through mixed microbial community cultivated in feast-famine regime and uncoupled feeding. The work was framed in the european project "Recycles". Previously she worked with nitrification, high salinity and in autotroph denitrification with sulphide.

Elia Biagini

What is your current position?

scholarship holder

Short biography of the presenter

Scholarship holder in University of Florence, working on soil contamination. During his Erasmus intership, he spend 9 months in the Autonomous university of Barcelona working on his master's thesis that was about PHA production through mixed microbial cultures and modelling of the PHA selection process.

Short abstract

The biological treatment and valorisation of saline wastewater remains challenging. Utilising saline wastewater to produce polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) could lower treatment costs and support a circular economy. PHA, biodegradable and biobased bioplastics, are traditionally produced by specific bacterial strains. Mixed microbial cultures (MMCs) enable PHA production using industrial waste, including saline wastewater, which constitutes 5% of global wastewaters. This study enriched a PHA-accumulating MMC under hypersaline conditions, the highest salinity reported in literature for the selection of a PHA accumulating community. The biomass selected, dominated by *Halomonas*, accumulated PHA, but showed poor settleability.

#2.15

Thermoplastic starch recovery via depolymerization and methane-arrested anaerobic digestion

Weishen Zeng, David Strik, Kasper de Leeuw
Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, Netherlands

Weishen Zeng

What is your current position?

PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

I am a PhD student in the Environmental Technology Group at Wageningen University & Research, specializing in carbon recovery from rich-carbon waste streams through chemical and biological technologies. My research focuses on recycling biodegradable plastics, particularly thermoplastic starch (TPS), using methane-arrested anaerobic digestion. I aim to develop innovative approaches to transform biodegradable plastics into valuable chemicals, such as volatile fatty acids, to promote sustainable waste management and circular resource use.

Short abstract

This study examined the conversion of a commercial thermoplastic starch (TPS) product using methane-arrested anaerobic digestion. First, abiotic TPS depolymerization was tracked, showing accelerated hydrolysis at higher temperatures and impacting TPS morphology, disintegration, and microplastic formation. Next, solid and/or hydrolysed TPS materials were digested into volatile fatty acids (VFA), accumulating 1,4-butanediol, adipate, and terephthalate. Hydrolysis efficiency reached 36.3% over 56 days, with 19.6% of TPS hydrolysates converted into mainly n-butyrate. Starch, polylactic acid copolymer, and its monomers (glucose and lactate) emerged as precursors of VFA. These chemicals are potentially recoverable into new products.

#2.16

Boosting the selective odd-chain carboxylate production from cheese whey

Ana Vázquez-Fernández, Iria Gómez-Torres, Sabela Balboa, Miguel Mauricio-Iglesias, Marta Carballa
CRETUS - University of Santiago de Compostela, Santiago de Compostela, Spain

Ana Vázquez-Fernández

What is your current position?

Postdoctoral researcher

Short biography of the presenter

I obtained a bachelor's degree in Chemical Engineering in University of Santiago de Compostela (USC,2016) and a Master in Biological and Environmental Engineering in Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB,2018). During the Master, I collaborated with the BioremUAB Group (UAB) in the study of bioethanol production using different strains of white-rot fungi. Then, I started my PhD in GENOCOV research group (UAB). My thesis focused on the influence of operational parameters and the substrate organic composition on the acidogenic fermentation of wastewater. From November 2023, I'm working as postdoctoral researcher in the BioGroup (USC) in the targeted VFA production research line.

Short abstract

Selective odd-chain carboxylate (OCCA) production from cheese whey (CW) fermentation was studied in batch tests and in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR), assessing the effect of several operational parameters (pH, OLR, nutrient supplementation and SRT). Slightly acidic pH resulted in higher OCCA molar fractions than neutral pH. Besides, lower OLR or higher SRT in the SBR improved the acidification degree (AD) and OCCA molar fraction. The addition of macronutrients only enhanced the AD. Bacterial communities' analyses were carried out in the SBR to understand which microorganisms are uniquely tied to OCCA production.

#2.17

Simultaneous Phenol Removal and Resource Recovery from Phenolic Wastewater by Electrocatalytic Hydrogenation

Zhenao Gu, Chengzhi Hu, Jiuhui Qu

Research Center for Eco-Environmental Sciences, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China

Zhenao Gu

What is your current position?

Associate Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Gu is currently an associate professor at the Research Center for Eco-Environmental Sciences (RCEES), Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS). He earned his Ph.D. degree from CAS in 2020 in environmental engineering. Currently, he serves as a member of the Young Academic Committee at RCEES and as a deputy secretary general at the Chinese Society for Environmental Sciences. Dr. Gu's research interests include electrochemical membrane for water purification, novel catalytic membrane for resource recovery, and environmental applications of nanomaterials.

Short abstract

Phenolic wastewater is highly toxic and usually in high concentrations. In this study, an electrocatalytic hydrogenation (ECH) system with Ru catalyst was developed to selectively transform phenol into cyclohexanol, which possesses high economic value and low toxicity and can be easily recovered. A pseudo-first-order rate constant of 0.135 min^{-1} was observed for ECH of phenol (1 mM), which was 34-fold higher than that of traditional electrochemical oxidation (EO). The ECH technique also showed excellent performance in a wide pH range of 3–11 and with a high concentration of phenol (10 mM).

#2.18

Finding Resource Recovery Pathways with OUTDOOR: Guiding Efficient Process design Exploration

Lucas Van der Hauwaert¹, Mias Sommer Schjønberg², [Alberte Regueira](#)¹, Miguel Mauricio Iglesias¹

¹USC, Santiago de Compostela, Spain. ²SDU, Odense, Denmark

Lucas Van der Hauwaert

What is your current position?

PhD Candidate

Short biography of the presenter

I hold a master's degree in Environmental Engineering from the University of Gent. Currently I'm pursuing a PhD in Chemical and Environmental Engineering at USC. My research focuses on the computer-aided design of biorefineries, where I develop and apply mathematical models to key processing units and optimize processing routes using superstructure optimization techniques. By leveraging these models and techniques, my work aims to unlock the potential of biorefineries and enhance the efficiency and environmental sustainability of biomass conversion.

Alberte Regueira

What is your current position?

Associate Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Alberte obtained a Phd on modelling mixed-culture fermentations for the production of volatile fatty acids at the University of Santiago de Compostela in 2020. Soon after, he moved to Ghent University, where he worked in chain elongation processes for high-value carboxylic acids production. Since 2023, he is an Assistant Professor at the Chemical Engineering Department (Universidade de Santiago de Compostela). His main research interests are centred on open culture fermentation processes for carbon recovery from wastes with an emphasis on understanding the mechanisms controlling the process both from an experimental and modelling perspective.

Short abstract

OUTDOOR is an open-source software designed to simplify superstructure optimization for the early stage of process design. It features a user-friendly interface that allows users to easily design valorization pathways for waste streams without advanced coding skills. By integrating advanced optimization techniques and Life Cycle Assessment, OUTDOOR facilitates the identification of economically and environmentally optimal processing pathways. A case study on tomato pomace valorization showcases its ability to address multiple stakeholder perspectives, supporting sustainable resource recovery. OUTDOOR aims to make superstructure optimization accessible, empowering users to design optimal and sustainable valorization processes.

#2.19

Valorization of Industrial Side Streams from Enzyme Production for PHA Production in a 2-Step Process

Isabell Eriksen¹, Cristiano Varrone¹, Kasper Kjellberg²

¹Aalborg University, Aalborg, Denmark. ²Novonosis, Kalundborg, Denmark

Isabell Eriksen

What is your current position?

PhD fellow

Short biography of the presenter

Isabell is a PhD fellow specializing in waste valorization primarily through fermentation processes. Their work focuses on methods for PHA production from industrial waste feedstocks through mixed culture fermentation. They are currently exploring how VFA production from complex protein-rich waste can be optimized using Design of Experiments and statistical analysis.

Short abstract

This study investigates a two-step process for polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) production using a protein-rich industrial side stream from commercial enzyme production as feedstock, addressing a gap in sustainable PHA production, which has primarily relied on carbohydrate-rich side streams. In the first step, volatile fatty acids (VFAs) are produced through acidogenic fermentation with an enriched mixed microbial culture. These VFAs then serve as substrates in the PHA production phase, also using an enriched mixed microbial culture. This approach aligns with circular bioeconomy principles and offers a potential pathway for biobased, biodegradable plastic alternatives.

#2.20

PHA2USE – Towards the commercial production of a natural alternative to plastics from organic side streams.

Bart Joosse¹, João Sousa²

¹Waterschap Brabantse Delta, Breda, Netherlands. ²Paques Biomaterials B.V., Balk, Netherlands

Bart Joosse

What is your current position?

Senior Process Engineer

Short biography of the presenter

Bart Joosse has a background in biotechnology at the Delft University of Technology. He now works as a senior process engineer at Waterschap Brabantse Delta, a water authority in the south of The Netherlands. Resource recovery and innovative process optimizations are his main focus areas. This includes work on PHA production and vivianite recovery from sewage sludge, and N₂O emission reduction.

Short abstract

The Dutch government and water authorities aim to be fully circular by 2050, focusing on extracting valuable resources from sewage sludge, such as a biodegradable natural alternative to plastics. This material offers higher societal value and meets the growing demand for plastics without persistent microplastics and reduced CO₂ emissions. In 2020, five water authorities, STOWA, HVC, and Paques Biomaterials launched the PHA2USE project to scale up this development. A pilot plant in Dordrecht produced 215 kg of Caleyda[®], a fully biodegradable plastic substitute. The project has provided insights into scaling and shows the growing demand for an alternative to plastics.

#2.21

Long-term production of bioplastics from cyanobacteria microbiomes

Beatriz Altamira-Algarra, Artai Lage, Lin Sun, Joan García, Estel Rueda, [Fabiana Passos](#), Eva González-Flo
Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain

Fabiana Passos

What is your current position?

Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Fabiana Passos is professor and researcher at the Environmental Engineering and Microbiology Group (GEMMA) from the Technical University of Catalonia (Spain). Her research is mainly focused on waste and wastewater treatment technologies for recovering bioproducts and bioenergy.

Short abstract

Polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) are the only bioplastics that can fully biodegrade under all possible of environmental conditions. Currently, commercial PHA production process is undertaken by heterotrophic microorganisms with high demands of energy, substrates and clean high-quality water. Long-term adapted cyanobacteria-rich microbiomes isolated from natural environments were able to accumulate steadily 25-28%_{dcw} of PHA in alternate cycles of growth and accumulation during over 160 days. This novel proposed PHA production process using photoautotrophic microorganisms eliminates the need for aeration and high substrate demands from conventional bioplastic approach. Moreover, it may be integrated in waste and wastewater treatment systems.

#2.22

Electrochemical carbon capture with anion exchange membrane electrode assembly allows production of a tunable CO₂:H₂ mixture at low energy input

[Mu Lin](#)

Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, Netherlands

Mu Lin

What is your current position?

Ph.D. researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Mu Lin is a Ph.D. researcher specializing in electrochemical carbon capture. His work focuses on developing energy-efficient CO₂ separation processes using membrane electrochemistry and pH swing optimization. He explores novel anion-exchange membrane systems to reduce energy consumption and enable CO₂ conversion pathways.

Short abstract

We present a novel electrochemical carbon capture system using an anion exchange membrane electrode assembly (AEMEA) with an amine-based CO₂ capture and pH buffer solution. This design significantly reduces energy consumption, requiring only 21 kJ/mol—eight times lower than a similar CEM-based system—by narrowing the pH swing range. Additionally, a tunable H₂:CO₂ gas mix (1:1 to 1:4) is generated, supporting carbon conversion processes like biomethanation. The system maintains 70% solvent capacity over 10 cycles, demonstrating stability and efficiency in continuous operation.

#2.23

Waste upgrade by autothermal torrefaction at industrial scale

Martijn Dekker, Chaitanya Bhatraju
Perpetual Next, Amsterdam, Netherlands

Martijn Dekker

What is your current position?

CTO

Short biography of the presenter

PhD Physics. R&D on Displays, Blu-Ray, EUV, Consumer life style products. CTO and CEO of LED companies Lemnis, Carus and Seaborough. MD and CTO of torrefaction companies CEG and Perpetual Next.

Short abstract

Torrefaction is a thermo-chemical process to upgrade organic waste streams, such as digestates. Key to an economically feasible application of the process is to use the released energy to dry the feedstock. Ideally, no additional heat source is required. The char that results from the process is high in nutrients and can be used for soil improvement, carbon sequestration or as required additive to enrich the ash content for entrained flow gasification of biomass.

In this presentation we will show results for various waste streams and quantify the maximum moisture content that can be processed autothermally for various process settings.

#2.24

Simultaneous Wastewater denitrification and Biogas Desulfurization by Membrane Biofilm Reactor: Operational Performance and Metabolic Mechanisms

Wei Wang

Harbin institute of technology, Harbin, China

Wei Wang

What is your current position?

assistant professor

Short biography of the presenter

Wei Wang, female, born in December 1993, holds a PhD in Engineering and a postdoctoral fellow at Harbin Institute of Technology. The main research directions are green and low-carbon wastewater treatment technology and resource utilization, carbon nitrogen sulfur cycling in water systems, and greenhouse gas emission reduction. As the person in charge, I have led 3 national level projects such as the National Natural Science Foundation and the Key Research and Development Program sub projects. As major participant, I have undertaken 5 national level projects such as the National Key Research and Development Program and the National Natural Science Foundation.

Short abstract

The SBR-MBfR and EGSB-MBfR systems coupling biogas desulfurization and methane-driven denitrification for wastewater treatment has been developed in this study. Both systems achieved >90% nitrate and >99% H₂S removal within a 5-day cycle. SBR-MBfR showed higher denitrification efficiency and sludge activity than EGSB-MBfR, with greater autotrophic denitrification contribution. Microbial analysis revealed dominant phyla (e.g., Pseudomonadota, Chloroflexota) and genera (e.g., Candidatus Metallomirabilis, Thiobacillus) linked to carbon, nitrogen, and sulfur metabolism. Moreover, 19 machine learning models were used for SDMO operation data training and random forest regressor was demonstrated to be the optimal model. The systems offered promising applications under low-carbon policies.

#3.1

From waste to animal feed: microbial protein production from biogas using methanotrophs

Patricia Mohedano Caballero^{1,2}, Patricia Ruiz Ruiz^{1,2}, Jo De Vrieze^{1,2}

¹Centre for Microbial Ecology and Technology (CMET), Ghent University, Gent, Belgium. ²Centre for Advanced Process Technology for Urban Resource recovery (CAPTURE), Gent, Belgium

Patricia Mohedano Caballero

What is your current position?

PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

Patricia Mohedano Caballero is a doctoral student at the Centre for Microbial Ecology and Technology from Ghent University (Belgium). She received a master's degree in Environmental Engineering and Technology from the Erasmus Mundus joint program between Prague University of Chemistry and Technology (Czech Republic), IHE Delft Institute for Water Education (Netherlands) and Ghent University (Belgium). Her MSc. project was focused on the development of methanotroph-microalgae enrichments from saline environments to produce ectoine utilizing biogas as its only carbon source. Her current research focuses on developing various strategies to increase the value of biogas through microbial-based technologies.

Short abstract

The global population reached 8 billion in 2022, projected to rise to 10 billion by 2050 with a 63% increase in protein demand driven by higher living standards. This growth raises food security concerns, emphasizing the need for sustainable protein alternatives. Microbial protein has emerged as a promising solution. This study explores methanotrophic protein production from *Methylomonas methanica* in a 5-L bubble column reactor using methane from biogas as sole carbon source. The findings obtained highlight the potential of methanotrophic bacteria as a low-cost and sustainable protein source for animal feed, addressing global protein shortages while contributing to biogas valorisation.

#3.2

Transforming harvested sewer cellulose into a glucose solution.

Bob de Boer¹, Coos Wessels², Ian Jordens³

¹Hoogheemraadschap Hollands Noorderkwartier, Heerhugowaard, Netherlands. ²CirTec B.V., Purmerend, Netherlands.

³Recell group B.V., Leek, Netherlands

Bob de Boer

What is your current position?

Policy advisor in sustainability

Short biography of the presenter

Bob de Boer studied Civil Engineering at the Technical University in Delft. He started working at Grontmij/Sweco, designing new sewer systems for housing area's and calculating on wastewater discharge. After seven years he stepped over to the water authority of Noord-Holland, first leading projects in the development phase and later as a advisor on sustainability and circular economy.

Short abstract

One of the purification steps at a wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) is the removal of suspend solids. New technics are available to filter wastewater with a sieve before the influent enters the aeration tank of the WTTP. A big amount of the solids that are extracted this way, consists of toilet paper. This cellulose material can be applied as a resource for glucose production, which can be reused in various ways.

#3.3

Resource Recovery Toolbox: accelerating the implementation of circular water solutions through bridging knowledge and practice

Daniel Ddiba

Stockholm Environment Institute, Stockholm, Sweden

Daniel Ddiba

What is your current position?

Research Fellow

Short biography of the presenter

Dr. Daniel Ddiba is a Research Fellow at the Stockholm Environment Institute with expertise in resource recovery, circular economy solutions, and sustainable urban sanitation. He leads the development of the Resource Recovery Toolbox, an innovative open access platform bridging knowledge and practice to accelerate circular water and waste management solutions. Daniel has over a decade of experience working on how to make urban sanitation and waste management systems more effective, more circular and more climate-smart through research and capacity-building initiatives. Daniel holds a PhD in Planning and Decision Analysis from KTH Royal Institute of Technology.

Short abstract

Urban areas are increasingly seeking to recover resources like water, energy, and nutrients from wastewater, but the lack of accessible decision-support tools hinders implementation. The open-access Resource Recovery Toolbox addresses this by collating and curating tools—such as datasets, design tools, software, and case studies—previously scattered across various platforms. Developed in collaboration with Dotwerkstatt and Baobab Tech, it features advanced search functions and an AI-powered chat interface, enhancing tool accessibility and discoverability for wastewater management professionals. This presentation will discuss the Toolbox's development, features, and how it bridges knowledge and practice to accelerate the implementation of circular water solutions.

#3.4

A Holistic Approach to Sustainable Brine Management. IMPORTANT: ABSTRACT IS AN INTRODUCTORY PIECE WHICH ADDS TO ABSTRACT: VALORIZATION OF COMPONENTS AND WATER IN RO CONCENTRATES - DE WAAL ET AL. 2024

Joshua de Jong^{1,2}, Jacqueline de Danschutter¹, Jouke Boorsma¹

¹AquaMinerals, Nieuwegein, Netherlands. ²University of Amsterdam, Amsterdam, Netherlands

Joshua de Jong

What is your current position?

Business developer / Business intelligence Specialist

Short biography of the presenter

I have a background in industrial engineering and management. During my studies, I interned at AquaMinerals, researching critical success factors in circular supply chains. Afterward, I completed a traineeship there, deepening my expertise in resource management, business development, and project management. Since 2024, I have worked as a business developer and business intelligence specialist at AquaMinerals, focusing on circular materials and data infrastructure. My research includes disruptions in chemical supply chains, the subject of this abstract. Additionally, I am pursuing an MBA at the University of Amsterdam to further expand my skills and knowledge.

Short abstract

The increasing adoption of Reverse Osmosis for drinking water production addresses growing water scarcity and pollution but generates brine streams rich in pollutants like PFAS, OMP's and microplastics, posing significant environmental challenges. Current disposal methods, such as discharge or injection, are unsustainable and don't have a positive impact on ecosystems. Additionally, valuable minerals aren't recovered. As stricter regulations emerge, a holistic approach is essential. Collaboration among stakeholders, including water companies, regulators, and knowledge institutions, is crucial to ensure safe access to water. The development of sustainable brine management is key in order to recover valuable resources and mitigate negative environmental impacts.

#3.5

SmartBrine: Simulating the nanofiltration process of Seawater Reverse Osmosis (SWRO) brine as pre-treatment option for disinfectant production by electrochlorination, as preliminary study for brine valorisation in Fortaleza's desalination plants (Brazil).

Esther J. de Kroon¹, Silvano P. Pereira^{2,3}, Mariko A. Carneiro^{4,5,1}, Hamed Rastegarian⁶, Bárbara Vital^{7,8}, Luewton L.F. Agostinho^{1,7}

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Esther J. de Kroon

What is your current position?

Lecturer-/researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Esther de Kroon has a background in Environmental Sciences and Chemical Engineering, with a specialization in Water Technology. After completing the Bachelor's degree regarding these two fields of study, she continued her studies with a Master's degree in Water Technology, during which she focused her research on vortex-based aeration systems, micropollutant degradation by plasma treatment and nanofiltration systems for SWRO brine pre-treatment. She is currently working as a researcher at the research group of Water Technology of NHL Stenden University of Applied Sciences, with the main focus on physical-chemical processes in water technology.

Short abstract

Brine valorisation can reduce environmental impacts of coastal brine discharge from desalination plants while promoting circularity. From a wider perspective, **SmartBrine** aims to explore several technology routes for (industrial) implementation and ultimately work towards an integrated brine valorisation strategy.

One such technology is electrochlorination for disinfectant production, for which the use of SWRO brine is a novel concept and requires further specification. Nanofiltration was hypothesized as a possible pre-treatment option, capable of separating divalent and monovalent ions. In this preliminary study, the nanofiltration process was simulated to evaluate its capacity of producing feedwaters in accordance with electrochlorination feed requirements.

#3.6

Strategies for the valorisation of brine streams from water reuse in the paper industry - *Results and insights from pilot testing.*

Tuur van den Eijnde¹, Yannick Severin¹, Sem Schrijer¹, Nicole Pernot², Timon Rijnaarts³, Simon Grasman⁴, Frank Oesterholt³, Danny Harmsen³, Kees Roest³, Wilbert Menkveld¹

¹Nijhuis Saur Industries, Doetinchem, Netherlands. ²Industriewater Eerbeek, Eerbeek, Netherlands. ³KWR, Nieuwegein, Netherlands. ⁴Redstack, Herenveen, Netherlands

Tuur van den Eijnde

What is your current position?

R&D Team Leader Technology Development

Short biography of the presenter

Tuur van den Eijnde is the Lead for Technology Development at Nijhuis Saur Industries, specializing in industrial wastewater treatment with a strong focus on resource recovery and water reuse. With extensive experience in developing and implementing innovative treatment technologies, he has contributed to projects addressing micropollutant removal, chemical-free nitrogen recovery, metal recovery, and chemical recovery from CIP (Cleaning in Place) processes.

Tuur is dedicated to advancing sustainable solutions that enhance efficiency while reducing environmental impact. His work supports Nijhuis Saur Industries' mission to provide smart, resilient water treatment strategies, helping industries transition toward circular and sustainable water management.

Yannick Severin

What is your current position?

Team Leader Water Consultancy

Short biography of the presenter

Yannick Severin is a passionate water technology engineer, spearheading consultancy at a leading water solutions provider. With expertise across critical domains — wastewater treatment, water reuse, energy recovery, and nutrient recovery — Yannick drives sustainable innovation and circular economy initiatives. Known for bridging technical knowledge with strategic insight, he works closely with stakeholders to implement transformative solutions in water management. His work aligns closely with the International Water Association's mission to advance water sustainability and resilience.

Short abstract

In this work, the results of a long-term evaluation on pilot scale (>10m³/h) are presented for reuse of water in the paper industry.

The aim of this pilot is to show an innovative approach to industrial water reuse, using a combination of treatment technologies that enables efficient water reuse as well as brine valorisation.

This presentation will outline test results and strategies for brine valorisation using a combination of membrane filtration, electrodialysis and ion exchange to convert brine streams into useful chemicals.

Finally, the value of brine valorisation compared to evaporation and discharge is discussed.

#3.7

Robust magnetic vivianite recovery from digested sewage sludge: Evaluating resilience to sludge dry matter and particle size variations

Ha Nguyen^{1,2}, Thomas Prot², Leon Korving², Wokke Wijdeveld², Iulian Dugulan¹, Ekkes Brück¹, Anna Haarala³, Mark van Loosdrecht¹

¹TU Delft, Delft, Netherlands. ²Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ³Kemira, Espoo, Finland

Ha Nguyen

What is your current position?

PhD Researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Ha Nguyen did her bachelor's internship and thesis at Wetsus, focusing on phosphorus recovery from sewage sludge via vivianite. She later pursued a master's double degree in water and environmental engineering from Aalto University and the Technical University of Denmark. Returning to Wetsus three years ago as a PhD researcher, she now investigates "Magnetic vivianite recovery from sewage sludge," building on her earlier work. The PhD was initiated by the collaboration between Wetsus and TU Delft.

Short abstract

Vivianite extraction from digested sludge through magnetic separation is a promising method for phosphorus recovery. This pilot-scale study tested the technology's robustness under varying sludge characteristics, including dry matter, and via that, viscosity and vivianite particle size. Results showed recovery depends on vivianite concentration, with efficient extraction even at higher dry matter (1.8%–3.3%) and hence higher sludge viscosity. Particles of all sizes were recovered, but smaller particles (<10 µm) were recovered at lower rates. This study demonstrates the technology's applicability across different wastewater treatment plants.

#3.8

A novel process for simultaneous phosphorus removal-enrichment-recovery from municipal wastewater with vivianite as recovered product

Lu Li, Xiaoya Wang, Yang Pan, Yong Huang

Suzhou University of Science and Technology, Suzhou, China

Lu Li

What is your current position?

Lecturer

Short biography of the presenter

Field: Biological treatment of wastewater, Phosphorus recovery, Anaerobic biological treatment

Short abstract

A novel approach has been proposed to integrate the biofilm sequencing batch reactor and fluidized bed crystallization process for the **simultaneous removal, enrichment, and recovery of phosphorus** in municipal wastewater. This method ensures that the effluent's phosphorus concentration complies with regulatory standards (≤ 0.5 mg/L) while facilitating the recovery of phosphorus in the form of vivianite. It is **resistant to low phosphorus loads**, with flexible operation and a wide range of process parameters. With a **small demand for carbon sources**, this innovative process holds promise as a sustainable phosphorus recovery model for wastewater treatment facilities.

#3.9

Oxalic acid-mediated production of phosphoric acid and iron coagulant from magnetically recovered vivianite of sewage sludge

Yudong Zhao¹, Leon Korving², Outi Grönfors³, Thomas Prot², Terhi Suopajarvi¹, Tero Luukkonen¹, Henrikki Liimatainen¹
¹University of Oulu, Oulu, Finland. ²Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ³Kemira Oyj, Espoo, Finland

Yudong Zhao

What is your current position?

PhD student

Short biography of the presenter

Yudong is an environmental researcher at the University of Oulu. He is strongly interested in resource recovery in wastewater treatment plants. He earned a master's degree in Environmental Science from Wageningen University in 2021.

In the ReCaP project (Capture, recycling and societal management of phosphorus in the environment), Yudong takes the work of ESR 6 "P and Fe recovery from iron phosphate materials". He will develop new approaches to separate Fe and P in Fe-P rich sludge, and produce iron raw material suitable for reuse and valuable fertilizer.

Short abstract

Magnetic separation of vivianite ($\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$) from sewage sludge can achieve 60% total phosphorus recovery from wastewater influent. To enhance the value of vivianite utilization, effective separation of iron and phosphorus is needed for further valorization. We designed a process (Kemira's patent pending) where vivianite is dissolved in phosphoric acid, followed by precipitation of ferrous iron by oxalic acid. The phosphoric acid concentration in the separated liquid phase can reach 42 wt.% H_3PO_4 , and be reused for vivianite extraction, while the solid oxalate compounds are treated with concentrated sulfuric acid to produce ferrous sulfate and regenerated oxalic acid.

#3.10

Applying CO₂ heat pump in a decentralized source-separated wastewater treatment plant for heat recovery: A model-based study

Shuoguang Yang¹, Robert de Kler¹, Maria Cristina Gagliano¹, Henny C. van der Mei², Bert Hamelers¹, Sybren Gerbens³, David da Silva⁴, Lucía Hernández-Leal¹

¹Wetsus, Leeuwarden, Netherlands. ²UMCG, Groningen, Netherlands. ³Wetterskip Fryslân, Leeuwarden, Netherlands.

⁴Université Gustave Eiffel, Champs-sur-Marne, France

Shuoguang Yang

What is your current position?

PhD researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Shuoguang Yang is currently a PhD researcher at Wetsus. He holds a Master's degree in Environmental Engineering from RWTH Aachen University. His research focuses on energy recovery from greywater and evaluating the microbiological safety of reusing treated greywater.

Short abstract

This work applies a CO₂ heat pump within a decentralized source-separated wastewater treatment pilot plant for energy recovery. A thermodynamic model was developed to compare three heat recovery configurations. Configuration 1 recovers heat to produce 40 °C shower water, Configuration 2 couples wastewater reuse after heat extraction, and Configuration 3 heats the hot water to 60 °C. Configuration 1 can save 18% of the energy used for household hot water and space heating and reduce 69% of CO₂ emissions from heating showering water. Configuration 2 can potentially reuse 80% of household wastewater for non-potable applications besides energy recovery.

#3.11

Resource Recovery and Water Reuse in Benin Republic : Experiences, Lessons learned, and challenges

A. Virgile Onésime Akowanou¹, Mawuli K. H. Bobobee², Aymar Y. Bossa³, Firmin M. Adandedji¹, Cintia Ahouandogbo³, Luc O. C. Sintondji³, Daouda Mama⁴

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⁴Institut National de l'Eau/Université d'Abomey-Calavi, UAC/Calavi, Benin

A. Virgile Onésime Akowanou

What is your current position?

Assistant Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Currently working as Assistant Professor at the National Water Institute at University of Abomey - Calavi, Republic of Benin. My main fields of research are : Water chemistry and Water treatment.

Short abstract

Resource recovery and water reuse offer transformative solutions to water scarcity in developing nations like Benin Republic. This study explores advancements in water reuse through industrial case studies, such as wastewater recovery in textile manufacturing, and reuse of treated wastewater in agriculture to enhance irrigation and soil health. It also addresses the challenges of stakeholder and population acceptance, emphasizing the importance of awareness and inclusive engagement. While progress is evident, barriers such as infrastructure limitations and quality assurance persist. The findings highlight the need for tailored policies and capacity building to scale sustainable water management practices in Benin Republic.

#3.12

Putting a golden lining in sewers: Heterotrophic and autotrophic in-sewer denitrification with nitrified urine for odour control, corrosion management and enhanced centralized treatment

Amber Brouns^{1,2,3}, [Iris J. De Corte](#)^{4,2,3}, Benjamin Horemans^{5,6,7}, Tim Van Winckel^{4,2,8}, Siegfried E. Vlaeminck^{4,2,8}
¹KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium. ²Biobased Sustainability Engineering (SUSTAIN), Department of Bioscience Engineering, University of Antwerp, Groenenborgerlaan 171, 2020 Antwerpen, Belgium, Antwerp, Belgium. ³Centre for Advanced Process Technology for Urban Resource Recovery (CAPTURE), Frieda Saeystraat 1, 9052 Gent, Belgium, Ghent, Belgium. ⁴UAntwerp, Antwerp, Belgium. ⁵KULeuven, Leuven, Belgium. ⁶Division of Chemical Reactor Engineering and Safety, Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering Science, KULeuven, Leuven, Belgium. ⁷Division of Soil and Water Management, Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, KULeuven, Leuven, Belgium. ⁸Centre for Advanced Process Technology for Urban Resource Recovery (CAPTURE), Ghent, Belgium

Amber Brouns

What is your current position?

Master student Bioscience Engineering

Short biography of the presenter

Masterstudent in Bioscience Engineering Environmental Technologies at KULeuven. Currently doing a thesis on the topic 'Sewer Solutions: Valorizing sewers as reactors for resource-efficient urine treatment' in the lab of Sustainable Biobased Engineering (SUSTAIN) at the university of Antwerp.

Iris J. De Corte

What is your current position?

PhD researcher

Short biography of the presenter

Iris De Corte obtained her bachelor's in Bioscience Engineering at the University of Antwerp, and her master's in Bioscience Engineering – Environmental Technology at the University of Leuven, including a master's thesis at the Biobased Sustainability Engineering (SUSTAIN) group at the University of Antwerp on combined membrane aeration and filtration for wastewater treatment. She won a PhD fellowship by The Research Foundation – Flanders (FWO) and investigates sustainable urban water cycle methods based on source-separated urine, maximizing resource efficiency and environmental sustainability.

Siegfried E. Vlaeminck

What is your current position?

Professor Microbial Cleantech and Environmental Systems Engineering

Short biography of the presenter

Siegfried Vlaeminck and his team at the University of Antwerp develop sustainable solutions for water treatment, nutrient management, food production, and CO₂ abatement. As head of Microbial Cleantech and Environmental Systems Analyses Team within the Biobased Sustainability Engineering (SUSTAIN) Research Group, he focuses on resource-efficient water treatment technologies. Key processes studied include nitrification, anammox, high-rate activated sludge, microalgae, and purple bacteria, aimed at producing clean water, nitrate-based solutions, microbial protein, ... Their work also includes LCA and MFA to improve sustainability. Prof. Vlaeminck has contributed to 160+ papers, cited 6000+ times. Follow their progress towards a circular, bio-based economy on LinkedIn.

Short abstract

Sulphurous odours in sewers and pumping stations are commonly controlled by dosing nitrate or ferrous iron, typically derived from non-renewable sources. Nitrified urine offers a sustainable alternative, reducing nitrogen loads on centralized sewage treatment plants, chemical savings, and independence from market acceptance for resource recovery products. To control odour with nitrate, (1) sulphate reduction is inhibited by maintaining anoxic conditions, stimulating heterotrophic denitrification, and (2) H₂S is oxidized via autotrophic denitrification. Explorative batch activity tests elucidate the maximum denitrification rates, inhibitory sulphide levels, and autotrophic-heterotrophic interactions under mixotrophic conditions, contributing to dosing strategies for effective odour control and resource-efficiency.

#3.13

Valorization of wastewater from potato-chips processing industry for biomethane and algae biomass production

Saber A. El-Shafai¹, Dong-Fang Deng², Karim Mohamed Aboelghait¹, Eun-Sung Kan³

¹Water Pollution research, national Research Centre, Cairo, Egypt. ²School of Freshwater Sciences, University of Wisconsin, Milwaukee, Wisconsin 53204,, USA. ³Texas A&M University, Stepehenville, USA

Saber A. El-Shafai

What is your current position?

Professor

Short biography of the presenter

Professor of wastewater treatment and reuse at the department of water pollution research, national Research Centre, Cairo, Egypt. Holding PhD from Wageningen University and UNESCO-IHE Institute (The Netherlands) in wastewater treatment and reuse in fish aquaculture. I have around 30 years' experience in municipal and industrial wastewater treatment using chemical coagulation, electro-chemical and biological treatment technologies. Waste valorization is one of my interest research areas. I have teaching experience in fields related to human activities and the environment and impacts of water pollution on aquatic fauna.

Short abstract

In this study evaluation of an integrated system of two-stages UASB reactor and High-Rate Algal Pond for valorization of wastewater generated from potato-chips processing industry was carried out. The UASB reactor is used to convert organic carbon into biomethane and release nutrients-rich effluent for the HRAP to produce algal biomass. Performance of the UASB reactor for biomethane production and pre-treatment of wastewater was carried out. The efficiency of HRAP for algae recovery and quality of the biomass as fish feed ingredient and/or substrate for biodiesel production was assessed. Cost benefits analysis of the system was carried out.

#3.14

Towards Circular Economy in Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API) Manufacturing Industries: Forward Osmosis for Solvent Recovery and API Concentration

Neelam Sarmah, Prashanth Suresh Kumar
Plaksha University, Mohali, India

Neelam Sarmah

What is your current position?

PhD Student

Short biography of the presenter

I am an early stage researcher in the field of wastewater treatment. My research interest focuses on development of energy efficient technologies for industries to achieve zero liquid discharge. Currently, I am working on development of Forward Osmosis membranes for solvent recovery from active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) manufacturing units.

Short abstract

The pharmaceutical industry faces significant environmental challenges due to the extensive use of organic solvents in API manufacturing. This research proposes a novel solution by integrating Forward Osmosis (FO) with polyethylene-based TFC membranes to reduce solvent consumption and waste generation. By optimizing membrane properties and investigating the impact of membrane permeability on energy consumption, we aim to develop a sustainable and energy-efficient process for API purification. This approach has the potential to significantly reduce the industry's environmental footprint and promote a circular economy.

#3.15

Water, mineral and metal recovery from mine process waters by combining nanofiltration with precipitation and adsorption.

Tatiana Samarina¹, [Viivi Vepsäläinen](#)¹, Mia Pursiainen², Jari Jäntti², Jari Sonninen², Kari Kuuspallo², Outi Laatikainen¹
¹Kajaani University of Applied Sciences, Kajaani, Finland. ²Savonia University of Applied Sciences, Kuopio, Finland

Viivi Vepsäläinen

What is your current position?

Research assistant

Short biography of the presenter

She graduated in 2021 with Master's Degree in Physical Geography and Quaternary Geology (Landscape Ecology specialization) from Stockholm University. From 2022, she has been working as a laboratory and research assistant in laboratory of Applied Geopolymer technologies at Kajaani University of Applied Sciences. Although her primary research interests are in the impacts of land use change and habitat fragmentation on biodiversity, approaches and technologies that facilitate more effective environmental management are also within her area of interest.

Short abstract

The new paradigm of responsible consumption drives industry to seek sustainable sources of materials to support to the green economy transition. By applying extraction processes to concentrates after nanofiltration (NF) membrane treatment rather than to non-concentrated streams, mineral and critical raw material recovery could be energetically more advantageous. Sulfate-containing minerals that are acceptable for construction industry are recovered from the NF membrane concentrate by precipitation of gypsum and ettringite. Metals preconcentrated in the concentrate removed via adsorption on industrial side stream and recovered by acid washing. The proof-of-concept demonstrated in this study intends to facilitate commercial development of 'concentrate mining'.

